

Checklists of the myxomycetes and macromycetes in Turkey

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Abstract. This paper attempts to compile available data on Turkish myxomycetes and macromycetes published between 1915 and February, 2005, and obtained from 294 publications. Two main lists of myxomycetes and macromycetes are given where the taxa are alphabetically arranged. The total number of correct names of species, recorded from Turkey and presented in both checklists, is 1778, including 177 myxomycetes and 1601 macromycetes. For each taxon, references are cited. An index of synonyms based on literature records from Turkey is appended. It includes 671 species and infraspecific taxa. Information about the species distribution in the European or/and Asian parts of Turkey is also given.

Key words: biodiversity, fungal diversity, macromycetes, myxomycetes, taxonomy, Turkey

Introduction

A number of studies on the mycota of Turkey have been published. Contemporary knowledge of the diversity of Turkish myxomycetes and macromycetes is based on a period of 90 years of investigations. In the course of our observation of literature sources we listed 294 scientific works, containing various Turkish records of myxomycetes and macromycetes.

The first contribution on macromycetes from Turkey was published by K. Vlaev in 1915. Baytop (1994) listed 168 publications dealing with Turkish macromycetes. Sesli & Baydar (1995, 1996) presented the first macromycetes checklists, including Russulaceae and Agaricales, respectively. The first checklist of myxomycetes was compiled by Ergül & Dülger (2000). Nevertheless a really complete catalogue of the myxomycetes and macromycetes of Turkey has not been published yet. This situation allows room for many mistakes, sometimes of their multiplication, in mycological papers, especially in some articles concerning new Turkish records. In the past, some species were published as new records many times and in different years by the same or different authors, and in the same or different journals.

The aim of the present study is an attempt to summarize the species of myxomycetes and macromycetes recorded in

Turkey and published in different journals to be a guide for future studies. In addition, we hope that the paper will be helpful for creating a database of the Turkish mycota.

Materials and Methods

Main lists of myxomycetes and macromycetes are created. The taxa are given in alphabetical order: orders within each class, families within each order, etc. The numbers within square brackets following the authors of each species or infraspecific taxon refer to the reference(s) where the taxon is reported. A number [001-288] is assigned to each reference in the section "Bibliography of the contributions to Turkish myxomycetes and macromycetes". The system of the suprageneric taxa is in accordance with Kirk *et al.* (2001). The generic and species treatment of and into different genera follows a lot of recent monographs and particular articles on European fungi. The names of authors of fungal species are abbreviated according to Kirk & Ansell (1992) and Kirk *et al.* (2004).

Because many species have been published under different names, a thesaurus of synonyms is listed separately with references to the correct names used in the main lists of myxomycetes and macromycetes.

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A list of myxomycetes

PROTOSTELIOMYCETES

Protosteliales

Ceratiomyxaceae

Famintzinia fruticulosa (O.F. Müll.) Lado [079, 086, 115, 179a, 259]

MYXOMYCETES

Echinosteliales

Clastodermataceae

Clastoderma debaryanum A. Blytt [079, 179a], *C. pachypus* Nann.-Bremek. [079]

Echinosteliaceae

Echinostelium arboreum H.W. Keller & T.E. Brooks [079], *E. coelocephalum* T.E. Brooks & H.W. Keller [079], *E. colliculosum* K.D. Whitney & H.W. Keller [079, 116], *E. corynophorum* K.D. Whitney [079, 114], *E. cribrarioides* Alexop. [079], *E. elachiston* Alexop. [079, 115], *E. fragile* Nann.-Bremek. [079, 114], *E. ladoi* Pando [190], *E. minutum* de Bary [074, 079, 115, 116, 177, 178, 179a]

Liceales

Cribrariaceae

Cribraria argillacea (Pers. ex J.F. Gmel.) Pers. [082, 086, 177, 179a], *C. aurantiaca* Schrad. [079, 086], *C. cancellata* (Batsch) Nann.-Bremek. [074, 079, 083, 086, 177, 178, 179a, 273], *C. elegans* Berk. & M.A. Curtis [082], *C. intricata* Schrad. [177, 179a], *C. macrocarpa* Schrad. [177, 179a], *C. microcarpa* (Schrad.) Pers. [082, 177, 179a], *C. minutissima* Schwein. [079], *C. tenella* Schrad. [082, 086], *C. violacea* Rex [074, 079, 116], *C. vulgaris* Schrad. [190]

Lindbladia tubulina Fr. [082]

Liceaceae

Licea belmontiana Nann.-Bremek. [190], *L. biforis* Morgan [177, 179a], *L. castanea* G. Lister [079, 178], *L. denudescens* H.W. Keller & T.E. Brooks [079, 116, 178], *L. inconspicua* T.E. Brooks & H.W. Keller [190], *L. kleistobolus* G.W. Martin [079, 115, 116, 179a], *L. minima* Fr. [079, 179a], *L. operculata* (Wingate) G.W. Martin [079, 179a], *L. parasitica* (Zukal) G.W. Martin [079, 179a], *L. pedicellata* (H.C. Gilbert) H.C. Gilbert [079], *L. perexigua* T.E. Brooks & H.W. Keller [190], *L. punctiformis* G.W. Martin [079], *L. pusilla* Schrad. [079, 179a], *L. pygmaea* (Meyl.) Ing [074, 079], *L. synsporos* Nann.-Brem. [179], *L. tenera* E. Jahn [079, 178], *L. tuberculata* G.W. Martin [177, 178], *L. variabilis* Schrad. [179]

Reticulariaceae

Lycogala epidendrum (L.) Fr. [074, 079, 086, 112, 113, 115, 135, 173, 179a, 204, 206, 207, 214, 246, 259, 261, 263], *L. exiguum* Morgan [177, 179a, 190],

L. flavofuscum (Ehrenb.) Rostaf. [079, 086], *L. terrestre* Fr. [164, 259]

Reticularia lycoperdon Bull. [062, 164, 259], *R. splendens* Morgan [079, 107, 112, 113, 246]

Tubulifera arachnoidea Jacq. [082, 177, 179a, 259]

Physarales

Didymiaceae

Diderma chondrioderma (de Bary & Rostaf.) G. Lister [074, 079], *D. hemisphaericum* (Bull.) Hornem. [079, 179a], *D. testaceum* (Schrad.) Pers. [082]

Didymium anellus Morgan [177, 179a], *D. bahiense* Gottsb. [082], *D. crustaceum* Fr. [177, 178], *D. difforme* (Pers.) Gray [079], *D. eximium* Peck [082], *D. floccosum* G.W. Martin, K.S. Thind & Rehill [074, 079], *D. iridis* (Ditmar) Fr. [179], *D. minus* (Lister) Morgan [079], *D. nigripes* (Link) Fr. [082, 177, 179a], *D. quitense* (Pat.) Torrend [079, 116, 178, 179a], *D. squamulosum* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr. [079, 116, 178, 179a]

Mucilago crustacea F.H. Wigg. [079, 080]

Physaraceae

Badhamia affinis Rostaf. [116], *B. capsulifera* (Bull.) Berk. [082], *B. foliicola* Lister [074, 079, 116, 178, 179a], *B. macrocarpa* (Ces.) Rostaf. [079, 178], *B. nitens* Berk. [079], *B. panicea* (Fr.) Rostaf. [079, 116, 178, 179a], *B. utricularis* (Bull.) Berk. [190], *B. versicolor* Lister [079, 116], *B. viridescens* Meyl. [079]

Badhamiopsis ainoae (Yamash.) T.E. Brooks & H.W. Keller [079, 178]

Craterium concinnum Rex [179a], *C. minutum* (Leers) Fr. [082, 086]

Fuligo septica (L.) F.H. Wigg. [079, 082, 084, 086, 179a]

Leocarpus fragilis (Dicks.) Rostaf. [074, 079, 179a]

Physarum album (Bull.) Chevall. [074, 079, 086, 179a, 273], *Ph. auriscalpium* Cooke [115], *Ph. bitectum* G. Lister [079, 116], *Ph. cinereum* (Batsch) Pers. [079, 115, 178, 179a], *Ph. compressum* Alb. & Schwein. [079], *Ph. contextum* (Pers.) Pers. [079, 116], *Ph. decipiens* M.A. Curtis [079, 116, 178, 273], *Ph. flavicomum* Berk. [082, 086], *Ph. leucophaeum* Fr. [079, 178], *Ph. leucopus* Link [178], *Ph. luteolum* Peck [190], *Ph. notabile* T. Macbr. [082, 178], *Ph. oblatum* T. Macbr. [079], *Ph. ovisporum* G. Lister [082], *Ph. pusillum* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) G. Lister [073, 074, 079, 178, 273], *Ph. vernum* Sommerf. [190], *Ph. viride* (Bull.) Pers. [074, 079, 086, 179a]

Protophysarum phloiogenum M. Blackw. & Alexop. [190]

Stemonitales

Stemonitidaceae

Collaria arcyrionema (Rostk.) Nann.-Bremek. [190],

C. lurida (Lister) Nann.-Bremek [079, 178, 179a],
C. rubens (Lister) Nann.-Bremek [115]

Comatricha elegans (Racib.) G. Lister [079, 116, 179a],
C. ellae Härk. [079], *C. laxa* Rostaf. [074, 079,
116], *C. nigra* (Pers. ex J.F. Gmel.) J. Schröt. [074,
079, 116, 178, 179a, 273], *C. pulchella* (C. Bab. ex
Berk.) Rostaf. [081, 177, 179a, 273], *C. tenerrima*
(M.A. Curtis) G. Lister [177, 179a]

Diachea leucopodia (Bull.) Rostaf. [079, 116]

Enerthenema papillatum (Pers.) Rostaf. [079, 116,
178, 179a]

Lamproderma arcyrioides (Sommerf.) Rostaf. [079,
115], *L. columbinum* (Pers.) Rostaf. [190], *L.
scintillans* (Berk. & Broome) Morgan [177,
179a]

Macbrideola cornea (G. Lister & Cran) Alexop. [079,
115, 116, 179a], *M. decapillata* H.C. Gilbert [079,
273], *M. martini* (Alexop. & Beneke) Alexop.
[190], *M. scintillans* H.C. Gilbert [082], *M.
synsporos* (Alexop.) Alexop. [079]

Paradiacheopsis acanthodes (Alexop.) Nann.-Bremek.
[076, 177, 179a], *P. cribrata* Nann.-Bremek. [190],
P. fimbriata (G. Lister & Cran) Hertel ex Nann.-
Bremek. [079, 115, 116], *P. microcarpa* (Meyl.)
D.W. Mitch. ex Ing [190], *P. rigida* (Brândză)
Nann.-Bremek. [076, 190], *P. solitaria* (Nann.-
Bremek.) Nann.-Bremek. [076]

Stemonaria irregularis (Rex) Nann.-Brem., R. Sharma
& Y. Yamam. [082]

Stemonitis axifera (Bull.) T. Macbr. [082, 086, 177,
179a], *S. flavogenita* E. Jahn [079, 086, 116],
S. fusca Roth [074, 079, 086, 116, 179a, 259],
S. herbatica Peck [082, 086, 177, 179a, 273], *S.
nigrescens* Rex [079], *S. pallida* Wingate [082,
086], *S. smithii* T. Macbr. [082, 086, 177, 179a],
S. splendens Rostaf. [079, 086], *S. virginensis* Rex
[082, 086]

Stemonitopsis hyperopta (Meyl.) Nann.-Bremek. [079,
178, 179a], *S. microspora* (Lister) Nann.-Bremek.
[078], *S. reticulata* (H.C. Gilbert) Nann.-Bremek.
& Y. Yamam. [079], *S. subcaespitosa* (Peck) Nann.-
Bremek. [082], *S. typhina* (F.H. Wigg.) Nann.-
Bremek. [078, 079, 086, 115]

Symphytocarpus flaccidus (Lister) Ing & Nann.-
Bremek. [075, 079]

Trichiales

Arcyriaceae

Arcyria affinis Rostaf. [082, 086], *A. anulifera* Torrend
[190], *A. cinerea* (Bull.) Pers. [079, 086, 115, 116,
178, 179a], *A. denudata* (L.) Wettst. [079, 086,
115, 179a], *A. ferruginea* Saut. [082], *A. globosa*
Schwein. [177, 179a], *A. incarnata* (Pers. ex J.F.
Gmel.) Pers. [079, 086, 179a, 273], *A. insignis*
Kalchbr. & Cooke [079, 086, 179a], *A. magna*
Rex [177, 179a], *A. minuta* Buchet [077, 079,

082], *A. nigella* Emoto [177, 179a], *A. obvelata*
(Oeder) Onsberg [074, 079, 086, 178, 179a,
259], *A. pomiformis* (Leers) Rostaf. [079, 086,
115, 116, 177, 178, 179a], *A. stipata* (Schwein.)
Lister [082, 086], *A. versicolor* W. Phillips [079,
115, 178, 179a]

Dianemataceae

Calomyxa metallica (Berk.) Nieuwl. [079]

Dianema corticatum Lister [179a], *D. repens* G. Lister
& Cran [082]

Trichiaceae

Hyporhamma calyculata (Speg.) Lado [079, 080, 086],
H. clavata (Pers.) Lado [079, 115], *H. leiocarpa*
(Cooke) Lado [190], *H. minor* (G. Lister) Lado
[190]

Lachnobolus atrus (Alb. & Schwein.) Lado [006, 079,
256]

Metatrichia floriformis (Schwein.) Nann.-Bremek.
[190], *M. vesparium* (Batsch) Nann.-Bremek. ex
G.W. Martin & Alexop. [079, 083, 086]

Oligonema schweinitzii (Berk.) G.W. Martin [179]

Perichaena chrysoesperma (Curr.) Lister [074, 079,
179a], *P. corticalis* (Batsch) Rostaf. [079, 115,
116, 178, 179a], *P. tessellata* G. Lister [190], *P.
vermicularis* (Schwein.) Rostaf. [079, 178]

Trichia affinis de Bary [082, 086], *T. alpina* (R.E. Fr.)
Meyl. [079, 115], *T. botrytis* (J.F. Gmel.) Pers. [079,
086, 178, 179a, 259], *T. contorta* (Ditmar) Rostaf.
var. *contorta* [079, 116], *T. contorta* var. *karstenii*
(Rostaf.) Ing [079, 085], *T. decipiens* (Pers.) T.
Macbr. [079, 086, 115, 178, 179a, 273], *T. erecta*
Rex [177, 179a], *T. favoginea* (Batsch) Pers. [079,
086, 115, 179a], *T. lutescens* (Lister) Lister [079],
T. subfusca Rex [190], *T. varia* (Pers. ex J.F. Gmel.)
Pers. [079, 086]

A list of macromycetes

ASCOMYCETES

Diaporthales

Melanconidaceae

Melogramma spiniferum (Wallr.) De Not. [069]

Helotiales

Bulgariaceae

Bulgaria inquinans (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [006, 131, 173, 214,
221, 228, 236, 254, 256]

Cudoniaceae

Cudonia circinans (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [211]

Spathularia flavida Pers. : Fr. [206, 207, 221, 226,
236]

Dermateaceae

Chlorociboria aeruginosa (Oeder) Seaver ex C.S.
Ramamurthi, Korf & L.R. Batra [001, 031, 173,
217]

- Tapesia fusca* (Pers. : Fr.) Fuckel [203, 259]
 Helotiaceae
Ascocoryne cylichnium (Tul.) Korf [108, 112, 135, 251, 246]
Bisporella citrina (Batsch : Fr.) Korf & S.E. Carp. [025, 108, 112, 113, 135, 203, 206, 207, 228, 239, 246, 248, 252a]
Colpoma quercinum (Pers. : Fr.) Wallr. [173]
Hymenoscyphus calyculus (Sowerby : Fr.) W. Phillips [112, 246]
 Hyaloscyphaceae
Arachnopeziza aurata Fuckel [258]
Lachnum cerinum (Pers. : Fr.) Nannf. [256], *L. niveum* (Hedw.) P. Karst. [259]
Lachnellula arida (W. Phillips) Dennis [066], *L. flavovirens* (Bres.) Dennis [259], *L. subtilissima* (Cooke) Dennis [066, 256, 259]
 Rutstroemiaceae
Rutstroemia echinophila (Bull. : Fr.) Höhn. [108, 112, 113, 246]
 Incertae sedis
Lachnea miniata (Fuckel) Sacc. [098, 109]
 Hypocreales
 Nectriaceae
Nectria cinnabarina (Tode : Fr.) Fr. s. lat. [001, 003, 066, 112, 113, 171, 199, 204, 206, 207, 214, 217, 246, 261, 263, 265], *N. cinnabarina* (Tode : Fr.) Fr. var. *minor* Wollenw. [217], *N. fuckeliana* C. Booth [001, 003, 173, 217], *N. galligena* Bres. [001, 003]
 Hysteriales
 Hysteriaceae
Hysterium pulicare Pers. : Fr. [069]
 Pezizales
 Discinaceae
Discina ancilis (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [036, 037, 239, 248], *D. melaleuca* Bres. [025]
Gyromitra ambigua (P. Karst.) Harmaja [174], *G. esculenta* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [009, 022, 025, 030, 036, 037, 042, 066, 091, 092, 095, 111, 112, 127, 128, 174, 199, 219, 239, 248, 266], *G. gigas* (Krombh.) Cooke [012, 025, 174], *G. infula* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Quél. [189, 227]
 Helvellaceae
Helvella acetabulum (L. : Fr.) Quél. [017, 025, 038, 046, 066, 097, 099, 102, 103, 120, 126, 127, 128, 131, 153, 155, 157, 163, 163a, 168, 198, 203, 205, 206, 207, 221, 236, 239, 248, 266], *H. atra* J. König [204, 206, 207, 220], *H. costifera* Nannf. [163a, 166], *H. crispa* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. [005, 023, 024, 025, 098, 109, 127, 128, 132, 134, 174, 195, 204, 205, 206, 207, 220, 275, 285], *H. dissingii* Korf [240], *H. ephippium* Lév. [153], *H. lactea* Boud. [235, 261, 263], *H. lacunosa* Afzel. : Fr. [007, 009, 010, 011, 015, 025, 039, 046, 056, 060, 062, 064, 098, 099, 102, 103, 109, 120, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 155, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 172, 174, 175, 198, 220, 265, 267, 277], *H. leucomelaena* (Pers.) Nannf. [011, 016, 022, 025, 026, 027, 036, 037, 066, 090, 091, 092, 098, 099, 103, 109, 110, 111, 112, 120, 126, 127, 128, 131, 135, 154, 163a, 166, 168, 174, 198, 199, 203, 239, 248, 260], *H. leucopus* Pers. [007, 009, 011, 025, 093, 099, 102, 103, 112, 120, 126, 127, 128, 131, 134, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 198, 206, 207, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 275, 279], *H. monachella* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. [195], *H. queletii* Bres. [017, 025, 062, 066, 099, 102, 103, 159, 160, 163a, 277], *H. solitaria* (P. Karst.) P. Karst. [012, 172], *H. spadicea* Schaeff. [026, 027, 066, 151, 155, 172, 199]
 Morchellaceae
Disciotis venosa (Pers. : Fr.) Arnould [016, 042, 111, 112, 136, 252a, 285]
Mitrophora semilibera (DC. : Fr.) Lév. [002, 016, 047, 050, 058, 066, 155, 157, 163a, 204, 205, 206, 207, 261, 263, 268a, 274]
Morchella angusticeps Peck [112, 135, 136, 139, 167, 250, 251], *M. costata* (Vent.) Pers. [025, 060, 104, 111, 112, 120, 135, 136, 139, 167, 239, 248, 251, 252a, 267], *M. crassipes* (Vent. : Fr.) Pers. [008, 139], *M. deliciosa* Fr. : Fr. [005, 015, 016, 021, 024, 025, 045, 047, 050, 066, 103, 104, 105, 111, 112, 136, 139, 163a, 166, 167, 180, 182, 183, 184, 187, 199, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 252a, 257], *M. distans* Fr. [103, 104, 111, 112, 135, 136, 139, 167, 239, 248], *M. elata* Fr. : Fr. s. lat. [009, 011, 015, 016, 021, 024, 025, 026, 027, 042, 066, 104, 111, 112, 113, 126, 127, 128, 136, 139, 157, 163a, 167, 195, 205, 206, 207, 239, 244, 248], *M. elata* Fr. : Fr. var. *purpurascens* Krombh. [139, 250], *M. elatoides* Jacquet. var. *elegans* Jacquet. [286a], *M. esculenta* (L. : Fr.) Pers. s. lat. [002, 005, 007, 011, 016, 021, 024, 025, 027, 030, 032, 035, 036, 037, 041, 043, 047, 050, 054, 056, 058, 060, 062, 064, 066, 091, 092, 093, 094, 098, 099, 106, 112, 121, 123, 127, 128, 132, 136, 139, 153, 154, 159, 160, 163a, 166, 167, 168, 169, 175, 182, 184, 187, 189, 193, 199, 203, 205, 206, 207, 239, 248, 252a, 253, 257, 260, 261, 263, 265, 266, 267, 268, 270, 274, 275, 277, 278, 280], *M. esculenta* (L. : Fr.) Pers. var. *umbrina* (Boud.) S. Imai [025, 026, 066, 139, 199, 250, 274], *M. eximia* Boud. [139, 167, 250], *M. inamoena* Boud. [139, 250], *M. intermedia* Boud. [025, 103, 109, 112, 136, 139, 167, 251, 274], *M. pseudoviridis* Jacquet. [286a], [*M. purpurascens* Krombh. var. *ionoviridis* Jacquet. – unclear status] [286a], *M. rielana* Boud. [167], *M. rigida* (Krombh.) Boud. [017, 025, 066, 103,

- 104, 111, 112, 120, 136, 139, 155, 199, 248, 252a], *M. vaporaria* Brond. [286a], *M. vulgaris* (Pers.) Boud. [002, 007, 009, 011, 015, 016, 017, 021, 025, 027, 030, 036, 037, 044, 047, 048, 050, 054, 056, 058, 060, 064, 066, 091, 092, 098, 099, 102, 106, 112, 113, 121, 123, 127, 128, 131, 132, 134, 135, 136, 139, 153, 154, 157, 167, 168, 169, 175, 189, 191, 193, 199, 203, 238, 241, 242, 243, 251, 252a, 260, 261, 263, 265, 267, 268, 275, 277, 278, 280, 288]
- Ptychoverpa bohémica* (Krombh.) Boud. [016, 038, 051, 159, 160]
- Verpa conica* (O.F. Müll. : Fr.) Sw. [016, 025, 042, 112, 132, 134, 136, 163a, 204, 205, 206, 207, 229, 252a, 265, 268a]
- Pezizaceae**
- Pachyella babingtonii* (Berk. & Broome) Boud. [259]
- Peziza ampelina* Quél. [041], *P. amphora* Quél. [203], *P. appianata* (Hedw. : Fr.) Fr. [233], *P. arvernensis* Boud. [066], *P. badia* Pers. : Fr. [098, 189], *P. badiocnifusa* Korf [099, 103, 192, 277], *P. cerea* Sowerby : Fr. [041], *P. coccinea* Jacq. [269], *P. depressa* Pers. [163], *P. domiciliana* Cooke [066], *P. erucaeformis* Batsch [209], *P. granulosa* Schumach. [070, 203], *P. michelii* (Boud.) Dennis. [070], *P. micropus* Pers. : Fr. [286], *P. succosa* Berk. [227], *P. varia* (Hedw. : Fr.) Fr. [066, 199, 258, 259], *P. vesiculosa* Bull. : Fr. [008, 015, 025, 035, 091, 092, 126, 132, 266, 278]
- Sarcosphaera coronaria* (Jacq.) Boud. [011, 017, 022, 025, 027, 064, 065, 066, 091, 092, 095, 112, 113, 122, 132, 154, 157, 166, 168, 169, 173, 174, 196, 197, 199, 203, 214, 239, 241, 243, 248, 260, 268]
- Tirmania pinoyi* (Maire) Malençon [285]
- Pyronemataceae**
- Aleuria aurantia* (Pers.) Fuckel [018, 025, 220, 221, 222, 228, 232, 269]
- Caloscypha fulgens* (Pers. : Fr.) Boud. [002, 016, 024, 025, 026, 066, 113, 157, 180, 203]
- Geopora arenicola* (Lév.) Kers [011, 066, 098, 103, 109, 126, 199], *G. arenosa* (Fuckel) S. Ahmad [155, 157, 166, 172], *G. cooperi* Harkn. f. *cooperi* [247, 252], *G. sumneriana* (Cooke) M. Torre [026, 027, 090, 110, 112, 157, 168, 234, 252a, 265]
- Flavoscypha cantharella* (Boud.) Häffner [025, 227, 228]
- Humaria hemisphaerica* (F.H. Wigg. : Fr.) Fuckel [153, 204, 206, 207, 227, 269]
- Marcellina persoonii* (H. Crouan & P. Crouan) Brumm. [278, 280]
- Otidea cochleata* (Huds.) Fuckel [109, 112], *O. leporina* (Batsch) Fuckel [004, 098, 109]
- Scutellinia scutellata* (L. : Fr.) Lambotte [066, 189, 204, 206, 207]
- Tarzettia catinus* (Holmsk.) Korf & J.K. Rogers [025, 279], *T. cupularis* (L. : Fr.) Svrček [009, 010, 235, 285]
- Rhizinaeae**
- Rhizina undulata* Fr. : Fr. [024, 025, 048]
- Sarcoscyphaceae**
- Pithya vulgaris* Fuckel [067]
- Sarcoscypha coccinea* (Jacq. : Fr.) Sacc. s. lat. [091, 092, 098, 135, 204, 205, 206, 207, 214, 246, 251, 266, 269], *S. hiemalis* (Nees & Bernstein) J. Schröt. [278]
- Terfeziaceae**
- Terfezia arenaria* (Moris) Trappe [009, 120, 124, 131, 152, 172, 188, 260], *T. boudieri* Chatin [066, 099, 100, 101, 103, 105, 110, 154, 277]
- Tuberaceae**
- Choironomyces meandriformis* Vittad. [042]
- Tuber aestivum* Vittad. [043], *T. brumale* Vittad. [196, 260]
- Xylariales**
- Diatrypaeae**
- Diatrype disciformis* (Hoffm. : Fr.) Fr. [206, 207, 258], *D. stigma* (Hoffm. : Fr.) Fr. [170, 214]
- Xylariaceae**
- Biscogniauxia nummularia* (Bull. : Fr.) Kuntze [006, 214, 254, 256]
- Daldinia concentrica* (Bolton : Fr.) Ces. & De Not. s. lat. [001, 003, 006, 031, 064, 192, 203, 204, 206, 207, 216, 217, 241, 243, 254, 256]
- Hypoxylon fragiforme* (Pers. : Fr.) J. Kickx f. [001, 003, 006, 031, 171, 173, 204, 206, 207, 214, 216, 217, 228, 254, 256], *H. fuscum* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [236, 259], *H. howeanum* Peck [006, 256]
- Kretzschmaria deusta* (Hoffm. : Fr.) P.M.D. Martin [001, 003, 200, 216, 262]
- Xylaria hypoxylon* (L. : Fr.) Grev. [001, 003, 112, 113, 135, 206, 207, 229, 246, 251, 252a, 259], *X. polymorpha* (Pers. : Fr.) Grev. [112, 204, 206, 207, 246]
- BASIDIOMYCETES**
- Agaricales**
- Agaricaceae**
- Agaricus altipes* (F.H. Møller) F.H. Møller [072, 202, 279], *A. arvensis* Schaeff. : Fr. [002, 005, 007, 009, 025, 039, 062, 064, 066, 072, 087, 112, 136, 151, 159, 160, 191, 220, 231, 251, 253, 268, 268a], *A. augustus* Fr. [021, 024, 025, 030, 060, 087, 220, 221, 222, 231, 232, 285], *A. benesii* (Pilát) Pilát [064, 268], *A. bernardii* (Quél.) Sacc. [039, 099, 102, 103, 120, 126, 131, 231, 268a], *A. bisporus* (J.E. Lange) Imbach [002, 009, 011, 015, 024, 025, 026, 027, 032, 091, 092, 093, 106, 110, 132, 134, 138, 147, 152, 168, 169, 172, 206, 207, 219, 231, 236, 244, 261, 263, 265, 266, 275, 277, 278, 280],

- A. bitorquis* (Quél.) Sacc. [002, 010, 039, 046, 047, 050, 058, 098, 106, 110, 112, 113, 135, 136, 147, 148, 151, 152, 154, 155, 170, 172, 181, 184, 188, 231, 238, 241, 242, 243, 244, 252a, 253, 260, 261, 263], *A. bresadolanus* Bohus [as '*bresadolianus*'] [011, 015, 025, 131, 154, 155, 198, 260], *A. campestris* L. : Fr. var. *campestris* [005, 007, 009, 010, 011, 015, 016, 017, 018, 021, 024, 025, 026, 027, 032, 033, 035, 036, 037, 039, 042, 045, 046, 047, 050, 055, 056, 057, 058, 060, 062, 064, 066, 090, 091, 092, 093, 106, 110, 112, 118, 121, 126, 127, 128, 132, 134, 135, 136, 144, 147, 151, 152, 154, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 171, 175, 181, 182, 183, 184, 187, 188, 192, 193, 197, 198, 206, 207, 221, 229, 231, 232, 236, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 244, 248, 251, 253, 257, 260, 261, 263, 265, 266, 267, 268, 268a, 269, 277, 278], *A. chionodermus* Pilát [249], *A. comptulus* Fr. [018, 025, 045, 112, 131, 136, 231], *A. cupreobrunneus* (F.H. Møller) Pilát [025, 112, 132, 134, 135, 136, 231, 251, 278, 280], *A. devoniensis* P.D. Orton [249], *A. essettei* Bon [013, 024, 025, 026, 027, 155, 157, 159, 160], *A. excellens* (F.H. Møller) F.H. Møller [018, 023, 025, 042], *A. impudicus* (Rea) Pilát [063, 132, 252a], *A. langei* (F.H. Møller & Jul. Schäff.) Maire [025, 066, 172], *A. lanipes* (F.H. Møller & Jul. Schäff.) Singer [007, 008, 231], *A. littoralis* (Wakef. & A. Pearson) Konrad & Maubl. [013, 015, 025, 172, 197], *A. luteomaculatus* (F.H. Møller) F.H. Møller [066, 202], *A. moelleri* Wasser [065], *A. pampeanus* Speg. [061, 066, 155], *A. pilatianus* (Bohus) Bohus [197], *A. placomyces* Peck s. lat. [022, 024, 149, 154, 260, 279, 284], *A. placomyces* Peck var. *meleagris* (Jul. Schäff.) R. Pascual [025, 219, 231], *A. porphyrizon* P.D. Orton [025], *A. pseudopratisensis* (Bohus) Wasser s. lat. [137], *A. pseudopratisensis* (Bohus) Wasser var. *pseudopratisensis* [244, 249], *A. rimulincola* Lasch [269], *A. rodmanii* Peck [045, 231], *A. romagnesii* Wasser [066, 157], *A. semotus* Fr. [112, 231, 251, 270], *A. silvaticus* Schaeff. : Fr. [025, 039, 040, 219, 253], *A. subperonatus* (J.E. Lange) Singer (incl. *A. vaporarius* (Pers.) Cappelli, 1984, non *A. vaporarius* Schrank, 1789) [042, 112, 136, 279, 283, 284], *A. sylvicola* (Vittad.) Peck [002, 016, 017, 021, 024, 025, 112, 136, 153, 154, 155, 163, 220, 221, 222, 231, 232, 236, 260, 261, 263, 277, 279], *A. urinascens* (F.H. Møller & Jul. Schäff.) Singer var. *urinascens* [024, 025, 026, 060, 064, 193, 198, 261, 263, 267, 268], *A. xanthoderma* Genev. [as '*xanthodermus*'] [017, 055, 060, 062, 064, 065, 087, 101, 103, 120, 127, 128, 151, 157, 159, 166, 174, 182, 183, 186, 188, 221, 231, 244, 267, 275, 277]
- Cystolepiota adulterina* (F.H. Møller) Bon [025], *C. seminuda* (Lasch) Bon [269]
- Endoptychum agaricoides* Czern. [125, 141]
- Lepiota aspera* (Pers. : Fr.) Quél. [039, 055, 113, 189, 231], *L. brunneoincarnata* Chodat & C. Martin [022, 024, 025, 105, 112, 174, 204, 206, 207, 231, 238, 241, 243, 261, 263], *L. castanea* Quél. [118, 119, 231, 285], *L. chypeolaria* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [016, 025, 066, 137, 157, 172, 279, 282, 285], *L. cristata* (Bolton : Fr.) P. Kumm. [024, 025, 046, 055, 064, 065, 066, 151, 159, 162, 163a, 203, 204, 206, 207, 221, 231, 235, 236, 261, 263, 265, 275], *L. cystophoroides* Joss. & Rioussat [279], *L. eriophora* Peck [279], *L. erminea* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [025, 026, 027, 038, 047, 050, 058, 064, 066, 118, 119, 149, 155, 159, 160, 212, 231, 268, 279, 284], *L. felina* (Pers.) P. Karst. [091, 092, 111, 112, 131, 132, 235, 252a, 261, 285], *L. forquignonii* Quél. [040], *L. helveola* Bres. [099, 101, 122, 132, 133, 134, 174], *L. ignivolvata* Bousset & Joss. ex Joss. [025, 040, 137, 197, 279, 282], *L. ochraceofulva* P.D. Orton [042], *L. oreadiformis* Velen. [025, 026, 027, 039, 066, 155, 172, 203], *L. rhodorbiza* Romagn. & Locq. ex P.D. Orton [231, 270], *L. subgracilis* Wasser [066, 202], *L. subincarnata* J.E. Lange [066, 202], *L. sublaevigata* Bon & Boiffard [132]
- Leucoagaricus badhamii* (Berk. & Broome) Singer [026, 027, 066, 231, 270], *L. barssii* (Zeller) Vellinga [137, 279], *L. carneifolius* (Gillet) Wasser [151, 197], *L. cinerascens* (Quél.) Bon & Boiffard [137, 279], *L. holosericeus* (Fr.) M.M. Moser [066, 194], *L. jubilaei* (Joss.) Bon [231, 270], *L. leucothites* (Vittad.) Wasser [046, 087, 112, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 134, 151, 153, 189, 231, 258, 268a, 270], *L. littoralis* (Menier) Bon & Boiffard [231, 270], *L. nympharum* (Kalchbr.) Bon [054, 064], *L. pudicus* (Bull.) Bon [066, 149, 152, 154, 155, 195, 252a, 260, 284]
- Leucocoprinus cygneus* (J.E. Lange) Bon [231, 270]
- Macrolepiota excoriata* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Wasser [023, 024, 025, 036, 037, 039, 042, 047, 050, 052, 054, 058, 064, 066, 112, 120, 131, 132, 136, 157, 159, 160, 163a, 172, 203, 231, 239, 248, 278, 280], *M. konradii* (Huijsman ex P.D. Orton) M.M. Moser [064, 087, 097, 112, 135, 136, 205, 206, 207, 251, 261, 263], *M. mastoidea* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer (incl. *M. gracilentia*) [018, 021, 024, 025, 042, 057, 064, 066, 087, 097, 111, 112, 132, 134, 135, 136, 221, 231, 232, 236, 239, 248, 252a, 253, 278, 280], *M. permixta* (Barla) Pacioni [102, 231], *M. procera* (Scop. : Fr.) Singer [001, 002, 003, 005, 018, 021, 024, 025, 030, 031, 032, 033, 035, 036, 037, 039, 040, 042, 046, 054, 057, 060, 064, 066, 087, 091, 092, 094, 097, 102, 106, 111, 112, 113, 127, 128, 132, 134, 135, 136, 144, 149, 151, 157, 168, 180, 182, 183, 185, 192, 193, 197, 205, 206, 207, 215, 220, 221, 222, 228, 231, 232, 238, 239,

241, 242, 243, 248, 251, 253, 257, 261, 263, 266, 269, 270, 278, 280], *M. prominens* (Viv. ex Fr.) M.M. Moser [269], *M. rachodes* (Vittad.) Singer s. lat. [011, 015, 016, 024, 025, 039, 048, 054, 060, 112, 135, 172, 251, 253], *M. rachodes* (Vittad.) Singer var. *rachodes* [036, 037, 269], *M. rachodes* var. *bohémica* (Wichanský) Bellù & Lanzoni [036, 037, 174]

Montagnea arenaria (DC.) Zeller [270], *M. candollei* Fr. [038, 118, 119, 212]

Bolbitiaceae

Agrocybe cylindracea (DC. : Fr.) Gillet [004, 009, 010, 024, 025, 028, 029, 047, 050, 054, 058, 066, 093, 097, 099, 103, 112, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 136, 145, 146, 147, 154, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163a, 166, 168, 204, 205, 206, 207, 231, 239, 244, 248, 251, 252a, 253, 260, 268a, 275, 277], *A. dura* (Bolton : Fr.) Singer [017, 024, 025, 062, 066, 090, 110, 152, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163a, 172, 199, 203, 231, 266, 268a], *A. molesta* (Lasch) Singer [050, 056, 175], *A. paludosa* (J.E. Lange) Kühner & Romagn. [017, 025, 026, 027, 048, 056, 062, 066, 152, 155, 157, 163, 175, 203, 279], *A. pediades* (Fr. : Fr.) Fayod [017, 026, 027, 047, 050, 060, 062, 064, 066, 118, 119, 157, 163, 166, 191, 210, 212, 231, 267, 270, 285], *A. praecox* (Pers. : Fr.) Fayod [010, 011, 015, 025, 026, 027, 048, 066, 154, 155, 172, 203, 260], *A. putaminum* (Maire) Singer [066, 071], *A. semiorbicularis* (Bull. : Fr.) Fayod [017, 026, 027, 066, 157, 231, 270], *A. sphaleromorpha* (Bull. : Fr.) Fayod [047, 050, 066, 199], *A. splendida* Cléménçon [026, 155, 158, 163a], *A. vervacti* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer [014, 023, 025, 066, 163, 203]

Bolbitius titubans (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [047, 050], *B. vitellinus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [047, 050, 091, 092, 112, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 155, 163a, 231, 239, 248, 252a]

Conocybe albipes Hauskn. [017, 033, 132, 155, 163, 163a, 166, 172, 231, 253, 268a, 270], *C. antipus* (Lasch) Fayod [as 'antipoda'] [210], *C. aporos* Kits van Wav. [157, 158], *C. arrhenii* (Fr.) Kits van Wav. [039], *C. coprophila* (Kühner) Kühner [231, 270], *C. fuscimarginata* (Murrill) Singer [158], *C. moseri* Watling var. *moseri* [163a], *C. pygmaeoaffinis* (Fr.) Kühner [066, 071], *C. rickeniana* P.D. Orton. [011, 047, 050, 062, 153, 197, 203, 231], *C. rickenii* (Jul. Schäff.) Kühner [026, 066], *C. semiglobata* Kühner & Watling [066, 071], *C. siennophylla* (Berk. & Broome) Singer [066, 071], *C. subovalis* Kühner & Watling [066, 071, 155, 163a], *C. subpubescens* P.D. Orton [158], *C. tenera* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Fayod [024, 025, 027, 155, 158, 163a, 268a]

Galeropsis lateritia (Watling) G. Moreno, Heykoop & Illana [117, 206, 207]

Hebeloma album Peck [025], *H. circinans* (Quél.) Sacc. [149], *H. cistophilum* Maire [025, 066], *H.*

crustuliniforme (Bull. : Fr.) Quél. [015, 017, 022, 023, 024, 025, 042, 066, 112, 122, 127, 128, 132, 135, 163, 174, 206, 244, 251], *H. eburneum* Malençon [025, 026, 027, 066, 151, 157, 203], *H. edurum* Métrod ex Bon [025, 066], *H. fragilipes* Romagn. [025], *H. fusipes* Bres. [159, 162], *H. hiemale* Bres. [156], *H. leucosarx* P.D. Orton [042, 047, 050, 058, 231], *H. longicaudum* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [026, 201], *H. mesophaeum* (Pers.) Fr. [018, 024, 025, 026, 027, 038, 062, 065, 066, 118, 119, 157, 159, 162, 203, 212], *H. populinum* Romagn. [008, 231], *H. pumilum* J.E. Lange [025, 156], *H. pusillum* J.E. Lange [025], *H. radicosum* (Bull. : Fr.) Ricken [004, 024, 025, 231], *H. sarcophyllum* (Peck) Sacc. [091, 096], *H. sinapizans* (Paulet) Gillet (at least a part of the records or all of them may represent *H. sinapizans sensu* J. Lange = *H. senescens* (Batsch) Berk. & Broome) [015, 018, 022, 040, 065, 112, 122, 132, 134, 159, 163a, 174, 203, 228, 231, 236, 278, 279, 280, 284], *H. truncatum* (Schaeff.) P. Kumm. [025, 066]

Panaeolina foenicicii (Pers. : Fr.) Maire [064, 065, 122, 132, 134, 159, 162, 189, 231, 268, 285]

Panaeolus acuminatus (Schaeff.) Quél. [047, 050, 091, 092, 094, 127, 128, 148, 231, 285], *P. ater* (J.E. Lange) Kühner & Romagn. [066, 198, 199], *P. campanulatus* (L. : Fr.) Quél. [015, 025, 126, 163a, 189, 231, 285], *P. fimicola* (Pers.) Quél. [026, 027, 066, 157, 163, 199, 231, 258], *P. fimiputris* (Bull. : Fr.) Quél. [197], *P. guttulatus* Bres. [163a], *P. olivaceus* F.H. Møller [026, 027, 065, 066, 157, 159, 162], *P. papilionaceus* (Bull. : Fr.) Quél. [026, 027, 066, 157, 163a, 166, 172, 260], *P. retirugis* (Fr.) Gillet [103, 231, 275, 277], *P. semiovatus* (With. : Fr.) S. Lundell & Nannf. [066, 127, 128, 168], *P. sphinctrinus* (Fr.) Quél. [017, 024, 025, 038, 062, 066, 118, 119, 131, 163a, 166, 212, 278, 285], *P. subbalteatus* (Berk. & Broome) Sacc. [066, 147, 191, 199], *P. subfirmus* P. Karst. [024, 025]

Clavariaceae

Clavaria abietina Pers. : Fr. (note: *C. abietina sensu auct.* = *Ramaria eumorpha*) [202, 245], *C. acuta* Sowerby : Fr. [025], *C. fragilis* Holmsk. : Fr. [064, 220, 221, 222, 232]

Clavulinopsis corniculata (Schaeff. : Fr.) Corner [005, 025, 204, 205, 206, 207, 269], *C. helvola* (Pers. : Fr.) Corner [204, 206, 207], *C. umbrinella* (Sacc.) Corner [040]

Coprinaceae

Coprinus alopecia Lasch [038, 118, 119, 212], *C. atramentarius* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [009, 010, 011, 015, 016, 017, 022, 025, 026, 027, 045, 050, 056, 058, 060, 062, 064, 065, 066, 090, 091, 092, 093, 094, 095, 097, 101, 102, 103, 110, 118, 120, 122, 126, 131, 132, 134, 147, 148, 151, 153, 154, 155, 159, 160, 162, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 172, 174, 175,

- 182, 183, 186, 188, 195, 198, 205, 206, 207, 229, 231, 244, 256, 260, 261, 263, 265, 266, 267, 268, 268a, 275, 277, 279, 285], *C. auricomus* Pat. [039, 062, 066, 155, 260, 285], *C. cinereus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Gray [066, 071, 166, 261, 263], *C. comatus* (O.F. Müll. : Fr.) Pers. [001, 002, 003, 005, 007, 009, 011, 015, 017, 018, 021, 024, 025, 026, 027, 036, 037, 045, 047, 048, 050, 054, 056, 058, 060, 062, 064, 066, 087, 088, 090, 091, 092, 093, 094, 097, 098, 099, 101, 102, 103, 106, 110, 111, 112, 118, 120, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 134, 136, 144, 147, 151, 152, 153, 154, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 172, 175, 180, 182, 183, 187, 188, 189, 191, 193, 195, 198, 204, 205, 206, 207, 221, 231, 232, 236, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 253, 257, 260, 261, 263, 265, 266, 267, 268, 268a, 275, 277, 278, 279, 280], *C. congregatus* (Bull.) Fr. [024, 025, 038, 118, 119, 212], *C. cothurnatus* Godey [066, 071], *C. deliquescens* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [269], *C. digitalis* (Batsch) Fr. [038, 118, 119, 212], *C. dilectus* Fr. [163a], *C. disseminatus* (Pers. : Fr.) Gray [002, 010, 011, 017, 026, 027, 038, 047, 050, 058, 062, 066, 094, 097, 112, 119, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 145, 146, 155, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 172, 173, 189, 191, 204, 206, 207, 214, 217, 221, 229, 231, 235, 251, 252a, 259, 261, 263, 265, 268a, 278, 280], *C. domesticus* (Bolton : Fr.) Gray [066, 163, 165, 206, 207, 259, 269, 278, 280], *C. ephemerus* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [066, 071], *C. episcopalis* P.D. Orton [066, 071], *C. extinctorius* (Bull.) Fr. [276], *C. galericuliformis* Losa ex Watling [112, 132, 134, 231, 251], *C. impatiens* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [235, 261, 263, 265], *C. lagopides* P. Karst. [039], *C. lagopus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [024, 025, 151], *C. micaceus* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [002, 009, 011, 016, 017, 024, 025, 026, 027, 036, 037, 038, 047, 050, 056, 058, 060, 062, 064, 066, 088, 090, 091, 092, 093, 098, 099, 101, 102, 103, 110, 112, 119, 120, 126, 131, 132, 145, 146, 147, 148, 149, 151, 154, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163a, 166, 168, 172, 173, 175, 191, 192, 195, 198, 204, 205, 206, 207, 220, 221, 229, 231, 236, 238, 241, 242, 243, 251, 256, 260, 261, 263, 265, 266, 267, 268, 268a, 275, 277], *C. niveus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [011, 016, 024, 025, 038, 064, 066, 118, 119, 155, 163a, 165, 166, 212, 231, 268a, 270], *C. patouillardii* Quél. [066, 071], *C. picaceus* (Bull. : Fr.) Gray [024, 025, 036, 037, 097, 112, 134, 135, 231, 251], *C. plicatilis* (Curtis : Fr.) Fr. [062, 066, 159, 160, 165, 191, 204, 205, 206, 207], *C. radiatus* (Bolton : Fr.) Pers. [158, 258], *C. radicans* Romagn. [119], *C. silvaticus* Peck [038, 118, 119, 212, 261, 263], *C. stanglianus* Enderle, Bender & Gröger [056, 163, 175], *C. sterquilinus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [066, 278], *C. truncorum* (Schaeff.) Fr. [066, 071], *C. xanthothrix* Romagn. [163]
- Lacrymaria glareosa* (J. Favre) Watling [091, 092, 112],
- L. lacrymabunda* (Bull. : Fr.) Pat. [042, 122, 132, 134, 153, 159, 160, 173, 204, 205, 206, 207, 214, 219, 231], *L. pyrotiricha* (Holmsk. : Fr.) Konrad & Maubl. [042]
- Psathyrella ammophila* (Durieu & Lév.) P.D. Orton [038, 118, 119, 212], *P. artemisiae* (Pass.) Konrad & Maubl. [066], *P. atomata* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. (a part of records or all of them may represent *P. atomata sensu auct.* = *P. prona* f. *cana* Kits van Wav.) [038, 118, 119, 163, 212, 268a], *P. badiophylla* (Romagn.) Park.-Rhodes [158], *P. bifrons* (Berk.) A.H. Sm. [158] *P. bipellis* (Quél.) A.H. Sm. [066, 071], *P. candolleana* (Fr. : Fr.) Maire [016, 017, 025, 026, 027, 055, 064, 066, 091, 092, 112, 127, 128, 131, 132, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 203, 231, 268a, 270, 285], *P. cernua* (Vahl.) M.M. Moser [158], *P. conopilus* (Fr. : Fr.) A. Pearson & Dennis [151], *P. cotonea* (Quél.) Konrad & Maubl. [026, 066, 071], *P. fatua* (Fr. : Fr.) Konrad & Maubl. [047, 050, 066, 199, 231], *P. frustulenta* (Fr.) A.H. Sm. [014], *P. gordonii* (Berk. & Broome) A. Pearson & Dennis [038, 118, 119, 212], *P. gracilis* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [039, 134, 231], *P. gyroflexa* (Fr.) Konrad & Maubl. [038, 118, 119, 212], *P. lutensis* (Romagn.) M.M. Moser [066, 071], *P. marcescibilis* (Britzelm.) Singer [025, 066, 071], *P. melanthina* (Fr.) Kits van Wav. [231, 270], *P. microrhiza* (Lasch) Konrad & Maubl. [014, 206, 207], *P. multipedata* (Peck) A.H. Sm. [023, 025], *P. murcida* (Fr. : Fr.) Kits van Wav. [158, 203], *P. obtusata* (Pers.) A.H. Sm. [025, 062, 172, 231, 256], *P. ochracea* (Romagn.) M.M. Moser ex Kits van Wav. [066, 071, 268a], *P. phegophila* Romagn. [026, 201], *P. piluliformis* (Bull. : Fr.) P.D. Orton [017, 024, 025, 038, 118, 119, 212], *P. prona* (Fr.) Gillet [231, 270], *P. pseudogracilis* (Romagn.) M.M. Moser [066, 071], *P. pygmaea* (Bull. : Fr.) Singer [259], *P. spadicea* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Singer [010, 025, 066, 151, 163], *P. spadiceogrisea* (Schaeff.) Maire [163, 231, 256, 270], *P. sphagnicola* (Maire) J. Favre [066, 071], *P. squamosa* (P. Karst.) M.M. Moser [172], *P. tephrophylla* (Romagn.) M.M. Moser [026, 027, 038, 066, 118, 119, 203], *P. umbonata* (Peck) A.H. Sm. [189]
- Cortinariaceae
- Cortinarius albidus* Peck subsp. *europaeus* (M.M. Moser) Quadr. [072], *C. aleurius* Maire [023, 025], *C. allutus* Fr. [018, 025], *C. anserinus* (Velen.) Rob. Henry [002, 180, 231], *C. balteatoalbus* Rob. Henry [023, 025], *C. balteatus* Fr. : Fr. [066], *C. bulbosus* (Sowerby) Fr. [041, 231], *C. bulliardii* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [041, 231, 236], *C. camphoratus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [023, 197], *C. cinnabarinus* Fr. [112], *C. cinnamomeoluteus* P.D. Orton [025, 066], *C. cinnamomeus* (L. : Fr.) Fr. [022, 024, 025], *C. claricolor* (Fr.) Fr. [197], *C. cotoneus* Fr.

- [231, 270], *C. croceus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Høil. [025], *C. delibutus* Fr. [023, 025], *C. diasemospermus* Lamoure var. *diasemospermus* [163a], *C. duracinus* Fr. [014, 015, 066, 149, 199, 203], *C. elegantior* (Fr.) Fr. [066, 194, 203], *C. elegantissimus* Rob. Henry ex Rob. Henry [042, 220, 231, 236], *C. flavopallidus* (M.M. Moser) M.M. Moser [066], *C. flexipes* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [203], *C. fraudulentus* Britzelm. [066], *C. fulvescens* Fr. [025, as *C. fasciatus sensu* J.E. Lange], *C. gentilis* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [022, 025, 156], *C. glaucopus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Fr. [220, 231], *C. herbarum* Rob. Henry [025], *C. herculeus* Malençon [150, 197], *C. hercynicus* (Pers.) M.M. Moser [061], *C. isabellinus* (Batsch) Fr. [025], *C. largus* Fr. [042], *C. malachius* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [231, 270], *C. melanotus* Kalchbr. [066], *C. mucosus* (Bull. : Fr.) Cooke [040], *C. obtusus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [023, 025, 040], *C. olivaceofuscus* Kühner [032, 231, 270], *C. orellanus* (Fr.) Fr. [022, 023, 025], *C. pseudosulphureus* Rob. Henry ex P.D. Orton [025], *C. psittacinus* M.M. Moser [023, 025, 066], *C. pulchripes* J. Favre [024, 025], *C. punctatus* (Pers.) Fr. [219, 231], *C. purpurascens* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [231, 258], *C. rapaceus* Fr. [039], *C. renidentoides* Rob. Henry [025], *C. rigidus* (Scop.) Fr. [025, 066], *C. rufoolivaceus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [132], *C. saginus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [066, 134, 157, 197, 199, 231], *C. semisanguineus* (Fr. : Fr.) Gillet [025], *C. sommerfeltii* Høil. [025], *C. spilomeus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [025], *C. splendens* Rob. Henry subsp. *splendens* [018, 022, 025], *C. splendens* subsp. *meinhardii* (Bon) Brandrud & Melot [066], *C. stillatitius sensu* Bres. [025], *C. subbalaustinus* Rob. Henry ex Rob. Henry [236], *C. subtortus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [023, 025], *C. subturbinatus* Rob. Henry ex P.D. Orton [018, 023, 025, 132, 220, 228, 231, 236], *C. sulphurinus* Quél. [066, 245], *C. talus* Fr. [025], *C. triformis* Fr. [023, 025], *C. triumphans* Fr. [025, 268a], *C. trivialis* J.E. Lange [018, 025, 040, 112, 113], *C. variicolor* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [002, 045, 180, 231, 257], *C. varius* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Fr. [018, 025], *C. venetus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [042], *C. vibratilis* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [024, 025], *C. violaceus* (L. : Fr.) Fr. [261, 263]
- Crepidotus calolepis* (Fr.) P. Karst. [028], *C. cesatii* (Rabenh.) Sacc. [041, 231, 258], *C. epibryus* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [231, 258], *C. lundellii* Pilát [028, 036, 037, 066, 112, 202, 239, 246, 248], *C. luteolus* (Lambotte) Sacc. [132, 153], *C. mollis* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Staude [028, 029, 066, 097, 112, 127, 128, 132, 135, 173, 199, 203, 214, 217, 231, 246, 251, 252a, 256, 259, 270], *C. variabilis* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [028, 203, 229, 259, 285]
- Flammulaster ferrugineus* (Maire ex Kühner) Watling [038, 118, 119, 212], *F. granulosa* (J.E. Lange) Watling [072]
- Galerina ampullaceocystis* P.D. Orton. [278], *G. atkinsoniana* A.H. Sm. [203], *G. badipes* (Fr.) Kühner [026, 201, 203], *G. cinctula* P.D. Orton [132], *G. clavus* Romagn. [038, 118, 119], *G. marginata* (Batsch : Fr.) Kühner [066, 151, 174, 199, 203, 231, 256, 270], *G. paludosa* (Fr.) Kühner [156], *G. pumila* (Pers. : Fr.) M. Lange [156], *G. sideroides* (Bull.) Kühner [038, 119, 212]
- Gymnopilus junonius* (Fr. : Fr.) P.D. Orton [206, 207, 239, 248], *G. liquiritiae* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst. [210, 231], *G. penetrans* (Fr. : Fr.) Murrill [025, 066, 157, 203, 210, 231, 256, 268a], *G. picreus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst. [066], *G. sapineus* (Fr. : Fr.) Maire [087, 189, 231]
- Inocybe abietis* Kühner [026, 066, 203], *I. acuta* Boud. [025], *I. adaequata* (Britzelm.) Sacc. [042, 156, 172], *I. asterospora* (Quél.) Quél. [036, 037, 203], *I. bongardii* (Weinm.) Quél. s. lat. [026, 038, 118, 119, 212], *I. bongardii* (Weinm.) Quél. var. *pisciadora* (Donadini & Rioussel) Kuyper [163a], *I. bresadolae* Masee [024, 025], *I. bresadolana* Bon [026, 201, 203], *I. caesariata* (Fr.) P. Karst. [066], *I. cervicolor* (Pers.) Quél. [038, 118, 119], *I. cincinnata* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [017, 025, 026, 157, 172], *I. corydalina* Quél. [025], *I. cucullata* G. Martin [066], *I. curvipes* P. Karst. [013, 016, 066, 157], *I. dulcamara* (Alb. & Schwein.) Quél. [065, 066, 120, 159, 199, 259], *I. duriuscula* Rea [231, 258], *I. erubescens* A. Blytt [010, 022, 025, 065, 091, 092, 122, 132, 134, 159, 162, 174, 231], *I. fibrosa* (Sowerby) Gillet [163], *I. flocculosa* (Berk.) Sacc. var. *flocculosa* [201], *I. fraudans* (Britzelm.) Sacc. [153], *I. fuscidula* Velen. var. *fuscidula* [025], *I. fuscomarginata* Kühner [066], *I. geophylla* (Sowerby : Fr.) P. Kumm. var. *geophylla* [017, 095, 111, 112, 113, 122, 127, 128, 132, 134, 151, 157, 168, 174, 189, 206, 207, 239, 244, 248, 279], *I. geophylla* var. *lilacina* (Peck) Gillet [025, 206, 207, 231, 281, 284, 285], *I. grammata* Quél. & Le Bret. [066], *I. gymnocarpa* Kühner [231, 270], *I. hirtella* Bres. [025, 066, 091, 096, 199], *I. hypophaea* Furrer-Ziogas [066], *I. lacera* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [066, 197, 199], *I. lucifuga* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [026], *I. mixtilis* (Britzelm.) Sacc. [025], *I. napipes* J.E. Lange [022, 023, 025], *I. nitidiuscula* (Britzelm.) Lapl. [022, 025, 203], *I. olida* Maire [221, 226], *I. perbrevis* (Weinm.) Gillet [038, 047, 050, 118, 119, 231], *I. petiginosa* (Fr. : Fr.) Gillet [025], *I. praetervisa* Quél. [153], *I. pusio* P. Karst. [018, 025], *I. pyriodora* (Pers.) P. Kumm. [278, 280], *I. queletii* Konrad [025, 026, 027, 066], *I. rimosa* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [009, 010, 017, 022, 025, 027, 050, 054, 055, 056, 058, 060, 062, 064, 065, 066, 091, 092, 094, 095, 098, 101, 102, 103, 112, 113, 120, 122, 127, 128, 131, 132, 151, 153, 155, 157, 159, 162, 163a, 166, 168, 174, 175, 182,

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- Leucocortinarius bulbiger* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Singer [004]
- Phaeomarasmius erinaceus* (Pers. : Fr.) Scherff. ex Romagn. [161]
- Pleurotellus chioneus* (Pers.) Kühner [200]
- Tubaria allostipitata* D.A. Reid [231, 270], *T. conspersa* (Pers. : Fr.) Fayod [039], *T. furfuracea* (Pers. : Fr.) Gillet [066, 157, 163, 199, 214, 231], *T. hiemalis* Romagn. ex Bon [066, 163a, 259], *T. pellucida* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [045, 231], *T. romagnesiana* Arnolds [045, 231]
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- Clitopilus prunulus* (Scop. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [023, 025, 048, 112, 131, 172, 173, 204, 205, 206, 207, 221, 231]
- Entoloma aethiops* (Scop.) G. Stev. [023, 025], *E. cetratum* (Fr. : Fr.) M.M. Moser [018, 066], *E. clypeatum* (L.) P. Kumm. [173, 214, 231], *E. hirtipes* (Schumach. : Fr.) M.M. Moser [014, 025, 203], *E. incanum* (Fr. : Fr.) Hesler [065, 159, 162], *E. juncinum* (Kühner & Romagn.) Noordel. [025], *E. lanicum* (Romagn.) Noordel. [038, 118, 119, 212, 231, 270], *E. longistriatum* (Peck) Noordel. [019, 025], *E. lucidum* (P.D. Orton) M.M. Moser [206, 207], *E. mammosum* (L.) Hesler [019, 024, 025], *E. niphoides* Romagn. ex Noordel. [066, 202], *E. rhodocalyx* (Lasch : Fr.) M.M. Moser [038, 118, 119, 212], *E. rhodopolium* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [023, 025], *E. rusticoides* (Gillet) Noordel. [163a], *E. sepium* (Noulet & Dass.) Richon & Roze [019, 025, 066], *E. sericatum* (Britzelm.) Sacc. [019, 025], *E. sericellum* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [065, 159, 162], *E. sericeoides* (J.E. Lange) Noordel. [065, 066, 159, 162], *E. sericeum* [Bull. ex] Quél. [024, 025, 039, 151], *E. sinuatum* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [065, 066, 106, 132, 155, 157, 159, 162, 163, 163a, 166, 173, 174, 214, 231, 252a, 258, 260], *E. subradiatum* (Kühner & Romagn.) M.M. Moser [066, 202], *E. undatum* (Fr.) M.M. Moser [163], *E. venosum* Gillet [197]
- Rhodocybe fallax* (Quél.) Singer [163], *R. gemina* (Fr.) Kuyper & Noordel. [270], *R. mundula* (Lasch) Singer [231, 270], *R. nitellina* (Fr.) Singer [039, 042]
- Fistulinaceae
- Fistulina hepatica* (Schaeff. : Fr.) With. [004, 005, 032, 042, 112, 135, 136, 159, 160, 176, 205, 206, 207, 217, 246, 251, 255, 256, 257]
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- Hydnangium virescens* Quél. [211]
- Laccaria amethystina* Cooke [023, 025, 033, 112, 113, 136, 204, 205, 206, 207, 228, 231, 236, 253], *L. bicolor* (Maire) P.D. Orton [023, 025, 203], *L. laccata* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. s. lat. [018, 023, 025, 091, 092, 098, 099, 103, 111, 112, 113, 120, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 134, 135, 136, 168, 173, 189, 198, 203, 204, 205, 206, 207, 214, 220, 221, 231, 236, 238, 241, 242, 243, 251, 252a, 261, 263, 266, 284], *L. laccata* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. var. *laccata* [239, 248], *L. proxima* (Boud.) Pat. [038, 118, 119], *L. pumila* Fayod [112, 136, 239, 248]
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- Bovista aestivalis* (Bonord.) Demoulin [211], *B. nigrescens* Pers. : Pers. [009, 010, 025, 172, 269], *B. pila* Berk. & M.A. Curtis [033, 253], *B. plumbea* Pers. : Pers. [010, 011, 015, 016, 025, 027, 030, 036, 037, 041, 046, 047, 050, 054, 055, 058, 060, 062, 064, 066, 091, 092, 098, 102, 103, 112, 113, 120, 126, 127, 128, 131, 134, 135, 155, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 172, 193, 197, 205, 206, 207, 211, 238, 239, 241, 243, 248, 251, 261, 263, 266, 267, 268, 269, 270], *B. polymorpha* (Vittad.) Kreisel [134, 147, 270], *B. pusilla* (Batsch : Pers.) Pers. [046, 112, 251]
- Calvatia cyathiformis* (Bosc) Morgan [066, 202], *C. maxima* (Schaeff.) Morgan [189]
- Disciseda bovista* (Klotzsch) Henn. [098, 238, 241, 243]
- Handkea excipuliformis* (Scop. : Pers.) Kreisel [011, 015, 024, 025, 041, 045, 048, 060, 064, 144, 149, 192, 195, 205, 206, 207, 211, 221, 228, 236, 243, 268], *H. utrififormis* (Bull. : Pers.) Kreisel [009, 010, 011, 015, 016, 017, 018, 024, 025, 030, 033, 048, 060, 062, 064, 066, 091, 092, 094, 099, 101, 102, 103, 111, 112, 131, 135, 159, 160, 193, 203, 211, 221, 228, 236, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 244, 248, 251, 252a, 253, 261, 263, 266, 267, 268, 268a, 269]
- Langermannia gigantea* (Batsch : Pers.) Rostk. [005, 010, 060, 062, 064, 066, 106, 155, 157, 172, 188, 195, 268, 269]
- Lycoperdon atropurpureum* Vittad. [030, 064, 134, 268, 270], *L. decipiens* Durieu & Mont. [049], *L. echinatum* Pers. : Pers. [112, 135, 136, 251, 252a, 269], *L. lividum* Pers. [025, 055, 066, 154, 172, 197, 203, 260], *L. mammiforme* Pers. [024, 025, 027, 112, 136, 259], *L. marginatum* Vittad. [066, 202], *L. molle* Pers. : Pers. [025, 026, 027, 030, 033, 036, 037, 046, 055, 060, 064, 088, 091, 092, 093, 098, 099, 103, 111, 112, 113, 120, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 134, 135, 136, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163a, 166, 168, 169, 182, 187, 188, 203, 239, 248, 251, 253, 266, 267, 268], *L. nigrescens* Wahlenb. [066, 206], *L. peckii* J.B. Morgan [030], *L. perlatum* Pers. : Pers. s. lat. [002, 010, 011, 023, 024, 025, 030, 033, 035, 036, 037, 039, 040, 042,

046, 054, 055, 060, 064, 066, 089, 091, 092, 093, 094, 097, 098, 099, 102, 103, 106, 111, 112, 113, 120, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 134, 135, 136, 157, 168, 169, 171, 172, 191, 199, 203, 205, 206, 207, 211, 220, 228, 236, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 251, 253, 259, 266, 269, 270, 278, 279, 280, 281, 284], *L. perlatum* Pers. : Pers. var. *perlatum* [180], *L. pulcherrimum* Berk. & M.A. Curtis [189], *L. pyriforme* Schaeff. : Pers. [004, 011, 015, 024, 025, 036, 037, 039, 097, 111, 112, 113, 136, 144, 229, 239, 243, 246, 248, 259], *L. subpedicellatum* Pilát [211], *L. umbrinum* Pers. : Pers. [011, 025, 030, 060, 064, 066, 144, 151, 203, 206, 207, 211, 219, 239, 243, 248, 270]

Vascellum pratense (Pers. : Pers.) Kreisel [018, 024, 025, 046, 064, 066, 097, 137, 147, 149, 151, 197, 205, 206, 207, 270, 279, 285]

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Flagelloscypha minutissima (Burt) Donk [097]

Flammulina ononidis Arnolds [204, 206, 207], *F. velutipes* (Curtis : Fr.) Singer [001, 003, 004, 009, 011, 015, 025, 047, 058, 066, 102, 110, 112, 136, 160, 191, 199, 217, 229, 231, 239, 246, 248, 252a, 268a]

Lentinula edodes (Berk.) Pegler [004]

Macrocyttidia cucumis (Pers. : Fr.) Joss. [066]

Marasmiellus candidus (Bolton) Singer [204, 206, 207], *M. foetidus* (Sowerby : Fr.) Antonín, Halling & Noordel. [066, 203], *M. perforans* (Hoffm. : Fr.) Antonín, Halling & Noordel. [025, 026, 210, 231], *M. ramealis* (Bull. : Fr.) Singer [041, 137, 231, 244, 256, 279, 285]

Marasmius alliaceus (Jacq. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 112, 136], *M. anisocystidiatus* Antonín, Desjardin & H. Gsell [235, 261], *M. bulliardii* Quéél. [118, 119, 212, 231], *M. calopus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [207, 231, 270],

M. cobaerens (Pers. : Fr.) Cooke & Quéél. [025, 261], *M. epiphyllus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [066, 112, 199, 203, 239, 248, 254], *M. hudsonii* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [154, 260], *M. oreades* (Bolton : Fr.) Fr. [002, 004, 005, 011, 015, 021, 023, 024, 025, 030, 033, 042, 048, 060, 062, 064, 098, 099, 103, 111, 112, 126, 135, 136, 148, 155, 159, 160, 163a, 166, 189, 193, 203, 204, 205, 206, 207, 210, 219, 220, 221, 222, 228, 231, 232, 236, 239, 248, 251, 252a, 253, 261, 263, 267, 268, 268a, 269, 277, 284], [*M. porreus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr., *nom. dubium*] [038, 118, 119, 212], *M. quercus* Britzelm. [038, 118, 119, 212], [*M. resinus* (Peck) Sacc., *nom. dubium*] [189, 231], *M. rotula* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 097, 163, 204, 206, 207, 231, 256, 270, 285], *M. scorodonius* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 038, 053, 112, 118, 119, 136, 151, 163, 212], *M. wynnei* Berk. & Broome [036, 037, 206, 207, 269]

Omphalotus illudens (Schwein.) Sacc. [004], *O. olearius* (DC. : Fr.) Singer [022, 023, 025, 028, 029, 036, 037, 064, 091, 092, 098, 101, 103, 111, 112, 113, 122, 127, 128, 132, 134, 157, 174, 206, 207, 231, 238, 239, 241, 243, 246, 248, 251, 253, 261, 263, 268, 278, 281, 284]

Oudemansiella mucida (Schrad. : Fr.) Höhn. [004, 024, 025, 036, 037, 048, 055, 064, 112, 136, 205, 206, 207, 221, 231, 236, 256]

Rhodocollybia butyracea (Bull. : Fr.) Lennox f. *butyracea* [024, 091, 092, 094, 111, 112, 132, 135, 137, 136, 189, 231, 239, 251, 279, 281], *R. butyracea* f. *asema* (Fr. : Fr.) Antonín, Halling & Noordel. [025, 039, 137, 279], *R. maculata* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Singer var. *maculata* [025, 039, 042], *R. prolixa* (Hornem. : Fr.) Antonín & Noordel. var. *distorta* (Fr.) Antonín, Halling & Noordel. [066, 285]

Setulipes androsaceus (L. : Fr.) Antonín [023, 025, 036, 037, 038, 097, 112, 118, 119, 132, 134, 135, 212, 231, 239, 248, 256], *S. quercophilus* (Pouzar) Antonín [231, 270]

Strobilurus esculentus (Wulfen : Fr.) Singer [203], *S. stephanocystis* (Kühner & Romagn. ex Hora) Singer [017, 025, 026, 027, 066, 199, 231, 239, 248, 270], *S. tenacellus* (Pers. : Fr.) Singer [025], *S. trullisatus* (Murrill) Lennox [097]

Xerula causei Maire [211], *X. hygrophoroides* (Singer & Cléménçon) Candusso & Basso [066], *X. melanotricha* Dörfelt [024, 025, 066, 112, 157, 199], *X. pudens* (Pers.) Singer [004, 025, 066, 211, 231], *X. radicata* (Relhan : Fr.) Dörfelt [002, 023, 024, 025, 036, 037, 038, 039, 046, 054, 055, 064, 087, 111, 112, 113, 118, 119, 132, 136, 145, 146, 149, 168, 173, 180, 182, 183, 204, 205, 206, 207, 214, 221, 228, 231, 236, 239, 248, 269, 270]

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- Crucibulum laeve* (Huds. : Pers.) Kambly [024, 025, 161, 166, 206, 207, 211, 259]
Cyathus olla (Batsch : Pers.) Pers. [024, 098, 110, 112, 127, 128, 134, 163a, 166, 168, 203, 206, 207, 217, 229, 239, 246, 248, 251, 252a, 261, 263, 265], *C. stercoreus* (Schwein.) De Toni [163a], *C. striatus* (Huds. : Pers.) Hoffm. [206, 207, 259, 269, 270]

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- Hohenbuehelia atrocoerulea* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer [066, 231, 258, 259], *H. longipes* (Boud.) M.M. Moser [112, 252a], *H. myxotricha* (Lév.) Singer [259], *H. petaloides* (Bull. : Fr.) Schulzer s. lat. [028, 029, 132, 228, 278], *H. petaloides* (Bull. : Fr.) Schulzer var. *petaloides* [098, 269], *H. tremula* (Schaeff.) Thorn & G.L. Barron [134, 231, 269]
Pleurotus cornucopiae (Paulet) Rolland [002, 004, 033, 041, 103, 120, 131, 154, 173, 180, 198, 204, 205, 206, 207, 217, 231, 253, 257, 260, 277], *P. dryinus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [004, 047, 066, 145, 146, 159, 160, 199, 231, 256], *P. eryngii* (DC. : Fr.) Quél. s. lat. [004, 009, 010, 011, 015, 016, 017, 025, 036, 037, 045, 046, 047, 054, 058, 060, 062, 064, 066, 088, 090, 093, 099, 103, 110, 112, 120, 124, 126, 131, 136, 147, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163a, 168, 169, 172, 184, 188, 193, 199, 197, 231, 244, 266, 267, 268, 285], *P. eryngii* (DC. : Fr.) Quél. var. *ferulae* (Lanzi) Sacc. [231], *P. ilgazicus* Pilát [210, 231], *P. nemecii* Pilát [210, 231], *P. ostreatus* (Jacq. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [001, 002, 003, 004, 005, 007, 009, 010, 011, 015, 016, 021, 024, 025, 026, 027, 028, 029, 030, 032, 036, 037, 043, 047, 048, 054, 056, 058, 060, 062, 064, 066, 088, 090, 091, 092, 093, 094, 097, 098, 099, 101, 102, 103, 110, 112, 113, 118, 119, 120, 121, 124, 126, 127, 128, 129, 131, 132, 134, 136, 145, 147, 151, 154, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163a, 166, 168, 169, 171, 172, 175, 180, 181, 182, 183, 184, 187, 188, 189, 191, 193, 195, 197, 198, 199, 205, 206, 217, 229, 231, 236, 238, 239, 241, 243, 246, 248, 251, 255, 256, 257, 260, 261, 263, 266, 267, 268, 268a, 275, 277, 278, 280], *P. populinus* O. Hilber & O.K. Mill. [159], *P. pubescens* Peck [219, 231], *P. pulmonarius* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [004, 024, 025, 066, 217, 231], *P. spodoleucus* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [269]

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- Amanita alba* Pers. [002, 064, 066, 268], *A. battarrae* (Boud.) Bon [023, 025, 231], *A. caesarea* (Scop. : Fr.) Pers. [002, 025, 040, 042, 112, 113, 132, 134, 135, 136, 144, 192, 215, 220, 221, 222, 228, 231, 232, 243, 253, 257], *A. ceciliae* (Berk. & Broome) Bas [048, 112, 136, 191], *A. citrina* (Schaeff.) Pers. s. lat. [018, 023, 024, 025, 036, 037, 040, 066, 087, 106, 112, 149, 182, 183, 185, 186, 199, 204, 206, 207, 231], *A. citrina* (Schaeff.) Pers. var. *alba* (Gillet) E.-J. Gilbert [025, 042], *A. codinae*

- (Maire) Bertault [087, 112, 132, 134, 231, 251], *A. crocea* (Quél.) Singer [228, 252a], *A. echinocephala* (Vittad.) Quél. [064, 065], *A. eliae* Quél. [025, 065], *A. franchetii* (Boud.) Fayod [022, 025], *A. friabilis* (P. Karst.) Bas [061], *A. fulva* (Schaeff. ex Pers.) Fr. [054, 064], *A. gemmata* (Fr.) Bertill. [010, 017, 022, 024, 025, 064, 065, 112, 113, 174, 210, 221, 231, 238, 241, 243, 251], *A. mairei* Foley [025], *A. muscaria* (L. : Fr.) Hook. [022, 025, 036, 037, 040, 054, 060, 065, 106, 112, 113, 135, 149, 171, 174, 180, 182, 183, 185, 186, 220, 221, 228, 231, 236, 241, 243, 253, 267], *A. ovoidea* (Bull. : Fr.) Link [007, 009, 025, 056, 066, 091, 092, 112, 121, 132, 134, 136, 175, 231, 278, 280, 285], *A. pantherina* (DC. : Fr.) Krombh. [022, 023, 024, 025, 040, 046, 054, 055, 064, 065, 106, 112, 113, 122, 132, 135, 171, 174, 180, 182, 183, 186, 206, 207, 231, 252a], *A. phalloides* (Fr. : Fr.) Link [036, 037, 040, 087, 094, 095, 122, 132, 149, 171, 174, 182, 183, 186, 191, 206, 207, 221, 231, 266], *A. porphyria* Fr. : Fr. [039, 064, 132], *A. rubescens* (Pers. : Fr.) Gray s. lat. [024, 025, 042, 054, 064, 065, 087, 106, 112, 132, 136, 173, 174, 185, 205, 206, 207, 214, 220, 221, 222, 228, 231, 236], *A. rubescens* (Pers. : Fr.) Gray var. *annulosulphurea* Gillet [112, 113, 136], [*A. solitaria sensu auct. mult.* = *A. echinocephala* or *A. strobiliformis*] [025, 065, 159, 162, 206, 207, 276], *A. spissa* (Fr.) P. Kumm. [023, 024, 025, 026, 027, 060, 087, 185, 220, 231, 267, 277], *A. strobiliformis* (Paulet ex Vittad.) Bertill. [026, 027], *A. subalpina* M.M. Moser [278, 280], *A. submembranacea* (Bon) Gröger [056, 175], *A. vaginata* (Bull. : Fr.) Vittad. s. lat. [021, 023, 024, 025, 030, 039, 046, 055, 064, 099, 102, 103, 106, 112, 113, 120, 124, 127, 128, 131, 132, 136, 157, 166, 173, 174, 189, 191, 203, 204, 205, 206, 207, 210, 214, 221, 231, 236, 252a, 270, 275, 277], *A. vaginata* (Bull. : Fr.) Vittad. var. *alba* Gillet [231], *A. valens* (E.-J. Gilbert) Bertault [231, 270], *A. verna* (Bull. : Fr.) Lam. [054, 182, 183, 186, 231, 275, 277], *A. virosa* (Fr.) Bertill. [040, 106, 173, 174, 214, 231, 275]

Limacella illinita (Fr. : Fr.) Maire [025]

- Pluteus atromarginatus* (Konrad) Kühner [025], *P. aurantiorugosus* (Trog) Sacc. [126, 132], *P. cervinus* (Schaeff.) P. Kumm. var. *cervinus* [004, 145, 146, 159, 160, 173, 214, 217, 231], *P. cinereofuscus* J.E. Lange [072], *P. dietrichii* Bres. [163a], *P. ephebeus* (Fr. : Fr.) Gillet [062], *P. leoninus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [024, 025], *P. nanus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [066, 202], *P. petasatus* (Fr.) Gillet [219, 231], *P. plautus* (Weinm.) Gillet [85, 203], *P. podospileus* Sacc. & Cub. [047, 066, 202, 231], *P. romellii* (Britzelm.) Sacc. [062, 066, 159, 160, 163a, 166, 278, 280, 285], *P. salicinus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [024, 025, 065, 112, 136, 162, 163, 166, 168, 174,

- 231, 258], *P. satur* Kühner & Romagn. [066, 203], *P. thomsonii* (Berk. & Broome) Dennis [159, 160, 203], *P. tomentosulus* Peck [045, 231], *P. umbrosus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [025]
- Torrendia pulchella* Bres. [134, 141, 231, 271]
- Volvariella bombycina* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Singer s. lat. [004, 025, 155, 159, 160, 163a, 168, 191, 210, 253], *V. bombycina* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Singer var. *maxima* Pilát [024, 231], *V. gloiocephala* (DC. : Fr.) Boekhout & Enderle [011, 026, 027, 035, 047, 055, 058, 062, 064, 066, 091, 092, 098, 099, 103, 111, 112, 126, 132, 134, 138, 153, 155, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 198, 203, 205, 206, 207, 231, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 268a, 275, 277, 281], *V. media* (Schumach. : Fr.) Singer [047, 050, 066, 231], *V. murinella* (Quél.) M.M. Moser [010], *V. pusilla* (Pers. : Fr.) Singer [025, 172, 197], *V. surrecta* (Knapp) Singer [013], *V. volvacea* (Bull. : Fr.) Singer [265]
- Pterulaceae
- Pterula multifida* (Chevall.) Fr. [259]
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- Henningsomyces candidus* (Pers.) Kuntze [209]
- Rectipilus fasciculatus* (Pers.) Agerer [209]
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- Strophariaceae
- Hypholoma capnoides* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [010, 015, 016, 025, 197, 236, 259], *H. elaeodes* (Fr.) Gillet [042], *H. epixanthum* (Fr.) Quél. [221, 226], *H. fasciculare* (Huds. : Fr.) Quél. [001, 003, 009, 022, 023, 024, 025, 026, 027, 031, 036, 037, 039, 062, 065, 066, 094, 095, 097, 101, 103, 111, 112, 113, 122, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 135, 152, 159, 162, 163a, 166, 168, 171, 173, 174, 180, 182, 183, 186, 197, 204, 206, 207, 214, 216, 217, 221, 228, 231, 236, 239, 241, 243, 244, 248, 251, 254, 256, 259, 265, 275, 277, 279, 281, 284], *H. laeticolor* (F.H. Møller) P.D. Orton [038, 118, 119], *H. marginatum* (Pers. : Fr.) J. Schröt. [025, 066, 259], *H. radicosum* J.E. Lange [259], *H. sublateritium* (Schaeff.) Quél. [011, 023, 025, 042, 112, 131, 135, 173, 206, 207, 214, 217, 231, 236, 252a, 259]
- Kuehneromyces mutabilis* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Singer & A.H. Sm. [099, 103, 112, 113, 120, 129, 149, 221, 231, 236, 246, 251, 277]
- Pholiota* [*adiposa sensu auct. mult.* = *Ph. aurivella* or *Ph. jahnii*] [004, 054, 110, 126, 129, 132, 173, 210, 217, 231, 254, 256], *Ph. astragalina* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer [023, 025, 134, 231, 259], *Ph. aurivella* (Batsch : Fr.) Fr. [009, 025, 047, 050, 058, 062, 064, 112, 113, 154, 159, 160, 163, 198, 217, 231, 238, 241, 243, 246, 256, 260, 261, 263, 268, 268a], *Ph. conissans* (Fr.) M.M. Moser [066, 163a, 231, 256], *Ph. flammans* (Batsch : Fr.) P. Kumm. [210, 231], *Ph. flavida* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Singer [013, 018, 025, 259], *Ph. gummosa* (Lasch : Fr.) Singer [025, 038, 066, 118, 119, 212, 268a], *Ph. highlandensis* (Peck) A.H. Sm. & Hesler [025, 091, 092, 111, 112, 127, 128, 132, 134, 239, 248], ? *Ph. jahnii* Tjall.-Beuk. & Bas [see *Ph. adiposa*], *Ph. lenta* (Pers. : Fr.) Singer [025], *Ph. limonella* (Peck) Sacc. [066], *Ph. lubrica* (Pers. : Fr.) Singer [026], *Ph. lucifera* (Lasch) Quél. [013, 015, 016, 066, 151, 163, 199], *Ph. populnea* (Pers. : Fr.) Kuyper & Tjall.-Beuk. [064, 148, 217, 231, 253, 260, 268a], *Ph. spumosa* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer [017, 038, 056, 066, 097, 118, 119, 175, 210, 212, 231, 256], *Ph. squarrosa* (Weigel : Fr.) P. Kumm. [001, 002, 003, 004, 016, 064, 065, 066, 102, 159, 162, 166, 174, 180, 182, 183, 231], *Ph. subochracea* (A.H. Sm.) A.H. Sm. & Hesler [066], *Ph. subsquarrosa* (Fr.) Quél. [260], *Ph. tuberculosa* (Schaeff. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [025, 026, 027, 066, 091, 092, 231, 256, 285]
- Psilocybe bullacea* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [066], *P. coprophila* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [066], *P. crobula* (Fr.) Singer [259], *P. inquilina* (Fr. : Fr.) Bres. [112, 251], *P. merdaria* (Fr. : Fr.) Ricken [127, 128], *P. montana* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [097], *P. pratensis* P.D. Orton [134, 231], *P. squamosa* (Pers. : Fr.) P.D. Orton [038, 112, 113, 118, 119, 278]
- Stropharia aeruginosa* (Curtis : Fr.) Quél. [015, 025, 036, 037, 066, 087, 112, 113, 132, 134, 135, 173, 206, 207, 214, 231, 239, 244, 248, 251], *S. caerulea* Kreisel [087], *S. coronilla* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [015, 016, 038, 046, 047, 050, 058, 062, 064, 066, 091, 092, 111, 112, 118, 119, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 135, 136, 152, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 189, 203, 231, 239, 248, 251, 279], *S. hornemannii* (Fr. : Fr.) S. Lundell & Nannf. [268a]; *S. inuncta* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [038, 118, 119], *S. rugosoannulata* Farl. ex Murrill [004], *S. semiglobata* s. lat. (Batsch : Fr.) Quél. [025, 066, 112, 135, 148, 163, 172, 189, 210, 231, 239, 244, 248, 252a, 265]
- Tricholomataceae
- Arrhenia lobata* (Pers. : Fr.) Kühner & Lamoure ex Redhead [264], *A. retiruga* (Bull. : Fr.) Redhead [210]
- Calocybe carnea* (Bull. : Fr.) Donk [025], *C. gambosa* (Fr. : Fr.) Donk [039, 112, 136]
- Chrysomphalina grossula* (Pers.) Norvell, Redhead & Ammirati [231, 256]
- Clitocybe agrestis* Harmaja [285], *C. alexandri* (Gillet)

- Konrad [098, 111, 112, 136, 138, 231, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 279], *C. alnetorum* J. Favre [022, 025], *C. bresadolana* Singer [as 'bresadoliana'] [066, 203, 239, 248], *C. brumalis* (Fr. : Fr.) Gillet [024, 025], *C. candicans* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [097, 157, 203], *C. clavipes* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [011, 018, 025, 066, 095, 097, 132, 174, 203, 265], *C. costata* Kühner & Romagn. [203], *C. dealbata* (Sowerby : Fr.) Gillet [? = *C. rivulosa* (Pers.) P. Kumm.] [011, 016, 022, 024, 025, 038, 095, 098, 112, 118, 119, 132, 155, 157, 174, 189, 203, 212, 231, 265, 268a, 279, 284], *C. diatretra* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [025], *C. bicolor* (Pers.) J.E. Lange [025], *C. ditopa* (Fr. : Fr.) Gillet [025, 228], *C. dryadicola* (J. Favre) Harmaja [025, 066], *C. foetens* Melot [026, 203], *C. fragrans* Sowerby : Fr. [026, 027, 203, 231, 256], *C. geotropa* (Bull.) Quél. [021, 025, 035, 036, 037, 044, 091, 092, 111, 112, 121, 123, 127, 128, 132, 135, 136, 154, 205, 206, 207, 231, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 251, 260, 266, 278, 280], *C. gibba* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [011, 016, 017, 023, 024, 025, 030, 041, 055, 064, 097, 173, 210, 214, 221, 231, 265, 268, 270, 277], *C. harperi* Murrill [112, 135, 252a], *C. houghtonii* (W. Phillips) Dennis [236], *C. inornata* (Sowerby : Fr.) Gillet [011, 252a], *C. laccata* (Scop.) Quél. var. *amethystea* Berk. & Broome [256], *C. lateritia* J. Favre [025], *C. martiorum* J. Favre [055], *C. maxima* (Gaertn. & G. Mey. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [112, 136, 285], *C. metachroa* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [156], *C. nebularis* (Batsch : Fr.) Quél. [011, 018, 025, 030, 042, 219, 231], *C. obsoleta* (Batsch) Quél. [066, 203], *C. odora* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [011, 015, 025, 035, 036, 037, 091, 092, 094, 111, 112, 127, 128, 132, 135, 136, 157, 168, 203, 205, 207, 231, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 251, 265, 278, 280], [*C. parilis* (Fr. : Fr.) Sacc., *nom. dubium*] [189, 193], *C. paropsis* (Fr.) Sacc. [210, 231], *C. phaeophthalma* (Pers.) Kuyper [204, 206, 207, 210, 231, 278, 280], *C. phyllophila* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [013, 039, 066, 157, 174, 199, 203, 206, 207, 285], *C. radicellata* Gillet [025, 097, 134, 231, 278, 280], *C. rhizophora* (Velen.) Joss. [030, 090, 091, 092, 099, 102, 103, 110, 112, 231], *C. sinopica* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [025], *C. squamulosa* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [098, 099, 103, 113, 231, 241, 242, 243, 258, 285], *C. subspadicea* (J.E. Lange) Bon & Chevassut [112, 239, 248, 279, 284], *C. tornata* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [118, 119, 212, 231], *C. vermicularis* (Fr.) Quél. [025, 239, 244, 248], *C. vibecina* (Fr.) Quél. [278]
- Clitocybula familia* (Peck) Singer [189, 231]
- Collybia cirrhata* (Schumach. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [025], *C. cookei* (Bres.) J.D. Arnold [024, 025, 066], *C. tuberosa* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [219, 231], *C. verna* Ryman [162a, 163]
- Cystoderma ambrosii* (Bres.) A.H. Sm. & Singer [066], *C. amianthinum* (Scop. : Fr.) Fayod [011, 018, 024, 025, 091, 092, 097, 111, 112, 113, 134, 135, 221, 231, 236, 239, 244, 248, 252a], *C. carcharias* (Pers.) Fayod [097, 239, 244, 248], *C. fallax* A.H. Sm. & Singer [025, 097], *C. granulorum* (Batsch : Fr.) Fayod [025, 026, 027, 157, 203, 239, 248], *C. longisporum* (Kühner) Heinem. & Thoen ex Arnolds [072], *C. superbum* Huijsman [004]
- Delicatula integrella* (Pers. : Fr.) Pat. [231, 270]
- Gamundia striatula* (Kühner) Raithelh. [039, 219, 231]
- Gymnopus acervatus* (Fr. : Fr.) Murrill [118, 119, 212, 217], *G. brassicolens* (Romagn.) Antonín & Noordel. [112, 203, 231, 270], *G. confluens* (Pers. : Fr.) Antonín, Halling & Noordel. [025, 195, 203], *G. dryophilus* (Bull. : Fr.) Murrill [004, 011, 016, 024, 025, 026, 027, 066, 091, 092, 112, 131, 136, 151, 155, 157, 163, 172, 197, 203, 204, 205, 206, 207, 210, 221, 231, 236, 239, 248, 278, 279, 280], *G. erythropus* (Pers. : Fr.) Antonín, Halling & Noordel. [025, 064, 091, 092, 111, 112, 155, 205, 239, 248, 251], *G. fuscopurpureus* (Pers. : Fr.) Antonín, Halling & Noordel. [038, 118, 119, 231, 270], *G. fusipes* (Bull. : Fr.) Gray [023, 025, 066], *G. hariolorum* (Bull. : Fr.) Antonín, Halling & Noordel. [026, 066], *G. ocior* (Pers.) Antonín & Noordel. [112, 136, 156, 239, 248], *G. oreadoides* (Pass.) Antonín & Noordel. [172], *G. peronatus* (Bolton : Fr.) Antonín, Halling & Noordel. [042, 231, 252a, 270]
- Hemimycena delectabilis* (Peck) Singer [210, 231], *H. lactea* (Pers. : Fr.) Singer [132], *H. pseudogracilis* (Kühner & Maire) Singer [112, 239, 244, 248]
- Hygrocybe acutoconica* (Clem.) Singer [210, 231], *H. ceracea* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [039, 205], *H. citrina* (Rea) J.E. Lange [042, 091, 096], *H. conica* (Schaeff. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [018, 025, 046, 157, 174, 204, 205, 206, 207, 221, 231, 265, 270, 285], *H. miniata* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [191], *H. nitrata* (Pers.) Wünsche [047], *H. perplexa* (A.H. Sm. & Hesler) Arnolds [221, 226, 236], *H. persistens* (Britzelm.) Singer s. lat. [018, 025, 132, 220, 231, 285], *H. persistens* (Britzelm.) Singer var. *konradii* (R. Haller Aar.) Boertm. [023, 025, 041, 231, 285], *H. psittacina* (Schaeff. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [039, 205, 206, 207, 221, 224], *H. punicea* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [287], *H. russocoriacea* (Berk. & T.K. Mill.) P.D. Orton & Watling [231], *H. virginea* (Wulfen : Fr.) P.D. Orton & Watling var. *virginea* [025, 042, 203, 204, 205, 206, 207, 219, 221, 231, 236, 269], *H. virginea* var. *fuscescens* (Bres.) Arnolds [025]
- Hygrophorus agathosmus* (Fr.) Fr. [053, 157], *H. aureus* Arrh. [018, 025], *H. calophyllus* P. Karst. [002, 180, 231], *H. camarophyllus* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Dumée, Grandjean & Maire [042, 090, 098,

- 110, 239, 248], *H. chrysodon* (Batsch : Fr.) Fr. [002, 025, 098, 112, 113, 127, 128, 132, 134, 136, 144, 149, 157, 180, 182, 183, 221, 228, 231, 236, 239, 243, 248, 257, 270], *H. discoideus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [036, 037, 203], *H. discoxanthus* (Fr.) Rea [025], *H. eburneus* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [018, 025, 112, 132, 135, 136, 189, 203, 231, 252a], *H. erubescens* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [066, 202], *H. fuscoalbus* (Lasch : Fr.) Fr. [231], *H. gliocyclus* Fr. [002, 180, 231, 236], *H. hedrychii* (Velen.) K. Kult [023, 025, 252a, 284], *H. hypothejus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [018, 025, 111, 112, 126, 132, 135, 136, 137, 239, 248, 269, 279, 281], *H. latitabundus* Britzelm. [020], *H. ligatus* Fr. : Fr. [017, 025, 203, 226], *H. limacinus* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. [025], *H. lucorum* Kalchbr. [020, 025], *H. marzuolus* (Fr. : Fr.) Bres. [042, 066, 268a], *H. olivaceoalbus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [036, 037], *H. penarius* Fr. [025], *H. piceae* Kühner [020, 025], *H. poetarum* R. Heim [020, 024, 025], *H. pudorinus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 180, 185, 203, 231], *H. queletii* Bres. [061], *H. russula* (Fr. : Fr.) Kauffman [098, 228, 231, 236], *H. unicolor* Gröger [025, 038, 118, 119, 212, 226, 228, 236]
- Hypsizygyus ulmarius* (Bull. : Fr.) Redhead [004, 231]
- Lepista flaccida* (Sowerby : Fr.) Pat. [039, 060, 138, 221, 267, 268, 278, 280], *L. glaucocana* (Bres.) Singer [025], *L. inversa* (Scop. : Fr.) Pat. [018, 039, 040, 056, 064, 138, 175, 219, 228, 231, 236, 279, 281], *L. irina* (Fr.) H.E. Bigelow [018, 023, 025, 040, 064, 268], *L. luscina* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer [040, 099, 103, 231], *L. nuda* (Bull. : Fr.) Cooke [002, 005, 010, 011, 015, 018, 021, 023, 024, 025, 030, 035, 037, 066, 087, 090, 091, 092, 093, 094, 098, 099, 103, 110, 111, 112, 113, 127, 128, 131, 132, 135, 136, 149, 154, 155, 157, 163a, 166, 168, 174, 180, 182, 183, 191, 199, 203, 205, 206, 207, 231, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 261, 263, 265, 266, 278, 279, 280], *L. personata* (Fr. : Fr.) Cooke [001, 002, 008, 062, 064, 159, 163, 163a, 166, 239, 244, 248, 279], *L. saeva* (Fr.) P.D. Orton [060, 131, 132, 134, 136, 154, 231, 252a, 260, 267, 268a], *L. sordida* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer [026, 134, 203, 204, 205, 206, 207, 219, 231, 279]
- Leucopaxillus albissimus* (Peck) Singer [008, 231], *L. amarus* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Kühner [180, 231], *L. candidus* (Bres.) Singer [098], *L. gentianeus* (Quél.) Kotl. [008, 231], *L. giganteus* (Sowerby : Fr.) Singer [219, 231], *L. paradoxus* (Costantin & L.M. Dufour) Boursier [039]
- Lichenomphalia umbellifera* (L. : Fr.) Redhead, Lutzoni, Moncalvo & Vilgalys [025, 118, 119, 172]
- Lyophyllum connatum* (Schumach. : Fr.) Singer [072, 157], *L. decastes* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer [204, 205, 206, 207], *L. favrei* (R. Haller Aar. & R. Haller Suhr) R. Haller Aar. & R. Haller Suhr [239, 248], *L. infumatum* (Bres.) Kühner [066], *L. leucophaeatum* (P. Karst.) P. Karst. [066], *L. lorricatum* (Fr.) Kühner ex Kalamees [156], *L. semitale* (Fr. : Fr.) Kühner [066], *L. transforme* (Britzelm.) Singer [156, 157]
- Megacollybia platyphylla* (Pers. : Fr.) Kotl. & Pouzar. [210, 231]
- Melanoleuca arcuata* (Bull. : Fr.) Singer [066, 131, 153, 278], *M. brevipes* (Bull. : Fr.) Pat. [013, 016, 024, 025, 064, 066, 159, 160], *M. cognata* (Fr.) Konrad & Maubl. s. lat. [011, 015, 025, 026, 027, 157, 203, 219, 231, 267], *M. cognata* (Fr.) Konrad & Maubl. var. *cognata* [035, 060, 066, 239, 244, 248], *M. excissa* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer s. lat. [025, 066, 137, 157, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 268a, 279], *M. excissa* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer var. *excissa* [047, 055, 231], *M. graminicola* (Velen.) Kühner & Maire [013, 015, 025, 026, 027, 091, 092, 157, 203], *M. grammopodia* (Bull. : Fr.) Murrill [010, 048, 195, 219, 231], *M. humilis* (Pers. : Fr.) Pat. [024, 025, 064, 066], *M. luteolosperma* (Britzelm.) Singer [066, 197], *M. melaleuca* (Pers. : Fr.) Murrill [011, 015, 025, 039, 066, 127, 128, 159, 160, 189, 195, 199, 231, 278, 280], *M. oreina* (Fr. : Fr.) Kühner & Maire [269], *M. paedida* (Fr.) Kühner & Maire [025, 066, 239, 248], *M. schumacheri* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer [066], *M. strictipes* (P. Karst.) Jul. Schäff. [016, 131, 195, 252a], *M. stridula* (Fr.) Singer [025, 026, 027, 066, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163a, 166, 203, 279], *M. subalpina* (Britzelm.) Bresinsky & Stangl [010, 015, 024, 025, 026, 027, 066], *M. subpulverulenta* (Pers.) Singer [010, 015, 025, 042], *M. substrictipes* Kühner [027, 066, 155, 157], *M. turrita* (Fr.) Singer [153]
- Mycena abramsii* (Murrill) Murrill [025, 156], *M. acicula* (Schaeff.) P. Kumm. [162a], *M. adonis* (Bull. : Fr.) Gray [026, 066], *M. aetites* (Fr.) Quél. [156], *M. alcalina* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [159, 160, 210, 231, 256, 259, 270], *M. amicta* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [066], *M. atroalba* (Bolton : Fr.) Fr. [189, 231], *M. aurantiomarginata* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [156], *M. capillaripes* Peck [025, 156], *M. capillaris* (Schumach. : Fr.) Gillet [023, 025, 112], *M. crocata* (Schrad. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 112, 135, 252a], *M. epipterygia* (Scop. : Fr.) Gray var. *epipterygia* [024, 025, 091, 092, 097, 112, 113, 132, 134, 135, 147, 148, 203, 231, 239, 248, 252a, 259], *M. epipterygia* var. *lignicola* A.H. Sm. [203], *M. epipterygia* var. *pelliculosa* (Fr. : Fr.) Maas Geest. [203], *M. epipterygia* var. *viscosa* (Secr. ex Maire) Ricken [259], *M. epipterygioides* A. Pearson [156], [*M. excisa* (Lasch) P. Kumm., nom. dubium] [038, 118, 119, 212], *M. filopes* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [231, 256], *M. flavescens* Velen. [025], *M. flavoalba* (Fr.) Quél. [024, 025], *M. galericulata* (Scop. : Fr.) Schaeff. [004, 040, 091, 092, 097, 132, 166, 203, 231, 259, 268a], *M. galopus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm.

- s. lat. [015, 023, 025, 203, 204, 205, 206, 207], *M. haematopus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [259, 275], *M. hiemalis* (Osbeck) Quél. [038, 066, 118, 119, 189, 212, 231, 259], *M. immaculata* Peck [? *nom. dubium*] [189], *M. inclinata* (Fr.) Quél. [025, 206, 207, 231, 256], *M. laevigata* (Lasch) Gillet [025], *M. latifolia* (Peck) A.H. Sm. [026], *M. leptocephala* (Pers. : Fr.) Gillet [025, 026, 039, 097, 201, 203], *M. leucogala* (Cooke) Sacc. [015, 112, 204, 205, 206, 207], *M. megaspora* Kauffman [278], *M. metata* (Secr. ex Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [066], *M. niveipes* (Murrill) Murrill [047, 145, 146, 231], *M. olida* Bres. [203], [*M. parabolica* (Fr.) Quél., *nom. dubium*] [231, 256], *M. pelianthina* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [026, 201], [*M. plicosa* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm., *nom. dubium*] [210, 231], *M. polygramma* (Bull. : Fr.) Gray [025, 026, 038, 040, 098, 118, 119, 157, 203, 212, 219, 231, 239, 248, 259], *M. pseudocorticola* Kühner [041, 231], *M. pura* (Pers. : Fr.) Sacc. [022, 024, 025, 026, 027, 036, 037, 112, 122, 127, 128, 132, 135, 148, 174, 189, 203, 219, 231, 239, 244, 248], *M. rosea* (Bull.) Gramberg [022, 024, 025, 112, 174, 203, 239, 248, 251, 252a, 261, 263], *M. rosella* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [112], *M. sanguinolenta* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [016, 025, 203, 231, 270], *M. seynesii* Quél. [036, 037, 278], *M. silvae-nigrae* Maas Geest. & Schwöbel [066, 199], *M. speirea* (Fr. : Fr.) Gillet [231, 256], *M. strobilicola* J. Favre & Kühner [062, 091, 092, 094, 111, 112, 127, 128, 132, 134, 135, 168, 231, 239, 244, 246, 248, 251, 252a, 266], *M. stylobates* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [231, 270], *M. subincarnata* Peck [189, 231], *M. tintinnabulum* (Fr.) Quél. [005, 231, 256], *M. vitilis* (Fr.) Quél. [118], *M. vulgaris* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [045, 192, 231], *M. xantholeuca* Kühner [066], *M. zephirus* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [042]
- Myxomphalia maura* (Fr. : Fr.) Hora [097, 197]
- Omphalina obscurata* D.A. Reid [066], *O. oniscus* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [023, 025, 026, 027, 066, 157, 172, 203], *O. pyxidata* (Bull. : Fr.) Quél. [163a, 235, 265], *O. rivulicola* (J. Favre) Lamoure [026, 203], *O. subhepatica* (Batsch) Murrill [023, 210, 231], *O. velutina* (Quél.) Quél. [231, 270], *O. velutipes* P.D. Orton [166]
- Ossicaulis lignatilis* (Pers.) Redhead & Ginns [047, 231]
- Panellus mitis* (Pers. : Fr.) Singer [112, 231, 246, 256], *P. pusillus* (Pers.) Burds. & O.K. Mill [259], *P. serotinus* (Schröd. : Fr.) J.G. Kühn [132, 231, 256], *P. stipticus* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Karst. [001, 003, 006, 025, 031, 157, 173, 203, 216, 217, 221, 231, 236, 253, 254, 256, 259, 270]
- Phaeolepiota aurea* (Matt. : Fr.) Maire [004, 111, 112, 174, 219, 231]
- Phyllotopsis nidulans* (Pers. : Fr.) Singer [024, 025, 038, 118, 119, 212]
- Pleurocybella porrigens* (Pers. : Fr.) Singer [197]
- Pseudoclitocybe cyathiformis* (Bull. : Fr.) Singer [025, 175, 231, 256, 279]
- Pseudoomphalina compressipes* (Peck.) Singer [042]
- Resupinatus applicatus* (Batsch : Fr.) Gray [256, 259], *R. trichotis* (Pers.) Singer [156], *R. unguicularis* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer [256]
- Rickenella fibula* (Bull. : Fr.) Raithehl. [112, 231, 251, 270]
- Tephrocycbe ambusta* (Fr. : Fr.) Donk [038, 118, 119, 212], *T. confusa* (P.D. Orton) M.M. Moser [025], *T. palustris* (Peck) Donk [025]
- Tricholoma acerbum* (Bull. : Fr.) Vent. [024, 025, 066], *T. albobrunneum* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [011, 015, 017, 025, 180, 182, 183, 186, 231], *T. album* (Schaeff. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [025, 066], *T. apium* Jul. Schäff. [066], *T. argyraceum* (Bull.) Gillet [151, 203], *T. arvernense* Bon [025], *T. aurantium* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Ricken [025, 066, 199, 210, 278, 280], *T. basirubens* (Bon) A. Riva & Bon [025], *T. batschii* Gulden [015, 017, 018, 025, 064, 091, 092, 112, 113, 132, 134, 135, 203, 205, 206, 207, 231, 239, 248, 251, 252a, 268, 282, 284], *T. caligatum* (Viv.) Ricken [004, 015, 030, 066, 088, 089, 098, 112, 121, 127, 128, 132, 134, 136, 199, 203, 231, 239, 248, 252a], *T. cingulatum* (Almfelt : Fr.) Jacobasch [025], *T. colossium* (Fr.) Quél. [015, 087, 091, 092, 112, 121, 132, 136, 252a], *T. columbetta* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [066, 112, 136, 199], *T. flavovirens* (Pers. : Fr.) S. Lundell [002, 009, 018, 066, 112, 136, 149, 174, 182, 183, 199, 203, 231, 238, 241, 242, 243, 252a, 275, 284], *T. focale* (Fr.) Ricken [004, 112, 203], *T. fulvum* (DC. : Fr.) Sacc. [025], *T. imbricatum* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [025, 066, 157], *T. inocyboides* Corner [148], *T. josserandii* Bon [039], *T. lascivum* (Fr. : Fr.) Gillet [024, 025, 064, 203], *T. luridum* (Schaeff.) P. Kumm. [025, 087, 162a], *T. myomyces* (Pers. : Fr.) J.E. Lange [066], *T. orirubens* Quél. [018, 025, 039, 066, 182, 183, 203, 231], *T. pardalotum* Herink & Kotl. [066, 174, 239, 248], *T. pessundatum* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [008, 025, 039], *T. populinum* J.E. Lange [007, 008, 015, 026, 027, 055, 066, 163, 231], *T. portentosum* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. [024, 025, 026, 027, 066], *T. radotinense* Pilát & Charvát [066], *T. robustum* (Alb. & Schwein.) Ricken [004], *T. saponaceum* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [017, 024, 025, 089, 278], *T. sculpturatum* (Fr.) Quél. [025, 026, 027, 065, 066, 159, 162, 162a, 199, 203, 204, 206, 207], *T. sciodes* (Pers.) C. Martin [010], *T. sejunctum* (Sowerby : Fr.) Quél. s. lat. [025, 203, 220, 231], *T. sejunctum* (Sowerby : Fr.) Quél. var. *coniferarum* Bon [206, 207], *T. squarulosum* Bres. [205, 206, 207], *T. stans* (Fr.) Sacc. [025, 066, 197, 203, 279, 282, 284], *T. striatum* (Schaeff.)

Sacc. [210], *T. sulphurescens* Bres. [024, 025], *T. sulphureum* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [011, 040, 112, 174, 206, 207, 278], *T. terreum* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Quél. [002, 010, 011, 015, 016, 017, 018, 024, 025, 026, 027, 035, 036, 037, 038, 041, 066, 090, 091, 092, 093, 097, 098, 102, 110, 111, 112, 118, 119, 127, 128, 131, 132, 134, 135, 136, 157, 168, 169, 180, 182, 183, 199, 203, 205, 206, 207, 214, 231, 236, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 257, 261, 263, 265, 266, 269, 278, 279, 280, 281, 283, 284], *T. triste* (Fr.) Quél. [118, 119, 231], *T. ustale* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [015, 023, 025, 060, 065, 098, 112, 122, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 174, 275], *T. ustaloides* Romagn. [091, 092, 124, 131], *T. virgatum* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Kumm. [008, 015, 025, 026, 066, 157, 199, 203, 231, 252a]

Tricholomopsis rutilans (Schaeff. : Fr.) Singer [024, 025, 149, 210, 221, 228, 231, 236]

Xeromphalina campanella (Batsch : Fr.) Maire [025, 066, 091, 092, 132, 153, 157, 231, 256], *X. caudicinalis* (With. : Fr.) Kühner & Maire [025, 066, 261, 263]

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Auriculariaceae

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Boletaceae

Boletus aereus Bull. : Fr. [008, 010, 231], *B. appendiculatus* Schaeff. [024, 025, 040, 261, 265], *B. badius* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [002, 024, 039, 042, 149, 215, 231, 257], *B. calopus* Pers. : Fr. [022, 024, 025, 042, 191, 220, 231], *B. chrysenteron* Bull. [011, 018, 024, 025, 030, 033, 036, 037, 054, 064, 066, 091, 092, 102, 112, 113, 132, 135, 136, 151, 159, 160, 163, 166, 220, 231, 241, 242, 243, 253, 261, 263, 268, 279], *B. depilatus* Redeuilh [025], *B. dupainii* Boud. [023, 025, 151], *B. edulis* Bull. : Fr. [002, 005, 009, 011, 015, 021, 023, 024, 025, 032, 040, 041, 042, 055, 057, 106, 112, 113, 136, 173,

176, 182, 183, 192, 208, 214, 215, 221, 231, 232, 236, 257], *B. erythropus* (sensu Persoon = *B. queletii* while sensu auct. europ. = *B. luridiformis* Rostk.) [002, 017, 025, 041, 054, 066, 157, 168, 174, 182, 183, 185, 191, 205, 206, 207, 208, 221, 231, 236, 261, 263, 265], *B. fechtneri* Velen. [132], *B. ferrugineus* Schaeff. [025], *B. fragrans* Vittad. [024, 060, 267], *B. impolitus* Fr. [023, 025, 066, 131, 152], *B. lanatus* Rostk. [025], *B. legaliae* Pilát ex Pilát [025, 102, 103, 151, 231], *B. luridus* Schaeff. : Fr. [005, 017, 022, 024, 025, 055, 064, 065, 151, 174, 203, 208, 220, 222, 231, 285], *B. moravicus* Vacek [023, 024, 025, 042], [*B. pinicola* Rea (nom. illeg., a later homonym; ? = *B. pinophilus*)] [001, 003, 031, 216, 217], *B. pinophilus* Pilát & Dermek [112, 113, 136], *B. porosporus* (Imler) Watling [052, 206, 207], *B. pulverulentus* Opat. [036, 037, 087], *B. queletii* Schulzer [041, 042, 231, 270], *B. radicans* Pers. : Fr. [022, 024, 025, 026, 033, 048, 064, 066, 090, 102, 103, 110, 120, 168, 191, 203, 219, 231, 253], *B. regius* Krombh. [219, 231], *B. reticulatus* Schaeff. [009, 011, 024, 025, 026, 027, 219, 231], *B. retipes* Peck [045, 231], *B. rhodopurpureus* Smotl. [151], *B. rhodoxanthus* (Krombh.) Kallenb. [261], *B. rubellus* Krombh. [033, 231, 253, 286], *B. satanas* Lenz [022, 025, 026, 055, 064, 065, 112, 113, 122, 132, 174, 175, 192, 206, 207, 261, 263, 265], *B. satanicolor* Pilát [208], *B. subappendiculatus* Dermek, Lazebníček & J. Veselský [025], *B. subtomentosus* L. : Fr. [018, 024, 025, 026, 027, 038, 039, 066, 119, 151, 212, 219, 231, 253], *B. truncatus* (Singer, Snell & E.A. Dick) Pouzar [039], *B. zelleri* Murrill [220, 231]

Leccinum aurantiacum (Bull.) Gray [025, 038, 118, 119, 132, 191, 212, 219, 231], *L. corsicum* (Rolland) Singer [134, 231], *L. crocipodium* (Letell.) Watling [023, 024, 025], *L. holopus* (Rostk.) Watling [046], *L. insigne* A.H. Sm., Thiers & Watling [231, 270], *L. onychinum* Watling [024, 025], *L. oxydabile* (Singer) Singer [Lannoy & Estadès (1995) treated this name as a nom. dubium] [041, 231, 261, 263], *L. pseudoscabrum* (Kallenb.) Šutara [002, 024, 025, 215, 220, 221, 231, 236, 270], *L. quercinum* Pilát ex Pilát & Dermek [191, 219, 231, 270], *L. scabrum* (Bull. : Fr.) Gray [024, 025, 030, 038, 046, 054, 055, 060, 064, 118, 119, 173, 212, 214, 231, 267, 268], *L. subleucophaeum* E.A. Dick & Snell [231, 270], *L. versipelle* (Fr.) Snell [025, 064, 231, 258, 268]

Porphyrellus porphyrosporus (Fr.) E.-J. Gilbert [220, 231]

Phylloporus pelletieri (Lév.) Quél. [045, 231, 269]

Tylopilus felleus (Bull. : Fr.) P. Karst. [219, 231]

Coniophoraceae

Coniophora arida (Fr. : Fr.) P. Karst. [259], *C. fusispora* (Cooke & Ellis) Cooke [209, 211], *C. olivacea* (Fr.

- : Fr.) P. Karst. [259], *C. puteana* (Schumach. : Fr.) P. Karst. [254, 258, 259]
- Leucogyrophana pinastri* (Fr. : Fr.) Ginns & Weresub [209]
- Gomphidiaceae
- Chroogomphus helveticus* (Singer) M.M. Moser [025, 060, 151, 203], *Ch. rutilus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) O.K. Mill. [002, 010, 011, 017, 018, 025, 030, 033, 035, 036, 037, 064, 066, 089, 091, 092, 093, 094, 098, 112, 113, 126, 127, 128, 132, 134, 135, 136, 137, 144, 151, 157, 168, 180, 199, 203, 205, 206, 207, 210, 221, 231, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 251, 253, 257, 258, 266, 268, 279]
- Gomphidius glutinosus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Fr. [016, 025, 066, 199, 221, 224, 228], *G. gracilis* Berk. [025], *G. maculatus* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. [055, 060, 203], *G. roseus* (Fr. : Fr.) Gillet [056, 060, 064, 171, 267, 268]
- Gyroporaceae
- Gyroporus castaneus* (Bull. : Fr.) Quél. [132]
- Hygrophoropsidaceae
- Hygrophoropsis aurantiaca* (Wulfen : Fr.) Maire [189]
- Tapinella panuoides* (Fr. : Fr.) E.-J. Gilbert [001, 003, 004, 091, 092, 098, 112, 132, 216, 231, 246, 265, 285]
- Leucogastraceae
- Leucogaster liosporus* R. Hesse [211], *L. luteomaculatus* Zeller & Dodge [211], *L. nudus* (Hazsl.) Hollós [211]
- Melanogastraceae
- Melanogaster broomeanus* Berk. [049, 055, 064]
- Paxillaceae
- Paxillus atrotomentosus* (Batsch : Fr.) Fr. [004, 025, 046, 055, 060, 064, 151, 180, 206, 207, 217, 220, 221, 228, 231, 236, 238, 241, 242, 243, 267], *P. involutus* (Batsch : Fr.) Fr. [004, 009, 022, 023, 024, 025, 030, 036, 037, 042, 062, 064, 065, 066, 087, 112, 122, 132, 135, 154, 159, 162, 174, 203, 204, 206, 207, 231, 238, 241, 243, 258, 260], *P. rubicundulus* P.D. Orton [022, 025, 159]
- Rhizopogonaceae
- Rhizopogon luteolus* Fr. [002, 004, 010, 011, 015, 016, 017, 025, 036, 037, 054, 064, 066, 091, 092, 093, 094, 112, 123, 127, 128, 132, 134, 135, 136, 157, 163a, 166, 168, 169, 182, 183, 187, 203, 211, 239, 248, 251, 257, 263, 265, 266, 284], *R. obtextus* (Spreng.) R. Rauschert [153], *R. roseolus* (Corda) Th. Fr. s. lat. [004, 015, 023, 024, 025, 026, 027, 030, 060, 066, 090, 091, 093, 098, 110, 112, 113, 127, 128, 132, 134, 135, 136, 151, 153, 168, 169, 203, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 251, 257, 261, 266, 267, 278, 279, 280], *R. rubescens* Tul. var. *rubescens* [180], *R. vulgaris* (Vittad.) M. Lange [231]
- Sclerodermataceae
- Astraeus hygrometricus* (Pers. : Pers.) Morgan [009, 010, 025, 026, 027, 041, 056, 064, 066, 102, 103, 112, 113, 126, 127, 128, 132, 134, 135, 175, 206, 207, 214, 252a, 253, 261, 263]
- Pisolithus arbizus* (Pers. : Pers.) Rauschert [036, 037, 091, 092, 094, 111, 112, 131, 132, 134, 135, 173, 239, 244, 248, 251], *P. tinctorius* (Pers. : Pers.) Coker & Couch [127, 128]
- Scleroderma areolatum* Ehrenb. [024, 025, 206, 207, 259], *S. bovista* Fr. [094], *S. cepa* Pers. : Pers. [207], *S. citrinum* Pers. : Pers. [046, 127, 128, 206, 207, 236], *S. polyrhizum* (J.F. Gmel. : Pers.) Pers. [025, 206, 245], *S. verrucosum* (Bull. : Pers.) Pers. [036, 037, 042, 055, 163, 163a, 191, 206, 207, 220, 253]
- Suillaceae
- Suillus bellinii* (Inzenga) Kuntze [018, 025, 030, 036, 037, 089, 090, 091, 092, 093, 094, 098, 099, 102, 103, 110, 111, 112, 113, 120, 127, 128, 131, 132, 134, 135, 136, 168, 231, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 251, 275, 279, 284], *S. boudieri* (Quél.) Marchand [097, 134, 231], *S. bovinus* (L. : Fr.) Roussel [002, 018, 024, 025, 033, 041, 111, 112, 113, 132, 136, 215, 231, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 244, 248, 251, 253, 257], *S. collinitus* (Fr.) Kuntze [025, 091, 092, 094, 132, 137, 206, 207, 279, 282], *S. granulatus* (L. : Fr.) Roussel [009, 011, 015, 017, 025, 038, 055, 060, 064, 066, 118, 119, 132, 154, 173, 203, 205, 206, 207, 208, 212, 214, 231, 236, 260, 268, 278], *S. grevillei* (Klotzsch : Fr.) Singer [002, 026, 027, 066, 157, 173, 199, 203, 214, 215, 231, 257], *S. luteus* (L. : Fr.) Roussel [002, 009, 010, 011, 015, 016, 018, 023, 024, 025, 026, 027, 038, 054, 055, 056, 060, 062, 064, 066, 089, 112, 113, 118, 119, 132, 135, 136, 144, 149, 151, 157, 159, 160, 163a, 166, 174, 175, 180, 182, 183, 185, 203, 212, 231, 243, 252a, 257, 261, 263, 265, 268, 268a, 275], *S. pictus* (Peck) A.H. Sm. & Thiers. [041, 231], *S. placidus* (Bonord.) Singer [038, 118, 119, 132, 203, 212, 278], *S. variegatus* (Sw.) Richon & Roze [025, 208, 219, 231, 267]
- Cantharellales
- Botryobasidiaceae
- Botryobasidium candicans* J. Erikss. [259], *B. subcoronatum* (Höhn. & Litsch.) Donk [142, 211]
- Botryohypochnus isabellinus* (Fr. : Fr.) J. Erikss. [211]
- Cantharellaceae
- Cantharellus amethysteus* (Quél.) Sacc. [269], *C. aurora* (Batsch) Kuyper [221, 225, 232], *C. cibarius* Fr. : Fr. var. *cibarius* [005, 021, 023, 024, 025, 032, 042, 046, 064, 057, 105, 112, 113, 135, 136, 153, 171, 180, 181, 182, 183, 184, 187, 192, 203, 205, 206, 207, 215, 220, 221, 222, 232, 236, 238, 241, 242, 243, 251, 257, 268, 269, 270], *C.*

cibarius var. *ferruginascens* (P.D. Orton) Courtec. [024, 025, 046, 064, 205, 206, 207, 220, 222], *C. cinereus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [269], *C. friesii* Quél. [024, 025], *C. subalbidus* A.H. Sm. & Morse [236], *C. tubaeformis* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [149, 189, 220, 221, 236]

Craterellus cornucopioides (L. : Fr.) Pers. [002, 039, 040, 171, 180, 182, 183, 205, 206, 207, 220, 221, 222, 232, 236, 257, 269, 270]

Pseudocraterellus sinuosus (Fr. : Fr.) Corner [041, 207, 221, 236]

Clavulinaceae

Clavulina cinerea (Bull. : Fr.) J. Schröt. [023, 025, 159, 160, 204, 205, 206, 207, 229], *C. coralloides* (L. : Fr.) J. Schröt. [004, 041, 159, 160, 209, 229, 285], *C. rugosa* (Bull. : Fr.) J. Schröt. [004, 018, 025, 046, 279]

Membranomyces spurius (Bourdote) Jülich [066, 202, 259]

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Hydnum molle Fr. [4], *H. repandum* L. : Fr. [002, 035, 089, 091, 092, 098, 132, 180, 182, 183, 203, 205, 206, 207, 209, 215, 220, 221, 222, 228, 229, 232, 236, 252a, 257, 269, 270], *H. rufescens* Schaeff. : Fr. [004, 042, 087, 090, 092, 203, 205, 206, 207, 270], *H. velutinum* Fr. : Fr. [189]

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Ceratobasidiaceae

Thanatephorus fusisporus (J. Schröt.) Hauerslev & P. Roberts [229], *T. ochraceus* (Masse) P. Roberts [259]

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Dacrymycetaceae

Calocera cornea (Batsch : Fr.) Fr. [064, 256, 259], *C. viscosa* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 064, 112, 132, 171, 221, 236, 246, 256]

Dacrymyces capitatus Schwein. [259], *D. deliquescens* (Bull.) Duby var. *deliquescens* [256], *D. stillatus* Nees : Fr. [142, 206, 207, 259], *D. variisporus* McNabb [025, 066, 229]

Hymenochaetales

Hymenochaetaceae

Coltricia cinnamomea (Jacq.) Murrill [025], *C. spathulata* (Hook.) Murrill [176], *C. perennis* (L. : Fr.) Murrill [112, 113, 151, 208]

Hymenochaete cruenta (Pers. : Fr.) Donk [214, 217, 256], *H. fuliginosa* (Pers. : Fr.) Lévy [209, 259], *H. rubiginosa* (Dicks. : Fr.) Lévy [001, 003, 006, 173, 203, 206, 207, 214, 216, 217, 254, 256, 259]

Inonotus cuticularis (Fr. : Fr.) P. Karst. [170, 253], *I. dryadeus* (Pers.) Murrill [056, 163, 173, 175, 214, 217, 255, 260], *I. hispidus* (Bolton : Fr.) P. Karst. [001, 003, 025, 033, 055, 059, 064, 066, 097,

098, 102, 103, 112, 126, 127, 128, 154, 163, 170, 173, 176, 199, 214, 217, 218, 221, 228, 236, 239, 246, 248, 253, 260, 275], *I. nidus-pici* Pilát [253], *I. obliquus* (Pers. : Fr.) Pilát [217], *I. radiatus* (Sowerby : Fr.) P. Karst. [028, 066, 151, 173, 214, 217], *I. rheades* (Pers.) Bondartsev & Singer [026, 066, 155, 157, 173, 199, 208, 217], *I. tamaricis* (Pat.) Maire [066, 068], *I. vulpinus* (Fr.) P. Karst. [217]

Phellinus chrysoloma (Fr.) Donk [001, 003, 216, 220], *Ph. conchatus* (Pers. : Fr.) Quél. [203, 208], *Ph. contiguus* (Pers. : Fr.) Pat. [253], *Ph. ferreus* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin [259], *Ph. hartigii* (Allesch. & Schnabl) Pat. [025, 066, 173, 217], *Ph. igniarius* (L. : Fr.) Quél. [024, 025, 026, 027, 029, 041, 047, 050, 062, 064, 066, 091, 092, 097, 101, 103, 112, 126, 127, 128, 129, 145, 146, 148, 151, 154, 155, 157, 163, 163a, 170, 172, 173, 176, 189, 198, 199, 204, 206, 207, 208, 217, 218, 239, 246, 248, 255, 256, 260, 268, 268a], *Ph. laevigatus* (Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin [026, 066], *Ph. pilatii* Černý [253], *Ph. pini* (Brot. : Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer [001, 003, 028, 029, 030, 031, 091, 092, 094, 098, 111, 112, 127, 128, 134, 135, 171, 173, 189, 203, 208, 217, 218, 239, 241, 243, 246, 248, 251, 252a, 256], *Ph. pomaceus* (Pers.) Maire [026, 027, 028, 029, 046, 047, 050, 056, 059, 060, 062, 064, 066, 090, 094, 098, 102, 103, 126, 129, 145, 146, 147, 153, 163, 163a, 168, 170, 173, 175, 176, 189, 197, 241, 243, 246, 256, 259, 267, 268, 268a], *Ph. punctatus* (Fr.) Pilát [066, 173, 214, 217, 218], *Ph. rimosus* (Berk.) Pilát [134, 170], *Ph. robustus* (P. Karst.) Bourdot & Galzin s. lat. [028, 056, 066, 113, 175, 203, 214, 217, 238, 241, 243, 252a], *Ph. torulosus* (Pers. : Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin [001, 003, 031, 033, 091, 092, 098, 102, 103, 111, 112, 113, 170, 173, 176, 203, 214, 216, 217, 218, 238, 239, 241, 243, 246, 248, 252a, 253, 255, 266, 275], *Ph. tremulae* (Bondartsev) Bondartsev & Borissov [025, 176, 217], *Ph. viticola* (Schwein. : Fr.) Donk [066, 199, 202], *Ph. vorax* (Harkn.) Černý [066, 229]

Phylloporia ribis (Schumach. : Fr.) Ryvarden [034, 091, 092]

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Basidioradulum radula (Fr. : Fr.) Nobles [229, 258]
Hypodontia arguta (Fr. : Fr.) J. Erikss. [209], *H. barba-jovis* (Bull. : Fr.) J. Erikss. [259], *H. breviseta* (P. Karst.) J. Erikss. [259], *H. crustosa* (Pers. : Fr.) J. Erikss. [142, 258], *H. pallidula* (Bres.) J. Erikss. [211], *H. rimosissima* (Peck) Gilb. [142], *H. sambuci* (Pers. : Fr.) J. Erikss. [259]

Kneiffella abieticola (Bourdote & Galzin) Jülich & Stalpers [209]

Schizopora paradoxa (Schrad. : Fr.) Donk [203, 258, 259]

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Geastrum asper Lloyd. [098], *G. corollinum* (Batsch) Hollós [113], *G. coronatum* Pers. : Pers. [206, 207], *G. elegans* Vittad. [112, 285], *G. fimbriatum* Fr. [025, 030, 066, 097, 098, 137, 157, 168, 199, 203, 204, 206, 207, 221, 229, 236, 238, 241, 243, 279], *G. floriforme* Vittad. [098], *G. fornicatum* (Huds.) Hook. [111, 112, 269, 285], *G. pectinatum* Pers. : Pers. [011, 025, 026, 027, 066, 090, 091, 092, 110, 112, 127, 128, 134, 135, 203, 239, 244, 248, 252a], *G. pseudostriatum* Hollós [211], *G. rufescens* Pers. : Pers. [011, 015, 025, 048, 066, 199, 229, 285], *G. schmidelii* Vittad. [066, 235, 269], *G. triplex* Jungh. [025, 066, 097, 098, 111, 112, 168, 203, 239, 248, 266]

Myriostoma coliforme (With. : Pers.) Corda [034]

Sphaerobolus stellatus Tode : Pers. [259]

Gomphaceae

Clavariadelphus pistillaris (L. : Fr.) Donk [001, 003, 031, 040, 189, 203, 205, 206, 207, 270], *C. truncatus* (Quél.) Donk [002, 025, 132, 157, 180, 182, 183]

Gomphus clavatus (Pers. : Fr.) Gray [066, 132, 153, 221, 225, 232, 236], *G. stereoides* Corner [233]

Lentaria afflata (Lagger) Corner [025]

Phallaceae

Anthurus muellerianus Kalchbr. var. *aseroeformis* (E. Fisch.) Sacc. [219]

Clathrus ruber [P. Micheli ex] Pers. : Pers. [024, 025, 041, 087, 204, 206, 207, 236, 285]

Mutinus caninus (Huds. : Pers.) Fr. [025, 063, 204, 206, 207, 269]

Phallus hadriani Vent. : Pers. [063, 191], *Ph. impudicus* L. : Pers. [025, 033, 036, 037, 040, 087, 101, 103, 112, 126, 127, 128, 131, 132, 155, 159, 160, 180, 189, 203, 205, 206, 207, 220, 221, 222, 228, 236, 269, 285]

Ramariaceae

Gautieria graveolens Vittad. [211]

Ramaria abietina (Pers. : Fr.) Quél. [066], *R. aurea* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Quél. [016, 018, 021, 024, 025, 042, 205, 206, 207, 228, 270], *R. bataillei* (Maire) Corner [132], *R. botrytis* (Pers. : Fr.) Ricken [004, 024, 025, 041, 112, 121, 132, 136, 189], *R. fennica* (P. Karst.) Ricken var. *griseolilacina* Schild [132], *R. flava* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Quél. [002, 004, 021, 023, 024, 025, 033, 066, 087, 098, 112, 113, 132, 136, 157, 171, 192, 199, 205, 206, 207, 215, 220, 236, 238, 241, 242, 243, 248, 253], *R. flavescens* (Jul. Schäff.) R.H. Petersen [025], *R. flavobrunnescens* (G.F. Atk.) Corner [025], *R. formosa* (Pers. : Fr.) Quél. [004, 033, 055, 098, 112, 113, 122, 132, 174, 206, 207, 253, 269, 270], *R. largentii* Marr & D.E. Stuntz [018, 025], *R. lutea* (Vent.) Schild [018, 021, 024, 025, 054], *R. mairei* Donk [270],

R. obtusissima (Peck) Corner [066, 202], *R. stricta* (Pers. : Fr.) Quél. [002, 004, 054, 062, 168, 180, 182, 183, 185, 206, 220, 258, 259, 285, 286]

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Albatrellaceae

Albatrellus cristatus (Schaeff. : Fr.) Kotl. & Pouzar [025, 226], *A. subrubescens* (Murrill) Pouzar [025]

Atheliaceae

Amphinema byssoides (Pers. : Fr.) J. Erikss. [211]

Amylocorticium cebennense (Bourdot) Pouzar [211], *A. laceratum* (Litsch.) Hjortstam & Ryvarden [259]

Athelia arachnoidea (Berk.) Jülich. [259], *A. rolfsii* (Curzi) C.C. Tu & Kimbr. [211]

Athelidium aurantiacum (M.P. Christ.) Oberw. [259]

Bysocorticium atrovirens (Fr. : Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer [258], *B. pulchrum* (S. Lundell) M.P. Christ. [259]

Cristinia helvetica (Pers.) Parmasto [209, 211]

Piloderma bicolor (Peck) Jülich [142], *P. byssinum* (P. Karst.) Jülich [211]

Plicaturopsis crispa (Pers. : Fr.) D.A. Reid [112, 113, 246]

Corticaceae

Corticium croceum (Kunze) Bres. [211]

Dendrothele macrospora (Bres.) P.A. Lemke [259]

Laeticorticium roseum (Pers. : Fr.) Donk [142]

Pulcherricium caeruleum (Lam. : Fr.) Parmasto [142, 170, 173, 203, 214, 217, 229, 254]

Vuilleminia comedens (Nees : Fr.) Maire [211], *V. megalospora* Bres. [142]

Cyphellaceae

Cyphella albissima Pat. & Doass. [209], *C. eumorpha* P. Karst. [209]

Radulomyces confluens (Fr. : Fr.) M.P. Christ. [211]

Fomitopsidaceae

Anomoporia bombycina (Fr. : Fr.) Pouzar [208]

Buglossoporus pulvinus (Pers.) Donk [176]

Daedalea berkeleyi Sacc. [259], *D. quercina* L. : Fr. [171, 173, 176, 217, 221, 228, 229, 236, 255, 256, 259, 269]

Fomitopsis cytisina (Berk.) Bondartsev & Singer [170, 253], *F. pinicola* (Sw. : Fr.) P. Karst. [003, 025, 048, 054, 064, 112, 113, 157, 171, 173, 176, 208, 238, 241, 243, 246, 256, 259], *F. rosea* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) P. Karst. [024, 025, 208, 259]

Piptoporus betulinus (Bull. : Fr.) P. Karst. [025]

Postia caesia (Schrad.) P. Karst. [208, 258], *P. floriformis* (Quél.) Jülich [214], *P. placenta* (Fr.) M.J. Larsen & Lombard [066, 202], *P. stiptica* (Pers. : Fr.) Jülich [036, 037, 066, 170, 203, 219, 236], *P. tephroleuca* (Fr. : Fr.) Jülich [066, 229]

Ganodermataceae

Ganoderma adpersum (Schulzer) Donk [024, 025, 028, 029, 091, 092, 157, 170, 176, 204, 206, 207,

- 253], *G. applanatum* (Pers.) Pat. [001, 003, 011, 024, 025, 028, 029, 031, 041, 042, 046, 055, 059, 062, 066, 101, 102, 112, 113, 127, 128, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 173, 176, 203, 204, 206, 207, 214, 216, 217, 218, 238, 241, 243, 246, 255, 256, 261, 263, 265], *G. carnosum* Pat. [053, 203, 260], *G. lucidum* (Curtis : Fr.) P. Karst. [001, 003, 009, 024, 025, 028, 031, 033, 039, 042, 054, 055, 064, 087, 110, 112, 113, 127, 128, 132, 166, 173, 176, 203, 204, 206, 207, 208, 214, 216, 217, 220, 221, 238, 241, 243, 246, 251, 253, 255, 256], *G. pfeifferi* Bres. [256], *G. resinaceum* Boud. [046, 112, 113, 217, 246, 253, 255, 268a]
- Gloeophyllaceae
Gloeophyllum abietinum (Bull. : Fr.) P. Karst. [001, 003, 066, 173, 176, 199, 208, 258], *G. carbonarium* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Ryvarden [259], *G. odoratum* (Wulfen : Fr.) Imazeki [203], *G. sepiarium* (Wulfen : Fr.) P. Karst. [001, 003, 028, 031, 066, 068, 171, 173, 189, 199, 208, 216, 217, 256, 259], *G. trabeum* (Pers. : Fr.) Murrill [028, 066, 197, 199, 203, 208, 256, 259]
- Hapalopilaceae
Aurantiporus fissilis (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) H. Jahn [006]
Bjerkandera adusta (Willd. : Fr.) P. Karst. [001, 003, 006, 033, 066, 097, 112, 113, 131, 134, 157, 163, 163a, 189, 203, 214, 216, 217, 238, 241, 243, 246, 252a, 253, 256, 259, 261, 263, 285], *B. fumosa* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst. [097]
Ceriporia reticulata (Hoffm.) Domański [208]
Hapalopilus nidulans (Fr. : Fr.) P. Karst. [023, 025, 219]
Ichnoderma benzoinum (Wahlenb. : Fr.) P. Karst. [112, 246], *I. resinatum* (Schr. : Fr.) P. Karst. [208], *I. trogii* (Fr.) Teixeira [268a]
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Spongipellis delectans (Peck) Murrill [028, 256], *S. spumeus* (Sowerby : Fr.) Pat. [214]
- Hyphodermataceae
Hyphoderma capitatum J. Erikss. & Å. Strid [259], *H. occidentale* (D.P. Rogers) Boidin & Gilles [259], *H. praetermissum* (P. Karst.) J. Erikss. & Å. Strid [203], *H. puberum* (Fr. : Fr.) Wallr. [259], *H. setigerum* (Fr. : Fr.) Donk [259]
Hypochnicium bombycinum (Sommerf. : Fr.) J. Erikss. [259], *H. lundellii* (Bourdot) J. Erikss. [259], *H. punctulatum* (Cooke) J. Erikss. [259]
- Meripilaceae
Abortiporus biennis (Bull. : Fr.) Singer [055, 132, 258]
Antrodia albida (Fr. : Fr.) Donk [142, 206, 207, 256, 258, 259], *A. gossypium* (Speg.) Ryvarden [208], *A. heteromorpha* (Fr. : Fr.) Donk [259], *A. juniperina* (Murrill) Niemelä & Ryvarden [217], *A. malicola* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Donk [256, 259], *A. serialis* (Fr. : Fr.) Donk [173, 217, 256, 259], *A. variiformis* (Peck) Donk [256], *A. xantha* (Fr. : Fr.) Ryvarden [024, 025]
- Grifola frondosa* (Dicks. : Fr.) Gray [004, 010, 011, 017, 025, 112, 136, 145, 146, 147, 148, 151, 154, 195, 246, 260, 261, 263]
- Hydnopolyporus fimbriatus* (Fr. : Fr.) D.A. Reid [259]
- Meripilus giganteus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst. [002, 017, 111, 112, 151, 159, 160, 163, 176, 180, 197, 221, 236, 246, 256, 285]
- Physisporinus vitreus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst. [066, 202, 259]
- Rigidoporus sanguinolentus* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Donk [259], *R. ulmarius* (Sowerby : Fr.) Imazeki [170, 173, 176, 204, 206, 207, 214, 217]
- Meruliaceae
Byssomerulius corium (Pers. : Fr.) Parmasto [142]
Chondrostereum purpureum (Pers. : Fr.) Pouzar [001, 003, 006, 031, 066, 171, 173, 209, 214, 216, 217, 229, 254, 256, 259]
Cylindrobasidium laeve (Pers. : Fr.) Chamuris [211, 259]
Dacryobolus sudans (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Fr. [209]
Gloeoporus dichrous (Fr. : Fr.) Bres. [145, 146, 148], *G. pannocinctus* (Romell) J. Erikss. [209]
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Merulius tremellosus Schr. : Fr. [204, 206, 207, 214, 217, 256]
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Phlebia cornea (Bourdot & Galzin) J. Erikss. [259], *Ph. cremeo-ochracea* (Bourdot & Galzin) J. Erikss. [259], *Ph. deflectens* (P. Karst.) Ryvarden [259], *Ph. radiata* Fr. : Fr. [258], *Ph. segregata* (Bourdot & Galzin) Parmasto [211]
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Scopuloides hydroides (Cooke & Masee) Hjortstam & Ryvarden [211]
- Phanerochaetaceae
Gyrophanopsis polonensis (Bres.) Stalpers & P.K. Buchanan [259]
Hyphodermella corrugata (Fr.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden [142, 258]
Phanerochaete calotricha (P. Karst.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden [259], *Ph. galactites* (Bourdot & Galzin) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden [142], *Ph. sordida* (P. Karst.) J. Erikss. & Ryvarden [203, 258], *Ph. tuberculata* (P. Karst.) Parmasto [259]
- Polyporaceae
Cerrena unicolor (Bull. : Fr.) Murrill [066, 163, 173, 199, 214, 217, 228, 236, 259, 265, 269, 285]
Coriolopsis gallica (Fr. : Fr.) Ryvarden [098, 173, 189, 203, 208, 217, 256, 259], *C. trogii* (Berk.) Domański [163a, 217, 252a, 256, 268a, 275]
Daedaleopsis confragosa (Bolton : Fr.) J. Schröt. [176,

- 204, 206, 207, 253, 256, 259]
Datronia mollis (Sommerf. : Fr.) Donk. [229], *D. scutellata* (Schwein.) Gilb. & Ryvarden [189], *D. stereoides* (Fr. : Fr.) Ryvarden [259]
Faerberia carbonaria (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Pouzar [002, 180]
Fibroporia vaillantii (DC. : Fr.) Parmasto [208, 219]
Fomes fomentarius (L. : Fr.) J.J. Kickx [001, 003, 006, 009, 010, 011, 015, 016, 017, 024, 025, 026, 027, 028, 029, 033, 036, 037, 042, 047, 059, 062, 064, 066, 090, 091, 092, 094, 098, 101, 102, 103, 110, 111, 112, 113, 126, 127, 128, 129, 132, 135, 145, 146, 148, 151, 154, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 171, 173, 176, 192, 195, 203, 206, 207, 217, 218, 229, 239, 241, 243, 246, 248, 251, 253, 255, 256, 259, 260, 261, 263, 265, 266, 268, 268a, 275, 277], *F. juniperinus* (H. Schrenk) Sacc. & Syd. [217], *F. tenuis* P. Karst. [259]
Incrustoporia nivea (Jungh.) Ryvarden [176, 258, 287]
Laetiporus sulphureus (Bull. : Fr.) Murrill [001, 002, 003, 004, 005, 009, 010, 011, 015, 017, 028, 029, 032, 062, 090, 093, 098, 099, 103, 110, 112, 127, 128, 129, 132, 136, 145, 146, 154, 159, 160, 168, 171, 172, 173, 174, 192, 205, 206, 207, 214, 215, 217, 218, 221, 228, 232, 236, 238, 239, 241, 243, 246, 248, 251, 253, 257, 260, 279, 281, 284]
Laricifomes officinalis (Vill. : Fr.) Kotl. & Pouzar [066, 143, 217]
Leontinus adhaerens (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Fr. [210], *L. carneotomentosus* (Batsch) J. Schröt. [173], *L. cyathiformis* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Bres. [047, 054, 059, 064, 163], *L. tigrinus* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [007, 009, 011, 026, 027, 028, 029, 047, 050, 056, 058, 059, 062, 064, 066, 112, 113, 127, 128, 129, 132, 134, 135, 136, 151, 153, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 170, 171, 189, 203, 204, 205, 206, 207, 210, 244, 246, 251, 252a, 253, 261, 263]
Lenzites abietinella (Murrill) Sacc. & Trotter [259], *L. betulina* (L. : Fr.) Fr. [001, 003, 006, 023, 025, 031, 042, 046, 064, 091, 092, 112, 113, 176, 203, 204, 206, 207, 214, 216, 217, 229, 238, 241, 243, 246, 254, 256, 269], *L. warnieri* Durieu & Mont. [033, 176, 253]
Neolentinus lepideus (Fr. : Fr.) Redhead & Ginns [002, 045, 054, 066, 157, 180, 199, 210, 256, 259], *N. schaefferi* (Weinm.) Redhead & Ginns [270]
Oligoporus sericeomollis (Romell) Bondartseva [258]
Pachykytospora tuberculosa (DC. : Fr.) Kotl. & Pouzar [066, 202, 214]
Panus conchatus (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [011, 023, 025, 047, 050, 098, 206, 207, 217], *P. lecomtei* (Fr. : Fr.) Corner [002, 004, 006, 180, 217, 256], *P. violaceofulvus* (Batsch) Quél. [210]
Perenniporia fraxinea (Bull. : Fr.) Ryvarden [203], *P. medulla-panis* (Jacq. : Fr.) Donk [025, 066, 202, 231, 259], *P. ochroleuca* (Berk.) Ryvarden [217]
Phaeolus schweinitzii (Fr. : Fr.) Pat. [001, 003, 031, 173, 176, 209, 217, 256, 285]
Podofomes trogii (Fr.) Pouzar [176]
Polyporus alveolaris (DC. : Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer [090, 110], *P. anisoporus* Mont. [176], *P. arcularius* (Batsch : Fr.) Fr. [025, 033, 042, 055, 110, 112, 113, 135, 163a, 203, 214, 219, 238, 241, 243, 246, 251, 253, 285], *P. badius* (Pers.) Schwein. [055, 062], *P. brumalis* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 028, 029, 033, 046, 064, 112, 113, 127, 128, 132, 157, 192, 203, 246, 253, 261, 263, 265, 268a, 278, 280], *P. ciliatus* Fr. : Fr. [024, 025], *P. confluens* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Fr. [004], *P. fulvus* (Schaeff. ex Scop.) Fr. [001, 003, 217], *P. leptoccephalus* (Jacq. : Fr.) Fr. [033, 206, 207, 209, 253], *P. meridionalis* (A. David) H. Jahn [064, 163], *P. rhizophilus* (Pat.) Sacc. [047, 050, 159, 160, 163a], *P. squamosus* (Huds. : Fr.) Fr. [001, 002, 003, 004, 005, 009, 010, 011, 015, 017, 023, 025, 028, 029, 031, 032, 033, 047, 050, 058, 062, 064, 088, 093, 097, 110, 112, 126, 131, 136, 145, 146, 154, 155, 157, 159, 160, 163, 163a, 166, 168, 171, 180, 182, 183, 188, 191, 195, 198, 204, 205, 206, 207, 217, 218, 220, 221, 232, 236, 238, 241, 243, 246, 253, 257, 260, 261, 263, 265, 266, 268, 268a], *P. tuberaster* (Jacq. : Fr.) Fr. [087, 258], *P. umbellatus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [004, 041, 229], *P. varius* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [017, 024, 025, 217, 253, 256, 268a], *P. versatilis* Berk. [217]
Poria calcea (Fr. : Fr.) Bres. [208]
Pycnoporus cinnabarinus (Jacq. : Fr.) Fr. [024, 025, 103, 268a]
Pyrofomes demidoffii (Lév.) Kotl. & Pouzar [066, 134, 199]
Skeletocutis amorpha (Fr. : Fr.) Kotl. & Pouzar [208], *S. carneogrisea* A. David [142]
Trametes cubensis (Mont.) Sacc. [259], *T. gibbosa* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [001, 003, 006, 009, 023, 025, 026, 027, 066, 157, 171, 173, 176, 206, 207, 214, 217, 220, 236, 238, 241, 243, 254, 256, 275], *T. hirsuta* (Wulfen : Fr.) Pilát [001, 003, 018, 023, 025, 026, 027, 031, 173, 176, 203, 204, 206, 207, 214, 216, 217, 218, 228, 253, 254, 259, 275], *T. ochracea* (Pers.) Gilb. & Ryvarden [026, 066, 090, 110, 113, 203, 241, 243], *T. pubescens* (Schumacher : Fr.) Pilát [024, 025, 046, 055, 064, 113, 126, 203, 208, 241, 243, 259, 268], *T. robiniophila* Murrill [258], *T. suaveolens* (L. : Fr.) Fr. [047, 066, 173, 199, 203, 217, 259], *T. versicolor* (L. : Fr.) Lloyd [001, 003, 006, 016, 024, 025, 028, 029, 031, 033, 036, 037, 039, 055, 062, 064, 065, 066, 090, 094, 101, 102, 103, 110, 111, 112, 113, 126, 127, 128, 129, 132, 134, 135, 145, 146, 148, 163, 163a, 168, 170, 171, 172, 173, 176, 189, 203, 206, 207, 214, 216, 217, 218, 220, 229, 231, 239, 241, 243, 246, 248, 251, 253, 254, 256, 259, 261, 263, 265, 275,

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- Trichaptum abietinum* (Dicks. : Fr.) Ryvarden [006, 026, 066, 112, 135, 151, 153, 157, 173, 197, 203, 208, 217, 246, 252a, 256, 259], *T. fuscoviolaceum* (Ehrenb. : Fr.) Ryvarden [066, 203], *T. pergamenum* (Fr.) G. Cunn. [as "*pargamenum*"] [006, 098, 102, 173, 176, 214, 217, 256, 259, 261, 263]
Tyromyces chioneus (Fr. : Fr.) P. Karst. [189, 259], *T. wynnei* (Berk. & Broome) Donk [060, 267]
Ungulina corrugis (Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin [208]

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- Sparassis crispa* (Wulfen : Fr.) Fr. [004, 025, 030, 111, 112, 135, 136, 185, 239, 248, 252a, 256, 257, 259], *S. laminosa* Fr. [004]

Steccherinaceae

- Antrodiella semisupina* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Ryvarden [259]
Odontia nemecii Pilát [209]
Steccherinum fimbriatum (Pers. : Fr.) J. Erikss. [259], *S. ochraceum* (Pers. : Fr.) Gray [024, 025, 256], *S. septentrionale* (Fr. : Fr.) Banker [256]

Sistotremataceae

- Sistotrema brinkmannii* (Bres.) J. Erikss. [209], *Sistotrema* sp. [142]
Trechispora farinacea (Pers. : Fr.) Liberta [211, 258] *T. mollusca* (Pers. : Fr.) Liberta [208]

Tubulicrinaceae

- Tubulicrinis calothrix* (Pat.) Donk [142], *T. gracillimus* (Ellis & Everh. ex D.P. Rogers & H.S. Jacks.) G. Cunn. [211], *T. incrassatus* Hallenb. [142], *T. thermometrus* (G. Cunn.) M.P. Christ. [259]

Russulales

Auriscalpiaceae

- Auriscalpium vulgare* Gray [025, 112, 130, 246]
Clavicornia pyxidata (Pers. : Fr.) Donk [209]
Lentinellus castoreus (Fr.) Kühner & Maire [210], *L. cochleatus* Hoffm. : Fr. [004, 053, 217], *L. omphalodes* (Fr.) P. Karst. [091, 096], *L. tridentinus* (Sacc. & Syd.) Singer [270], *L. vulpinus* (Sowerby : Fr.) Kühner & Maire [180]

Bondarzewiaceae

- Bondarzewia montana* (Quél.) Singer [256]
Heterobasidium annosum (Fr. : Fr.) Bref. [001, 055, 127, 128, 208]

Cystostereaceae

- Cystostereum murrayi* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Pouzar [209]

Hericiaceae

- Dentipellis fragilis* (Pers. : Fr.) Donk [004, 259]
Hericium cirrhatum (Pers. : Fr.) Nikol. [004, 023, 025, 066], *H. coralloides* (Scop. : Fr.) Pers. [002, 004, 102, 180, 185, 217, 256, 257, 278, 280], *H. erinaceus* (Bull. : Fr.) Pers. [004, 024, 025, 217]

Lachnocladiaceae

- Asterostroma medium* Bres. [259]

- Dichostereum granulosum* (Pers. : Fr.) Boidin & Lanq. [209, 211]

- Scytinostroma odoratum* (Fr. : Fr.) Donk [259]

- Vararia ochroleuca* (Bourdot & Galzin) Donk [258]

Peniophoraceae

- Peniophora aurantiaca* (Bres.) Bourdot & Galzin [229], *P. cinerea* (Pers. : Fr.) Cooke [142], *P. heterogenea* Bourdot & Galzin [211], *P. limitata* (Chaillat) Cooke [142], *P. lycii* (Pers.) Höhn. & Litsch. [142, 258], *P. malenconii* Boidin & Lanq. [170], *P. meridionalis* Boidin [142], *P. piceae* (Pers.) J. Erikss. [211, 259], *P. polygonia* (Pers. : Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin [211], *P. quercina* (Pers. : Fr.) Cooke [142, 214, 217, 219], *P. rufomarginata* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin [258], *P. subcremea* Höhn. & Litsch. [211]

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- Lactarius acerrimus* Britzelm. [025, 066, 131, 140, 220, 230, 236, 261, 263], *L. acris* (Bolton : Fr.) Gray [039, 230, 270], *L. affinis* Peck [140, 220, 230], *L. aurantiacus* (Pers. : Fr.) Gray [039, 042, 055, 113, 140, 210, 230, 238, 241, 242, 243], *L. azonites* (Bull.) Fr. [025, 140, 206, 207, 236], *L. blennius* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [002, 046, 087, 140, 180, 181, 184, 192, 230, 270], *L. camphoratus* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [018, 025, 140, 221], *L. chrysorrhoeus* Fr. [025, 091, 092, 112, 140, 251, 285], *L. circellatus* Fr. [018, 025, 087, 140, 204, 206, 207], *L. controversus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [018, 021, 025, 060, 097, 140, 205, 206, 207, 268a], *L. decipiens* Quél. [024, 025, 140], *L. deliciosus* (L. : Fr.) Gray [002, 005, 018, 021, 023, 025, 032, 033, 035, 036, 037, 038, 040, 042, 046, 054, 055, 057, 064, 066, 091, 092, 093, 106, 111, 112, 118, 119, 121, 123, 127, 128, 132, 134, 135, 136, 140, 157, 168, 169, 171, 182, 183, 184, 185, 187, 189, 191, 205, 206, 207, 215, 220, 221, 222, 228, 230, 232, 236, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 251, 253, 257, 261, 263, 265, 268, 278, 279, 280, 284], *L. deterrimus* Gröger [025, 035, 041, 046, 054, 055, 064, 091, 092, 094, 112, 113, 132, 135, 136, 140, 168, 169, 203, 230, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 244, 248, 251, 252a, 266, 268], *L. evosmus* Kühner & Romagn. [018, 025], *L. flavidus* Boud. [140, 221, 226], *L. fluens* Boud. [140, 206, 207], *L. fuliginosus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [140, 205, 206, 207], *L. fulvissimus* Romagn. [018, 025, 140, 206, 207], *L. glyciosmus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [023, 025, 140], *L. helvus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [022, 025, 140, 149, 174], *L. hepaticus* Plov. [018, 025, 230, 270], *L. hysginus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 039], *L. insulsus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [220, 230], *L. intermedius* [Krombh. ex] Berk. & Broome [025, 140, 230, 241, 242, 243], *L. luteolus* Peck [140, 220, 230], *L. mairei* Malençon [091, 092, 140], *L. mammosus* Fr. [055], *L. pallidus* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [140, 205, 206, 207, 230, 270], *L. piperatus* (L. : Fr.) Pers. [002, 005, 021, 024, 033, 046, 054,

- 055, 056, 064, 112, 113, 135, 136, 140, 174, 175, 182, 183, 184, 187, 220, 221, 230, 232, 236, 241, 242, 243, 252a, 253], *L. porninsis* Rolland [137, 140], *L. pubescens* (Fr.) Fr. [055, 140, 189, 230], *L. pyrogalus* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [018, 025, 140, 205, 206, 207], *L. quieticolor* Romagn. [132, 140], *L. quietus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [038, 042, 087, 118, 119, 140, 212], *L. resimus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [024, 025, 140], *L. rufus* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 140, 171, 220, 230, 236, 269], *L. ruginosus* Romagn. [230, 270], *L. salmonicolor* R. Heim & Leclair [002, 021, 025, 030, 054, 089, 098, 111, 112, 136, 140, 144, 180, 181, 182, 183, 184, 185, 187, 192, 203, 230, 239, 243, 248, 257, 278, 280], *L. sanguifluus* (Paulet) Fr. s. lat. [009, 091, 092, 097, 098, 112, 113, 132, 135, 136, 138, 140, 230, 279, 283], *L. sanguifluus* (Paulet) Fr. var. *violaceus* (Barla) Basso [140, 205, 206, 207, 245], *L. scrobiculatus* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. s. lat. [046, 064, 087, 118, 140, 210, 221, 230, 236, 270], *L. scrobiculatus* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. var. *canadensis* (A.H. Sm.) Hesler & A.H. Sm. [220, 230], *L. semisanguifluus* R. Heim & Leclair [112, 132, 136, 138, 140, 205, 206, 207, 279, 283], *L. subdulcis* (Bull. : Fr.) Gray [025, 230, 270], *L. torminosus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Gray [005], *L. uvidus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [018, 025, 041, 140, 149, 230], *L. vellereus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. var. *vellereus* [025, 038, 055, 064, 111, 112, 118, 119, 140, 180, 206, 207, 212, 230, 239, 248, 270], *L. vellereus* var. *bertillonii* (Z. Schaeff.) Bon [220, 230], *L. vietus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [024, 025, 140], *L. volemus* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [002, 021, 023, 024, 025, 052, 140, 182, 183, 187, 220, 221, 230, 232, 236, 257, 270], *L. zonarioides* Kühner & Romagn. [230, 270], *L. zonarius* (Bull.) Fr. [046, 140, 206, 207, 220, 230]
- Russula aeruginea* Fr. [024, 025, 038, 118, 119, 212, 220, 230], *R. acrifolia* Romagn. [230, 270], *R. adulterina* Fr. [024, 025, 230, 270], *R. albonigra* (Krombh.) Fr. [024, 025, 054, 055, 060, 064, 191, 220, 230], *R. alutacea* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [042], *R. amethystina* Quéf. [023, 025], *R. amoena* Quéf. [024, 025], *R. anatina* Romagn. [180, 230], *R. anthracina* Romagn. [024, 025], *R. aquosa* Leclair [025, 210, 230], *R. atropurpurea* (Krombh.) Britzelm. [024, 060, 112, 132, 136, 189, 191, 230, 285], *R. atrorubens* Quéf. [042], *R. aurantiaca* (Schaeff.) Romagn. [042], *R. aurea* Pers. [005, 009, 025, 030, 033, 042, 099, 102, 103, 113, 192, 220, 221, 230, 238, 241, 242, 243, 244, 253], *R. aurora* (Krombh.) Bres. [039, 269], *R. betularum* Hora [022, 024, 046, 056, 060, 064, 097, 175, 230, 267, 268], *R. borealis* Kauffman [025], *R. brevipes* Peck [219, 230], *R. brunneoviolacea* Crawshay [024, 025], *R. cavipes* Britzelm. [025], *R. cessans* A. Pearson [018, 024, 025], *R. chloroides* (Krombh.) Bres. [002, 066, 088, 132, 180, 185, 230], *R. claroflava* Grove [025, 118], *R. curtipes* F.H. Møller & Jul. Schäff. [038, 118, 119, 212], *R. cyanoxantha* (Schaeff.) Fr. [009, 011, 015, 017, 024, 025, 046, 064, 127, 128, 132, 221, 230, 236, 268], *R. delica* Fr. s. lat. [002, 007, 009, 010, 011, 015, 017, 021, 025, 032, 035, 036, 037, 040, 042, 044, 046, 054, 055, 056, 057, 060, 064, 091, 092, 093, 097, 099, 102, 103, 111, 112, 113, 118, 123, 127, 128, 132, 134, 135, 136, 155, 157, 168, 169, 175, 182, 183, 187, 191, 203, 204, 205, 206, 207, 219, 220, 222, 230, 236, 238, 239, 241, 242, 243, 248, 257, 267, 268, 278, 280, 284], *R. delica* Fr. var. *trachyspora* Romagn. [270], *R. densifolia* Gillet [097, 132], *R. emetica* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Pers. [041, 066, 171, 174, 203, 230], *R. farinipes* Romell [024, 025], *R. fellea* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 039, 064, 132, 230, 268, 270], *R. foetens* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 039, 046, 054, 055, 064, 112, 113, 132, 180, 220, 221, 230, 236, 252a, 269, 284], *R. fragilis* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [024, 025, 040], [*R. furcata* (Pers.) Fr., *nom. dubium*, according to various authors identical with *R. grisea*, *R. heterophylla* or *R. cyanoxantha*] [102, 103, 230], *R. gracilis* Burl. [025], *R. grata* Britzelm. [024, 025, 054, 220, 230], *R. grisea* (Pers.) Fr. [024, 025, 046, 157, 230], *R. heterophylla* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 039], *R. integra* (L.) Fr. [025, 042, 055], *R. ionochlora* Romagn. [024], *R. livescens* (Batsch) Bataille [024, 025], *R. lutea* (Huds. : Fr.) Fr. [025, 191], *R. luteotacta* Rea [025, 042, 055, 060, 065, 220, 221, 230, 270], *R. maculata* Quéf. & Roze [025, 180, 230, 270], *R. melliolens* Quéf. [039], *R. minutula* Velen. [018, 025], *R. nigricans* (Bull.) Fr. [023, 024, 025, 046, 132, 230], *R. aff. nitida* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [230, 270], *R. nobilis* Velen. [018, 024, 025, 040, 087, 203, 230, 270], *R. ochroleuca* (Pers.) Fr. [015, 023, 025, 026, 027, 030, 039, 056, 066, 132, 134, 175, 199, 203, 230], *R. olivacea* (Schaeff.) Fr. [033, 113, 144, 174, 230, 241, 242, 243, 253], *R. olivascens* (Pers.) Bres. [024, 025], *R. pallidospora* J. Blum ex Romagn. [066, 153, 230], *R. paludosa* Britzelm. [025, 041, 230], *R. parazurea* Jul. Schäff. [024, 025, 220, 221, 230], *R. pectinatoides* Peck [025, 042], *R. persicina* Krombh. [024, 025, 039, 054], *R. pseudodelica* J.E. Lange [009, 219, 230], *R. pseudointegra* Arnaud & Goris [245], *R. puellaris* Fr. [025, 230, 270], *R. pulchella* I.G. Borshch. [024, 025], *R. rhodopoda* Zvára [219, 230, 278], *R. romellii* Maire [042], *R. rosea* Pers. [038, 040, 097, 118, 119, 212, 219, 230], *R. rubroalba* (Singer) Romagn. [275], *R. sanguinaria* (Maire) Bon [025], *R. sanguinea* (Bull.) Fr. [024, 025, 027, 054, 134, 203, 230, 261, 263, 265], *R. seperina* Dupain [091, 096], *R. silvestris* (Singer) Reumaux [022, 023], *R. solaris* Ferd. & Winge [025], *R. subfoetens* Wm.G. Sm. [024, 025, 230, 270], *R. torulosa* Bres. [018, 024, 025, 042, 112],

[*R. transiens* (Singer) Romagn. – unclear status] [180, 230], *R. turci* Bres. [064, 091, 092], *R. velenovskyi* Melzer & Zvára [041, 230], *R. vesca* Fr. [009, 011, 015, 017, 025, 066, 203], *R. vinosa* Lindblad [024, 025, 132, 134, 137, 230, 279], *R. violacea* Quél. [038, 118, 119], *R. violeipes* Quél. [011, 017], *R. virescens* (Schaeff.) Fr. [060, 113, 219, 230, 236, 241, 243], *R. xerampelina* (Schaeff.) Fr. [023, 025, 046, 132, 134, 180, 230, 231, 270], *R. zonatula* Ebbesen & Jul. Schäff. [230, 270], *R. zvarae* Velen. [018, 023, 025]

Stereaceae

Aleurodiscus cerussatus (Bres.) Höhn. & Litsch. [142]

Amylostereum chailletii (Pers. : Fr.) Boidin [209]

Conferticium ochraceum (Fr. : Fr.) Hallenb. [211]

Gloeocystidiellum lactescens (Berk.) Boidin [259], *G. leucoxanthum* (Bres.) Boidin [259], *G. luridum* (Bres.) Boidin [259], *G. porosum* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Donk [259]

Laxitextum bicolor (Pers. : Fr.) Lentz [259]

Stereum gausapatum (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. [001, 003, 142, 173, 176, 203, 204, 206, 207, 214, 217, 254, 259], *S. hirsutum* (Willd. : Fr.) Gray [001, 003, 006, 017, 025, 028, 029, 031, 036, 037, 039, 042, 062, 066, 091, 092, 094, 097, 102, 111, 112, 127, 128, 131, 134, 142, 168, 170, 171, 173, 176, 203, 204, 206, 207, 214, 216, 217, 218, 228, 229, 239, 244, 246, 248, 251, 253, 254, 256, 259, 279], *S. insignitum* Quél. [028, 033, 113, 176, 238, 241, 243, 253], *S. ochraceoflavum* (Schwein.) Fr. [024, 025, 203, 259], *S. ostrea* Nees [239, 248], *S. rugosum* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [028, 203, 259], *S. sanguinolentum* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Fr. [001, 003, 024, 025, 066, 142, 171, 173, 209, 259], *S. subtomentosum* Pouzar [259]

Vesiculomyces citrinus (Pers.) E. Hagstr. [142, 211]

Xylobolus frustulatus (Pers. : Fr.) Boidin [001, 006, 031, 173, 214, 216, 217, 254, 256]

Thelephorales

Bankeraceae

Bankera violascens (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Pouzar [132]

Boletopsis leucomelaena (Pers.) Fayod [066, 098, 157, 197, 199, 203, 285]

Hydnellum auratile (Britzelm.) Maas Geest. [025, 229], *H. caeruleum* (Hornem. : Fr.) P. Karst. [229], *H. conrescens* (Pers.) Banker [041, 203, 236], *H. ferrugineum* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Karst. [055, 285], *H. peckii* Banker [048, 054, 055, 220, 221, 222, 236], *H. scrobiculatum* (Fr.) P. Karst. [025]

Phellodon confluens (Pers.) Pouzar [229], *Ph. niger* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Karst. [091, 092, 203, 270], *Ph. tomentosus* (L. : Fr.) Banker [025, 041, 189, 203]

Sarcodon glaucopus Maas Geest. & Nannf. [025, 055,

066, 157], *S. imbricatus* (L. : Fr.) P. Karst. [004, 009, 015, 066, 112, 136, 180, 199, 220, 221, 222, 232, 236], *S. leucopus* (Pers.) Maas Geest. & Nannf. [004, 025], *S. scabrosus* (Fr.) P. Karst. [064, 132, 134, 285], *S. squamosus* (Schaeff.) Quél. [002, 004]

Thelephoraceae

Pseudotomentella mucidula (P. Karst.) Svrček [209], *P. tristis* (P. Karst.) M.J. Larsen [209]

Thelephora anthocephala (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [064, 268], *T. caryophyllea* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Pers. [066, 202], *T. palmata* (Scop. : Fr.) Fr. [206, 207, 229, 236], *T. penicillata* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. [023, 025, 206, 207], *T. terrestris* Ehrh. : Fr. [025, 060, 112, 135, 246, 252a, 267]

Tomentella asperula (P. Karst.) Höhn. & Litsch. [209], *T. atroviolacea* Litsch. [209], *T. cinerascens* (P. Karst.) Höhn. & Litsch. [209], *T. ferruginea* (Pers. : Fr.) Pat. [209], *T. fibrosa* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Kõljalg [209], *T. flaccida* Bourdot & Galzin [209], *T. fuliginea* (Burt) Bourdot & Galzin [209], *T. lapida* (Pers.) Stalpers [209], *T. ochraceo-olivacea* Litsch. [209], *T. pilatii* Litsch. [209], *T. porulosa* (Bourdot & Galzin) M.P. Christ. [209], *T. ruttneri* Litsch. [209], *T. subclavigera* Litsch. [209], *T. subfusca* (Pers.) Höhn & Litsch. [209]

Tremellales

Exidiaceae

Eichleriella deglubens (Berk. & Broome) Lloyd [258]

Exidia glandulosa (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. [004, 006, 024, 025, 112, 113, 173, 203, 204, 206, 207, 214, 229, 246, 252a, 254, 256, 269], *E. pithya* Fr. : Fr. [142, 229], *E. saccharina* Fr. : Fr. [256], *E. thuretiana* (Lév.) Fr. [259], *E. truncata* Fr. : Fr. [025, 036, 037, 142, 259]

Pseudohydnum gelatinosum (Scop. : Fr.) P. Karst. [004, 066, 112, 113, 199, 246, 256]

Sebacina epigaea (Berk. & Broome) Bourdot & Galzin [233], *S. grisea* (Pers. : Fr.) Bres. [142, 211], *S. incrustans* (Pers. : Fr.) Tul. & C. Tul. [018, 024, 025, 226, 236]

Tremellaceae

Tremella encephala Willd. [025, 259], *T. foliacea* Pers. : Fr. [226, 252a], *T. fuciformis* Berk. [004], *T. globispora* D.A. Reid. [259], *T. mesenterica* Retz. : Fr. [006, 025, 028, 112, 127, 128, 132, 135, 136, 203, 204, 206, 207, 217, 228, 229, 239, 246, 248, 251, 252a, 256, 259, 261, 263], *T. virescens* (Fr.) Rabenh. [269]

List of synonyms

ACETABULA vulgaris Fuckel = *Helvella acetabulum*

AGARICUS aestivalis (F.H. Møller) Pilát = *Agaricus altipes*;

- Agaricus aestivalis* var. *veneris* (R. Heim & G. Becker) Wasser = ? *Agaricus altipes*; *Agaricus albertii* Bon = *Agaricus urinascentis*; *Agaricus bitorquus* var. *validus* (F.H. Møller) Bon & Cappelli = *Agaricus bitorquus*; *Agaricus campester* L. = *Agaricus campestris*; *Agaricus campestris* L. : Fr. var. *squamulosus* (Rea) Pilát = *Agaricus campestris*; *Agaricus edulis* (Vittad. ex Jul. Schäff. & F.H. Møller) Hlavaček = *Agaricus bitorquus*; *Agaricus haemorrhoidarius* Schulzer = *Agaricus silvaticus*; *Agaricus leucotrichus* (F.H. Møller) F.H. Møller = *Agaricus arvensis*; *Agaricus macrosporus* (F.H. Møller & Jul. Schäff.) Pilát = *Agaricus urinascentis*; *Agaricus maleolens* F.H. Møller = *Agaricus bernardii*; *Agaricus meleagris* (Jul. Schäff.) Pilát = *Agaricus placomyces* var. *meleagris*; *Agaricus praeclaresquamosus* A.E. Freemann = *Agaricus moelleri*; *Agaricus spissicaulis* F.H. Møller = *Agaricus litoralis*; *Agaricus variegans* F.H. Møller = *Agaricus impudicus*; *Agaricus variicolor* Pers. = *Cortinarius variicolor*; *Agaricus volemus* Fr. = *Lactarius volemus*; *Agaricus xanthodermus* Genev var. *lepiotoides* Maire = *Agaricus xanthodermus*; *Agaricus xerampelinus* Schaeff. = *Russula xerampelina*
- AGROCYBE *aegerita* (V. Brig.) Singer = *Agrocybe cylindracea*
- ALEURODISCUS *polygonius* (Pers. : Fr.) Höhn. & Litsch. = *Peniophora polygonia*
- AMANITA *excelsa* (Fr.) Bertill. = *Amanita spissa*; *Amanita inaurata* Secr. ex Gillet = *Amanita ceciliae*; *Amanita junquillea* Quéf. = *Amanita gemmata*; *Amanita phalloides* Fr. : Fr. var. *verna* (Bull. : Fr.) Lanzi = *Amanita verna*; *Amanita solitaria sensu auct. mult.* = *Amanita echinocephala* or *A. strobiliformis*; *Amanita umbrinolutea* (Secr. ex Gillet) Bertill. = *Amanita battarrae*; *Amanita vaginata* var. *umbrinolutea* Secr. ex E.-J. Gilbert = *Amanita battarrae*
- AMANITOPSIS *vaginata* (Bull. : Fr.) Roze = *Amanita vaginata*
- AMAUROCHAETE *atra* (Alb. & Schwein.) Rostaf. = *Lachnobolus atrus*; *Amaurochaete fuliginosa* (Sowerby) T. Macbr. = *Lachnobolus atrus*
- ARCYRIA *guelmae* Nann.-Bremek. = *Arcyria minuta*; *Arcyria nutans* (Bull.) Grev. = *Arcyria obvelata*
- ARMILLARIA *bulbiger* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Leucocortinarius bulbiger*; *Armillaria bulbosa* (Barla) Kile & Watling = *Armillaria gallica*; *Armillaria caligata* (Viv.) Gillet = *Tricholoma caligatum*; *Armillaria focalis* (Fr.) P. Karst. = *Tricholoma focale*; *Armillaria haematites sensu auct.* = *Cystoderma superbum*; *Armillaria mucida* (Schrad. : Fr.) Fr. = *Oudemansiella mucida*; *Armillaria obscura sensu auct.* = *Armillaria ostoyae*; *Armillaria polymyces sensu auct.* = *Armillaria ostoyae*; *Armillaria robusta* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Fr. = *Tricholoma robustum*
- ARMILLARIELLA *tabescens* (Scop. : Fr.) Singer = *Armillaria tabescens*
- ASTEROSTROMELLA *granulosa* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Dichostereum granulatum*
- AURICULARIA *auricula* (Hook. f.) Underw. = *Auricularia auricula-judae*
- BARLAEINA *persoonii* (H. Crouan & P. Crouan) Sacc. & Traverso = *Marcelleina persoonii*
- BOLBITIUS *lacteus* J.E. Lange = *Conocybe albipes*
- BOLETUS *aestivalis* (Paulet) Fr. = *Boletus reticulatus*; *Boletus bovinus* L. : Fr. = *Suillus bovinus*; *Boletus carpini* (R. Schulz) A. Pearson = *Leccinum pseudoscabrum*; *Boletus elegans* Schumch. = *Suillus grevillei*; *Boletus granulatus* L. : Fr. = *Suillus granulatus*; *Boletus luteus* L. : Fr. = *Suillus luteus*; *Boletus miniatoporus sensu Nüesch & Kallenbach.* = *Boletus erythropus*; *Boletus pachypus* Fr. = *Boletus radicans*; *Boletus porphyrosporus* Fr. = *Porphyrelus porphyrosporus*; *Boletus radicans* Pers. : Fr. = *Boletus radicans* Gillet; *Boletus rufus* Schaeff. = *Leccinum aurantiacum*; *Boletus satanoides sensu auct. mult.* = *Boletus legaliae*; *Boletus splendidus* C. Martin = *Boletus legaliae*; *Boletus variegatus* Sw. : Fr. = *Suillus variegatus*; *Boletus versicolor* Rostk. = *Boletus rubellus*
- BOVISTA *gigantea* Batsch = *Langermannia gigantea*
- BULGARIA *polymorpha* Oeder ex Wettst = *Bulgaria inguinans*
- CALVATIA *caelata* (Bull.) Morgan = *Handkea utrififormis*; *Calvatia excipuliformis* (Scop. : Pers.) Perdeck = *Handkea excipuliformis*; *Calvatia gigantea* (Batsch : Pers.) Lloyd = *Langermannia gigantea*; *Calvatia saccata* (Vahl) Morgan = *Handkea excipuliformis*; *Calvatia utrififormis* (Bull. : Pers.) Jaap = *Handkea utrififormis*
- CAMAROPHYLLUS *russocoriaceus* (Berk. & T.K. Mill.) J.L. Lange = *Hygrocybe russocoriaceae*; *Camarophyllus virgineus* (Wulfen : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Hygrocybe virginea* var. *virginea*
- CANTHARELLUS *aurantiacus* (Wulfen : Fr.) Fr. = *Hygrophoropsis aurantiaca*; *Cantharellus cibarius* var. *amethysteus* (Quéf.) Cetto = *Cantharellus amethysteus*; *Cantharellus cornucopioides* (L.) Fr. = *Craterellus cornucopioides*; *Cantharellus ferruginascens* P.D. Orton = *Cantharellus cibarius* var. *ferruginascens*; *Cantharellus infundibuliformis* (Scop.) Fr. = *Cantharellus tubaeformis*; *Cantharellus lutescens* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. = *Cantharellus aurora*
- CERATOMYXA *fruticulosa* (O.F. Müll.) T. Macbr. = *Famintzinia fruticulosa*
- CHLOROCIBORIUM *aeruginosum* (Oeder) De Not. = *Chlorociboria aeruginosa*
- CLAVARIA *botrytis* Pers. : Fr. = *Ramaria botrytis*; *Clavaria condensata* Fr. = *Ramaria stricta*; *Clavaria corniculata* Schaeff. = *Clavulinopsis corniculata*; *Clavaria cristata* (Holmsk.) Pers. = *Clavulina coralloides*; *Clavaria fastigiata* L. = *Clavulinopsis corniculata*; *Clavaria flava* Tourn. ex Schaeff. : Fr. = *Ramaria flava*; *Clavaria formosa* Pers. : Fr. = *Ramaria formosa*; *Clavaria pistillaris* L. : Fr. = *Clavariadelphus pistillaris*; *Clavaria pyxidata* Pers. : Fr. = *Clavicornia pyxidata*; *Clavaria rugosa* Bull. : Fr. = *Clavulina rugosa*; *Clavaria stricta* Pers. : Fr. = *Ramaria stricta*; *Clavaria vermicularis* Scop. : Fr. = *Clavaria fragilis*
- CLAVULINA *cristata* (Holmsk. : Fr.) J. Schröt. = *Clavulina coralloides*
- CLAVULINOPSIS *argillacea* Pers. ex Fr. — ambig. record; *Clavulinopsis cineroides* (G.F. Atk.) Comer = *Clavulinopsis umbrinella*
- CLITHRIS *quercina* = *Colpoma quercinum*

- CLITOCYBE cyathiformis* (Bull.) Fr. = *Pseudoclitocybe cyathiformis*; *Clitocybe ectypa* (Fr.) Sacc. = *Armillaria ectypa*; *Clitocybe ericetorum* (Bull.) Fr. = *Lichenomphalia umbellifera*; *Clitocybe favrei* Kühner & Romagn. = *Clitocybe vibecina*; *Clitocybe flaccida* (Sowerby : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Lepista flaccida*; *Clitocybe gigantea* (Sowerby : Fr.) Quél. = *Leucopaxillus giganteus*; *Clitocybe graminicola* Bon = *Clitocybe agrestis*; *Clitocybe hydrogramma* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Clitocybe phaeophthalma*; *Clitocybe illudens* (Schwein.) Sacc. = *Omphalotus illudens*; *Clitocybe infundibuliformis* (Schaeff.) Fr. = *Clitocybe gibba*; *Clitocybe inversa* (Scop.) Fr. = *Lepista inversa*; *Clitocybe laccata* (Scop.) Quél. = *Laccaria laccata*; *Clitocybe lignatilis* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst. = *Ossicaulis lignatilis*; *Clitocybe mellea* (Vahl) Ricken = *Armillaria mellea*; *Clitocybe pelletieri* Lev. = *Phylloporus pelletieri*; *Clitocybe tabescens* (Scop. : Fr.) Bres. = *Armillaria tabescens*
- COLLYBIA acervata* (Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Gymnopus acervatus*; *Collybia butyracea* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Rhodocollybia butyracea*; *Collybia butyracea* var. *asema* (Fr. : Fr.) Quél. = *Rhodocollybia butyracea* f. *asema*; *Collybia cessans* sensu A.A. Pearson = *Gamundia striatula*; *Collybia confluens* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Gymnopus confluens*; *Collybia confusa* P.D. Orton = *Tephroclype confusa*; *Collybia distorta* (Fr.) Quél. = *Rhodocollybia proluxa* var. *distorta*; *Collybia dryophila* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Gymnopus dryophilus*; *Collybia erythropus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Gymnopus erythropus*; *Collybia exculpta* (Fr.) Gillet = *Gymnopus ocior*; *Collybia fuscopurpurea* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Gymnopus fuscopurpureus*; *Collybia fusipes* (Bull. : Fr.) Quél. = *Gymnopus fusipes*; *Collybia grammocephala* (Bull.) Quél. = *Megacollybia platyphylla*; *Collybia hariolorum* (Bull. : Fr.) Quél. = *Gymnopus hariolorum*; *Collybia longipes* (Bull.) P. Kumm. = *Xerula longipes*; *Collybia maculata* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Rhodocollybia maculata*; *Collybia marasmioides* (Britzelm.) Bresinsky & Stangl = *Gymnopus erythropus*; *Collybia nivalis* (Luthi & Plomb) M.M. Moser = *Collybia verna*; *Collybia oreaidoides* (Pass.) P.D. Orton = *Gymnopus oreaidoides*; *Collybia palustris* (Peck) A.H. Sm. = *Tephroclype palustris*; *Collybia peronata* (Bolton : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Gymnopus peronatus*; *Collybia radicata* Relh. = *Xerula radicata*; *Collybia velutipes* (Curtis : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Flammulina velutipes*
- COMATRICHA acanthodes* Alexop. = *Paradiacheopsis acanthodes*; *Comatricha dictyospora* L.F. Čelak. = *Stemonitopsis reticulata*; *Comatricha lurida* Lister = *Collaria lurida*
- CONOCYBE lactea* (J.E. Lange) Métrod = *Conocybe albipes*
- COPRINUS fimetarius* sensu auct. = *Coprinus cinereus*; *Coprinus ovatus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) Fr. = *Coprinus comatus*
- COPRINUSELLA silvatica* (Peck) Zerov = *Coprinus silvaticus*
- CORIOLELLUS albidus* (Fr. : Fr.) Bondartsev = *Antrodia albidia*
- CORIOLOUS abietinus* (Dicks.) Quél. = *Trichaptum abietinum*; *Coriolus hirsutus* (Wulfen) Pat. = *Trametes hirsuta*; *Coriolus pargamenus* (Fr.) G. Cunn. = *Trichaptum pargamenum*; *Coriolus pubescens* (Schumach. : Fr.) Quél. = *Trametes pubescens*; *Coriolus unicolor* (Bull. : Fr.) Pat. = *Cerrrena unicolor*; *Coriolus versicolor* (L. : Fr.) Quél. = *Trametes versicolor*; *Coriolus zonatus* (Nees) Quél. = *Trametes ochracea*
- CORTICIUM byssinum* (Karst.) Sacc. = *Piloderma byssinum*; *Corticium caeruleum* (Schrad.) Fr. = *Pulcherricum caeruleum*; *Corticium cebennense* Bourdot = *Amylocorticium cebennense*; *Corticium centrifugum* (Lév.) Bres. = *Athelia rolfssii*; *Corticium confluens* (Fr.) Fr. = *Radulomyces confluens*; *Corticium fuisporum* Cooke & Ellis = *Coniophora fuispora*; *Corticium laeve* Pers. = *Cylindrobasidium laeve*; *Corticium macrosporopsis* Jülich = *Dendrothele macrospora*; *Corticium subcoronatum* Höhn. & Litsch. = *Botryobasidium subcoronatum*; *Corticium submutabile* Höhn. & Litsch. = *Trechispora farinacea*
- CORTINARIUS amoenolens* Rob. Henry ex P.D. Orton = *Cortinarius anserinus*; *Cortinarius aureoturbinatus* (Secr. ex M.M. Moser) J.E. Lange = *Cortinarius elegantissimus*; *Cortinarius carviolaceus* P.D. Orton = *Cortinarius aleuriomus*; *Cortinarius cinnamomeobadius* (Rob. Henry) M.M. Moser = *Cortinarius sommerfeltii*; *Cortinarius crocolitus* Quél. = ? *Cortinarius triumphans*; *Cortinarius fasciatus* sensu J.E. Lange = *Cortinarius fulvescens*; *Cortinarius malachioides* P.D. Orton = *Cortinarius malachius*; *Cortinarius subvalidus* Rob. Henry = *Cortinarius saginus*; *Cortinarius vitellinus* M.M. Moser = *Cortinarius splendens* subsp. *meinhardii*
- CREOLOPHUS cirrhatus* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst. = *Hericium cirrhatum*
- CREPIDOTUS amygdalosporus* Kühner = *Crepidotus lundellii*; *Crepidotus pubescens* sensu Kühner & Romagnesi = *Crepidotus epibryus*; *Crepidotus sphaerosporus* (Pat.) J.E. Lange = *Crepidotus cesatii*; *Crepidotus subtilis* P.D. Orton. = *Crepidotus lundellii*
- CRUCIBULUM vulgare* Tul. & C. Tul. = *Crucibulum leave*
- CUPHOPHYLLUS subradiatus* (Schumach.) Bon = *Hygrocybe virginea* var. *virginea*; *Cuphophyllum virgineum* (Wulfen : Fr.) Kovalenko = *Hygrocybe virginea* var. *virginea*
- CYATHIPODIA villosa* (Hedw.) Boud. = *Helvella dissingii*
- CYATHUS hirsutus* (Schaeff.) Sacc. = *Cyathus striatus*; *Cyathus vernicosus* (Bull.) DC. = *Cyathus olla*
- CYLINDROBASIDIUM evolvens* (Fr. : Fr.) Jülich = *Cylindrobasidium leave*
- CYPHELLA albocarnea* Quél. = *Calathella eruciformis*; *Cyphella erucaeformis* (P. Micheli ex Batsch) Fr. = *Calathella eruciformis*
- CYSTOLEPIOTA aspera* (Pers.) Bon = *Lepiota aspera*
- DAEDALEA confragosa* (Bolton) Pers. = *Daedaleopsis confragosa*; *Daedalea juniperina* (Murrill) Murrill = *Antrodia juniperina*; *Daedalea unicolor* (Bull.) Fr. = *Cerrrena unicolor*
- DASYSCYPHUS cerinus* = *Lachnum cerinum*; *Dasyscyphus niveus* = *Lachnum niveum*
- DENDROPOLYPORUS umbellatus* (Pers.) Jülich = *Polyporus umbellatus*
- DERMOCYBE carpineti* M.M. Moser (nom. inval.) = *Cortinarius olivaceofuscus*; *Dermocybe cinnamomea* (L. : Fr.) M.M. Moser = *Cortinarius cinnamomeus*; *Dermocybe crocea*

- (Schaeff.) M.M. Moser = *Cortinarius croceus*; *Dermocybe semisanguinea* (Fr. : Fr.) M.M. Moser = *Cortinarius semisanguineus*
- DICTYDIUM* Schrad. = *Cribraria* Pers.
- DISCINA* gigas (Krombh.) Eckblad = *Gyromitra gigas*; *Discina perlata* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. = *Discina ancilis*
- ECCILIA* lanica (Romagn.) anon. = *Entoloma lanicum*; *Eccilia rhodocalyx* (Lasch : Fr.) Sacc. = *Entoloma rhodocalyx*
- ENTOLOMA* lividum (Bull.) Quél. = *Entoloma sinuatum*; *Entoloma nidorosum* (Fr.) Quél. = *Entoloma rhodopolium* var. *nidorosum*
- EXIDIOPSIS* grisea (Pers.) Bourdot & Maire = *Sebacina grisea*
- FAVOLUS* rhipidium (Berk.) Sacc. = *Panellus pusillus*
- FLAMMULA* hybrida (Bull.) Gillet = *Gymnopilus penetrans*; *Flammula liquiritiae* (Pers.) P. Kumm. = *Gymnopilus liquiritiae*; *Flammula penetrans* (Fr.) Quél. = *Gymnopilus penetrans*; *Flammula sapinea* (Fr.) Pat. = *Gymnopilus sapineus*; *Flammula spumosa* (Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Pholiota spumosa*
- FOMES* applanatus (Pers.) Wallr. = *Ganoderma applanatum*; *Fomes hartigii* (Allesch. & Schnabl) Bres. = *Phellinus hartigii*; *Fomes igniarius* (L.) Cooke = *Phellinus igniarius*; *Fomes officinalis* (Vill.) Bres. = *Laricifomes officinalis*; *Fomes pini* (Thore) P. Karst. = *Phellinus pini*; *Fomes pinicola* (Sw.) Fr. = *Fomitopsis pinicola*; *Fomes pomaceus* (Pers.) Lloyd = *Phellinus pomaceus*; *Fomes roseus* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr. = *Fomitopsis rosea*; *Fomes scutellatus* (Schwein.) Sacc. = *Datronia scutellata*; *Fomes torulosus* (Pers.) Lloyd. = *Phellinus torulosus*; *Fomes ulmarius* Fr. = *Rigidoporus ulmarius*
- FULIGO* candida Pers. = *Fuligo septica*
- FUNALIA* extenuata (Durieu & Mont.) Domański = *Corioloopsis gallica*; *Funalia trogii* (Berk.) Bondartsev & Singer = *Corioloopsis trogii*
- GALERA* antipoda (Lasch) Quél. = *Conocybe antipoda*
- GALERINA* mutabilis (Schaeff.) P. D. Orton = *Kuehneromyces mutabilis*; *Galerina unicolor* (Vahl : Fr.) Singer = *Galerina marginata*
- GAMUNDIA* pseudoclusilis (Joss. & Konrad) Raithehl. = *Gamundia striatula*
- GASTROCYBE* lateritia Watling = *Galeropsis lateritia*
- GEASTRUM* badium Pers. = *Geastrum elegans*; *Geastrum nanum* Pers. = *Geastrum schmidelii*; *Geastrum sessile* (Sowerby) Pouzar = *Geastrum fimbriatum*; *Geastrum vulgatum* Vittad. = *Geastrum rufescens*
- GEOPETALUM* carbonarium (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Pat. = *Faerberia carbonaria*
- GERRONEMA* ericetorum (Fr. : Fr.) Singer = *Lichenomphalia umbellifera*
- GLOEOCYSTIDIUM* alutaceum (Schrad.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Vesiculomyces citrinus*; *Gloeoystidium ochraceum* (Fr.) Höhn. & Litsch. = *Conferticium ochraceum*
- GLOEOPHYLLUM* striatum (Sw. : Fr.) Murrill = *Gloeophyllum trabeum*
- GOMPHIDIUM* helveticum Singer = *Chroogomphus helveticus*; *Gomphidium rutilus* (Schaeff. : Fr.) S. Lundell = *Chroogomphus rutilus*; *Gomphidium viscidum* (L. : Fr.) Fr. = *Chroogomphus rutilus*
- GRANDINIA* barba-jovis (Bull.) Jülich = *Hyphodontia barba-jovis*; *Grandinia breviseta* (P. Karst.) Jülich = *Hyphodontia breviseta*; *Grandinia brinkmanni* (Bres.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Sistotrema brinkmanni*; *Grandinia helvetica* (Pers.) Fr. = *Cristinia helvetica*; *Grandinia mutabilis* subsp. *granulosa* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Dichostereum granulatum*
- GRIFOLA* umbellata (Pers.) Pilát = *Polyporus umbellatus*
- GYMNOPILUS* hybridus (Bull. : Fr.) Maire = *Gymnopilus penetrans*; *Gymnopilus spectabilis* sensu A.H. Smith (1949) and sensu auct. = *Gymnopilus junonius*
- GYROPHANA* pinastri (Fr. : Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Leucogyrophana pinastri*
- HAPALOPILUS* rutilans (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst. = *Hapalopilus nidulans*
- HEBELOMA* sinapizans sensu J. Lange = *Hebeloma senescens*; *Hebeloma strophosum* (Fr.) Sacc. = *Hebeloma mesophaeum*
- HELVELLA* infula Schaeff. = *Gyromitra infula*
- HEMITRICHIA* calyculata (Speg.) M.L. Farr = *Hyporhamma calyculata*; *Hemitrichia clavata* (Pers.) Rostaf. = *Hyporhamma clavata*; *Hemitrichia karstenii* (Rostaf.) Lister = *Trichia contorta* var. *karstenii*
- HERICUM* ramosum (Bull.) Letell. = *Hericum coralloides*
- HETEROPORUS* biennis (Bull. : Fr.) Lázaro Ibiza = *Abortiporus biennis*
- HIRSCHIOPORUS* pergamenus (Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer [as "pargamenus"] = *Trichaptum pergamenum*
- HIRNEOLA* auricula-judae (L. : Fr.) Berk. = *Auricularia auricula-judae*
- HOHENBUEHELIA* geogenia (DC. : Fr.) Singer = *Hohenbuehelia petaloides* var. *petaloides*; *Hohenbuehelia rickenii* (Kühner) P.D. Orton = *Hohenbuehelia tremula*
- HYDNANGIUM* nudum Hazsl. = *Leucogaster nudus*
- HYDNUM* cirrhatum Pers. : Fr. = *Hericum cirrhatum*; *Hydnum coralloides* Scop. = *Hericum coralloides*; *Hydnum cyathiforme* Schaeff. = *Phellodon tomentosus*; *Hydnum diversidens* Fr. = *Hericum cirrhatum*; *Hydnum fragile* Fr. : Fr. = *Dentipellis fragilis*; *Hydnum imbricatum* L. = *Sarcodon imbricatus*; *Hydnum laevigatum* Sw. = *Sarcodon leucopus*; *Hydnum repandum* L. : Fr. var. *rufescens* (Fr.) Barla = *Hydnum rufescens*; *Hydnum squamosum* Schaeff. = *Sarcodon squamosus*
- HYGROCYPE* konradii R. Haller Aar. = *Hygrocybe persistens* var. *konradii*; *Hygrocybe langei* Kühner = *Hygrocybe persistens* var. *persistens*; *Hygrocybe nigrescens* sensu auct. = *Hygrocybe conica*; *Hygrocybe nivea* (Scop. : Fr.) P.D. Orton & Watling = *Hygrocybe virginea* var. *virginea*; *Hygrocybe psittacina* (Fr.) Fr. = *Hygrocybe psittacina* var. *psittacina*; *Hygrocybe sciophana* (Fr.) Wünsche = *Hygrocybe psittacina* var. *perplexa*; *Hygrocybe subglobispora* (P.D. Orton) M.M.

- Moser = *Hygrocybe persistens* var. *konradii*
HYGROPHORUS croceus (Bull.) P. Karst. = *Hygrocybe persistens*;
Hygrophorus leucophaeus sensu auct. = *Hygrophorus unicolor*;
Hygrophorus virgineus Wulfen = *Hygrocybe virginea* var.
virginea
HYMENOCHAETE fuliginosum (Pers.) Bres. = *Hymenochaete*
fuliginosa; *Hymenochaete mougeotii* (Fr. : Fr.) Cooke =
Hymenochaete cruenta
HYPHODERMA radula (Fr. : Fr.) Donk. = *Basidioradulum*
radula; *Hyphoderma subdefinitum* J. Erikss. & Å. Strid =
Hyphoderma occidentale
HYPHODERMOPSIS polonensis (Bres.) Jülich = *Gyrophanopsis*
polonensis
HYPHODONTIA verruculosa J. Erikss. & Hjortstam = *Hyphodontia*
rimosissima
HYPOCHNUS fusisporus J. Schröt. = *Thanatephorus fusisporus*
HYPOXYLON coccineum Bull. : Fr. = *Hypoxylon fragiforme*;
Hypoxylon nummularium Bull. : Fr. = *Biscogniauxia*
nummulara
INOCYBE boltonii R. Heim (*nom. inval.*) = ? *Inocybe curvipes*;
Inocybe fastigiata (Schaeff. : Fr.) Quél. = *Inocybe rimosa*;
Inocybe fibrosa var. *trivialis* J.E. Lange = *Inocybe duriuscula*;
Inocybe friesii R. Heim = *Inocybe nitidiuscula*; *Inocybe*
fuscidula Bres. (*nom. illeg.*, Art. 53.1) = *Inocybe bresadolana*;
Inocybe geophylla (Sow. : Fr.) Kumm. var. *violacea* (Pat.)
Sacc. = *Inocybe geophylla* var. *lilacina*; *Inocybe jurana* (Pat.)
Sacc. = *Inocybe adaequata*; *Inocybe lanuginella* (J. Schröt.)
Konrad & Maubl. = *Inocybe curvipes*; *Inocybe obscuroides*
P.D. Orton = *Inocybe cincinnata*; *Inocybe patouillardii* Bres.
= *Inocybe erubescens*; *Inocybe pudica* Kühner = *Inocybe*
whitei
ITHYPHALLUS impudicus (L.) Fr. = *Phallus impudicus*
KROMBHOLZIA pseudoscabra (Kallenb.) Šutara = *Leccinum*
pseudoscabrum
LACCARIA altaica Singer = *Laccaria pumila*; *Laccaria amethystea*
(Bull.) Murrill = *Laccaria amethystina*
LACRYMARIA lacrymabunda var. *velutina* (Pers. : Fr.) J.E. Lange
= *Lacrymaria lacrymabunda*; *Lacrymaria velutina* (Pers. :
Fr.) Konrad & Maubl. = *Lacrymaria lacrymabunda*
LACTARIUS aurantiofulvus J. Blum ex Bon = *Lactarius*
aurantiacus; *Lactarius bresadolianus* Singer (*nom. nud.*)
= *Lactarius zonarioides*; *Lactarius britannicus* D.A.
Reid = *Lactarius fulvissimus*; *Lactarius cilicioides* (Fr.)
Fr. = *Lactarius pubescens*; *Lactarius fuscus* Rolland =
Lactarius mammosus; *Lactarius ichoratus* (Batsch) Fr.
= *Lactarius volemus* but *L. ichoratus sensu auct.* = *L.*
fulvissimus; *Lactarius mitissimus* (Fr.) Fr. = *Lactarius*
aurantiacus; *Lactarius subsericatus* Kühner & Romagn.
ex Bon = *Lactarius fulvissimus*; *Lactarius vellerens* (Fr.)
Fr. = *Lactarius vellerens* var. *velereus*; *Lactarius vellerens*
var. *velutinus* (Bertill.) Bataille = *Lactarius vellerens* var.
velereus; *Lactarius vinosus* Quél = *Lactarius sanguifluus*
var. *violaceus*
LECCINUM carpini (R. Schulz) M.M. Moser ex D.A. Reid =
Leccinum pseudoscabrum; *Leccinum nigrescens* (Richon &
Roze) Singer = *Leccinum crocipodium*; *Leccinum quercinum*
(Pilát) E.E. Green & Watling = *L. quercinum* Pilát ex Pilát
& Dermek
LENTARIA delicata (Fr.) Corner = *Lentaria afflata*
LENTINUS castoreus Fr. = *Lentinellus castoreus*; *Lentinus*
cochleatus (Pers) Fr. = *Lentinellus cochleatus*; *Lentinus*
degener Kalchbr. = *Neolentinus schaefferi*; *Lentinus edodes*
(Berk.) Singer = *Lentinula edodes*; *Lentinus lepideus* (Fr. :
Fr.) Fr. = *Neolentinus lepideus*; *Lentinus squamosus* (Schaeff.)
Quél. = *Neolentinus lepideus*; *Lentinus strigosus* (Schwein.
: Fr.) Fr. = *Panus lecomtei*; *Lentinus torulosus* (Pers. : Fr.)
Lloyd = *Panus conchatus*; *Lentinus vulpinus* (Sowerby : Fr.)
Fr. = *Lentinellus vulpinus*
LENZITES abietina (Bull.) Fr. = *Gloeophyllum abietinum*; *Lenzites*
sepiaria (Wulfen : Fr.) Fr. = *Gloeophyllum sepiarium*;
Lenzites striata (Sw.) Fr. = *Gloeophyllum trabeum*; *Lenzites*
trabea (Pers.) Fr. = *Gloeophyllum trabeum*
LEPIOTA acutesquamosa = *Lepiota aspera*; *Lepiota adulterina* F.H.
Møller = *Cystolepiota adulterina*; *Lepiota alba* (Bres.) Sacc.
= *Lepiota erminea*; *Lepiota badhamii* (Berk. & Broome)
Quél = *Leucoagaricus badhamii*; *Lepiota cygnea* J.E. Lange
= *Leucocoprinus cygneus*; *Lepiota excoriata* (Schaeff. : Fr.) P.
Kumm. = *Macrolepiota excoriata*; *Lepiota holosericea* (Fr.)
Gillet = *Leucoagaricus leucothites*; *Lepiota jubilai* Joss.
= *Leucoagaricus jubilai*; *Lepiota konradii* Huijsman ex P.D.
Orton = *Macrolepiota kondradii*; *Lepiota kuehneriana*
Locq. = *Lepiota subgracilis*; *Lepiota littoralis* Menier =
Leucoagaricus littoralis; *Lepiota mastoidea* (Fr. : Fr.) P.
Kumm. = *Macrolepiota mastoidea*; *Lepiota naucina* (Fr.) P.
Kumm. = *Leucoagaricus leucothites*; *Lepiota procera* (Scop.
: Fr.) Gray = *Macrolepiota procera*; *Lepiota procera* var.
rhacodes Vitt. = *Macrolepiota rhacodes* var. *rhacodes*; *Lepiota*
seminuda (Lasch.) P. Kumm. = *Cystolepiota seminuda*
LEPISTA gilva (Pers. : Fr.) Pat. = *Lepista flaccida*; *Lepista nebularis*
(Fr.) Harmaja = *Clitocybe nebularis*
LEPTOGLOSSUM retirugum (Bull.) Ricken = *Arrhenia retiruga*
LEPTOPODIA atra (J. König) Boud. = *Helvella atra*
LEPTOPORUS adustus (Wild. : Fr.) Quél. = *Bjerkandera adusta*;
Leptoporus amorphus (Fr.) Quél. = *Skeletocutis amorphus*;
Leptoporus bourdotii Pilát = *Gloeoporus pannocinctus*;
Leptoporus caesius (Schrad.) Quél. = *Postia caesia*; *Leptoporus*
floriformis (Quél.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Postia floriformis*;
Leptoporus resupinatus Bourdot & Galzin ex Pilát = *Antrodia*
gossypium
LEUCOAGARICUS badhamii (Berk. & Broome) Singer =
Leucocoprinus badhamii; *Leucoagaricus macrorhizus* Locq.
ex E. Horak = *Leucoagaricus barsii*
LEUCOPAXILLUS cerealis sensu auct. recent. (non sensu Lasch) =
Leucopaxillus albissimus
LEUCOPORUS arcularius (Batsch) Quél. = *Polyporus arcularius*
LOWEOMYCES wynnei (Berk. & Broome) Jülich = *Tyromyces*
wynnei
LYCOPERDON caelatum Bull. = *Handkea utrififormis*; *Lycoperdon*
foetidum Bonorod. = *Lycoperdon nigrescens*; *Lycoperdon*

- furfuraceum* Schaeff. = *Bovista aestivalis*; *Lycoperdon gemmatum* Batsch = *Lycoperdon perlatum*; *Lycoperdon giganteum* Batsch = *Langermannia gigantea*; *Lycoperdon molle* Pers. : Pers. var. *atropurpureum* (Vittad.) F. Šmarda = *Lycoperdon atropurpureum*; *Lycoperdon saccatum* Vahl = *Handkea excipuliformis*
- LYOMYCES *sambuci* (Pers.) P. Karst. = *Hyphodontia sambuci*
- LYOPHYLLUM *ambustum* (Fr.) Singer = *Tephrocye ambusta*; *Lyophyllum fumatofoetens* Secr. ex Jul. Schäff. = *Lyophyllum leucophaeatum*; *Lyophyllum ulmarium* (Bull. : Fr.) Kühner = *Hypsizygos ulmaris*
- MACROLEPIOTA *gracilentia* (Krombh.) Wasser = *Macrolepiota mastoidea*; *Macrolepiota heimii* (Locq.) Bon = *Macrolepiota excoriata*; *Macrolepiota puellaris* (Fr.) M.M. Moser = *Leucoagaricus nymphaeum*; *Macrolepiota rachodes* var. *hortensis* Pilát = *Macrolepiota rachodes* var. *bohémica*
- MARASMIUS *androsaceus* (L. : Fr.) Fr. = *Setulipes androsaceus*; *Marasmius candidus* (Bolton) Fr. = *Marasmiellus candidus*; *Marasmius caryophylleus* (Schaeff.) J. Schröt. = *Marasmius oreades*; *Marasmius globularis* var. *carpathicus* (Kalchbr.) Costantin & L.M. Dufour = *Marasmius wynnei*; *Marasmius perforans* (Hoffm. : Fr.) Fr. = *Marasmiellus perforans*; *Marasmius prasiosmus* sensu auct. = *Marasmius quercus*; *Marasmius ramealis* (Bull. : Fr.) Fr. = *Marasmiellus ramealis*; *Marasmius splachnoides* (Hornem.) Fr. = *Setulipes quercophilus*
- MEGALOCYSTIDIUM *lactescens* (Berk.) Jülich = *Gloeocystidiellum lactescens*; *Megalocystidium leucoxanthum* (Bres.) Jülich = *Gloeocystidiellum leucoxanthum*; *Megalocystidium luridum* (Bres.) Jülich = *Gloeocystidiellum luridum*
- MELANOLEUCA *cinerascens* D.A. Reid = *Melanoleuca excissa* var. *excissa*; *Melanoleuca vulgaris* (Pat.) Pat. = *Melanoleuca melaleuca*
- MICROMPHALE *brassicolens* (Romagn.) P.D. Orton = *Gymnopus brassicolens*; *Micromphale foetidum* (Sowerby : Fr.) Singer = *Marasmiellus foetidus*; *Micromphale perforans* (Hoffm. : Fr.) Gray = *Marasmiellus perforans*
- MORCHELLA *conica* Pers. = *Morchella vulgaris*; *Morchella conica* var. *deliciosa* (Fr.) Cetto = *Morchella deliciosa*; *Morchella conica* var. *distans* Fr. = *Morchella distans*; *Morchella conica* var. *intermedia* Boud. = *Morchella intermedia*; *Morchella esculenta* var. *costata* Vent. = *Morchella costata*; *Morchella esculenta* var. *crassipes* (Vent. : Fr.) Kreisel = *Morchella crassipes*; *Morchella esculenta* var. *rotunda* Fr. = *Morchella esculenta*; *Morchella esculenta* var. *vulgaris* Pers. = *Morchella vulgaris*; *Morchella hortensis* Boud. = *Morchella vaporaria*; *Morchella rimosipes* DC. = *Mitrophora semilibera*; *Morchella rotunda* (Fr.) Boud. = *Morchella esculenta*; *Morchella rotunda* var. *rigida* Jet. [nom. inval., Art. 33.2]; *Morchella umbrina* f. *macroalveola* Jacquet. [nom. inval., Art. 36.1, 37.1]
- MYCENA *chlorinella* (J.E. Lange) Singer = *Mycena leptocephala*; *Mycena corticola* sensu auct. = *Mycena hiemalis*; *Mycena epipterygia* (Scop. : Fr.) Gray var. *lignicola* A.H. Sm. = *Mycena epipterygia* var. *epipterygia*; *Mycena fibula* (Bull. : Fr.) Kühner = *Rickenella fibula*; *Mycena galericulata* var. *calopus* (Fr.) P. Karst. = *Mycena inclinata*; *Mycena galopus* var. *nigra* Rea = *Mycena leucogala*; *Mycena integrella* (Pers.) Gray = *Delicatula integrella*; *Mycena viscosa* Secr. ex Maire = *Mycena epipterygia* var. *viscosa*
- NAUCORIA *abstrusa* sensu auct. = *Pholiota conissans*
- NECTRIA *cucurbitula* (Tode) Fr. = *Nectria fückeliana*
- NEMATOLOMA *fasciculare* (Huds. : Fr.) P. Karst. = *Hypholoma fasciculare*; *Nematoloma sublateritium* (Schaeff.) P. Karst. = *Hypholoma sublateritium*
- NOLANEA *lucida* P.D. Orton = *Entoloma lucidum*
- NUMMULARIA *bulliardii* Tul. & C. Tul. = *Biscogniauxia nummulara*
- OCTAVIANIA *silesiaca* Becker = *Leucogaster liosporus*
- ODONTIA *arguta* (Fr.) Quél. = *Hyphodontia arguta*; *Odontia barba-jovis* (With.) Fr. subsp. *abieticola* Bourdot & Galzin = *Kneiffiella abieticola*; *Odontia hydnoidea* (Cooke & Massee) Höhn. = *Scopuloides hydnoidea*; *Odontia sudans* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Bres. = *Dacryobolus sudans*
- OMPHALIA *hydrogramma* (Bull.) Gillet = *Clitocybe phaeophthalma*; *Omphalia leucophylla* sensu J. Lange = *Gamundia striatula*
- OMPHALINA *abiegna* (Berk. & Broome) Singer = *Chrysomphalina grossula*; *Omphalina campanella* (Batsch) Quél. = *Xeromphalina campanella*; *Omphalina ericetorum* (Fr. : Fr.) M. Lange = *Lichenomphalia umbellifera*; *Omphalina gracillima* auct. = *Hemimycena delectabilis*; *Omphalina hepatica* (Batsch : Fr.) P.D. Orton = *Omphalina subhepatica*
- OTIDEA *concinna* (Pers.) Sacc. = *Flavoscypha cantharella*; *Otidea umbrina* (Pers.) Bres. = *Otidea cochleata*
- OUDEMANSIELLA *hygrophoroides* Singer & Cléménçon = *Xerula hygrophoroides*; *Oudemansiella longipes* (P. Kumm. : Fr.) M.M. Moser = *Xerula pudens*; *Oudemansiella melanotricha* (Dörfelt.) M.M. Moser = *Xerula melanotricha*; *Oudemansiella radicata* (Relhan : Fr.) Singer = *Xerula radicata*
- PANAEOLUS *foeniseccii* (Pers. : Fr.) J. Schröt. = *Panaeolina foeniseccii*; *Panaeolus rickenii* Hora = *Panaeolus acuminatus*; *Panaeolus speciosus* P.D. Orton = *Panaeolus subfirmus*
- PANUS *rudis* Fr. = *Lentinus strigosus*; *Panus stipticus* (Bull.) Fr. = *Panellus stipticus*; *Panus strigosus* Berk. & M.A. Curtis = *Panus lecomtei*; *Panus tigrinus* (Bull. : Fr.) Singer = *Lentinus tigrinus*
- PAXILLUS *filamentosus* sensu auct. = *Paxillus rubicundulus*; *Paxillus panuoides* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. = *Tapinella panuoides*
- PAXINA *acetabulum* (L.) Kuntze = *Helvella acetabulum*; *Paxina costifera* (Nannf.) Stangel = *Helvella costifera*; *Paxina leucomelas* (Pers.) Kuntze = *Helvella leucomelaena*
- PENIOPHORA *byssoides* (Pers. : Fr.) Höhn. & Litsch. = *Amphinema byssoides*; *Peniophora cinerea* (Pers. : Fr.) Cooke var. *piceae* (Pers.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Peniophora piceae*; *Peniophora corticalis* (Bull.) Bres. = *Peniophora quercina*; *Peniophora*

- gigantea* (Fr. : Fr.) Masee = *Phebiopsis gigantea*; *Peniophora glebulosa* (Fr.) Sacc. & P. Syd. = *Tubulicrinis gracillimus*; *Peniophora livida* Fr. ex Burt = *Phebia segregata*; *Peniophora pallidula* (Bres.) Bres. = *Hyphodontia pallidula*
- PERENNIPORIA *robiniophila* (Murrill) Ryvarden = *Trametes robiniophila*
- PEZIZA *aurantia* Pers. = *Aleuria aurantia*; *Peziza coccinea* Jacq. = *Sarcoscypha coccinea*
- PHAEOMARASMIUS *ferrugineus* (Maire) M.M. Moser = *Flammulaster ferruginea*
- PHALLUS *caninus* Huds. = *Mutinus caninus*
- PHELLINUS *dryadeus* (Pers.) Pat. = *Inonotus dryadeus*; *Phellinus friesianus* (Bres.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Phellinus punctatus*; *Phellinus nigricans* (Fr. : Fr.) P. Karst. = *Phellinus igniarius*; *Phellinus ribis* (Schumach.) Quél. = *Phylloporia ribis*; *Phellinus robustus* var. *hartigii* (Allescher & Schm.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Phellinus hartigii*; *Phellinus salicinus* (Pers.) Quél. = *Phellinus conchatus*; *Phellinus tuberculatus* (Baumg.) Niemelä = *Phellinus pomaceus*
- PHLEBIA *merismoides* (Fr. : Fr.) Fr. = *Phebia radiata*
- PHLEGMACIUM *amoenolens* (Rob. Henry) M.M. Moser = *Cortinarius amoenolens*; *Phlegmacium varicolor* (Fr.) Wünsche = *Cortinarius varicolor*
- PHOLIOTA *adiposa* sensu auct. mult. = *Pholiota aurivella* or *Ph. jabnii*; *Pholiota caperata* sensu P. Kumm. = *Phaeolepiota aurea*; *Pholiota carbonaria* (Fr. : Fr.) Singer = *Pholiota highlandensis*; *Pholiota cerifera* sensu auct. = *Pholiota aurivella*; *Pholiota destruens* (Brond.) Gillet = *Pholiota populnea*; *Pholiota graminis* (Quél.) Singer = *Pholiota conissans*; *Pholiota mutabilis* (Schaeff. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Kuehneromyces mutabilis*; *Pholiota nematolomoides* (J. Favre) M.M. Moser = *Pholiota subochracea*; *Pholiota ochrochlora* (Fr.) P.D. Orton = *Pholiota gummosa*; *Pholiota radicata* (Bull.) P. Kumm. = *Hebeloma radicosum*; *Pholiota spectabilis* sensu auct. europ. = *Gymnopilus junonius*
- PHOLIOTINA *aporos* (Kits van Wav.) Cléménçon = *Conocybe aporos*; *Pholiotina pygmaeoaffinis* (Fr.) Singer = *Conocybe pygmaeoaffinis*
- PHYLLOPORUS *rhodoxanthus* (Schw. : Fr.) Bres. = *Phylloporus pelletieri*
- PHYLLOTUS *porrigens* (Pers. : Fr.) P. Karst. = *Pleurocybella porrigens*
- PHYSARUM *auriscalpium* Cooke = *Physarum decipiens*; *Physarum nutans* Pers. = *Physarum album*
- PHYSISPORINUS *sanguinolentus* (Alb. & Schwein. : Fr.) Pilát = *Rigidoporus sanguinolentus*
- PILODERMA *croceum* J. Erikss. & Hjortstam = *P. bicolor*
- PISOLITHUS *arenarius* Alb. & Schwein. = *Pisolithus arbizus*
- PLECTANIA *coccinea* (Jacq.) Fuckel = *Sarcoscypha coccinea*
- PLEUROTUS *ostreatus* f. *pulmonarius* (Fr.) Pilát = *Pleurotus pulmonarius*; *Pleurotus ostreatus* f. *salignus* (Pers. : Fr.) Pilát = *Pleurotus ostreatus*; *Pleurotus salignus* (Schrad.) Quél. = *Pleurotus ostreatus*; *Pleurotus serotinus* (Schrad.) P. Kumm. var. *flaccidus* J.E. Lange = *Panellus serotinus*; *Pleurotus tremulus* Sch. = *Hohenbuehelia tremula*; *Pleurotus ulmarius* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Lyophyllum ulmarium*
- PLUTEOPSIS *velutina* = *Psathyrella velutina* (Pers. : Fr.) Singer = *Lacrymaria lacrymabunda*
- PLUTEUS *atricapillus* (Batsch : Fr.) Fayod = *Pluteus cervinus* var. *cervinus*; *Pluteus minutissimus* Maire = *Pluteus podospileus*; *Pluteus olivaceus* P.D. Orton = *Pluteus cinereofuscus*; *Pluteus pallescens* P.D. Orton = *Pluteus satur*; *Pluteus tricuspis* Velen. = *Pluteus atromarginatus*
- POLYPORELLUS *elegans* (Bull.) P. Karst. = *Polyporus leptocephalus*
- POLYPORUS *abietinus* (Dicks.) Fr. = *Trichaptum abietinum*; *Polyporus adustus* (Willd.) Fr. = *Bjerkandera adusta*; *Polyporus albellus* Fr. = *Tyromyces chioneus*; *Polyporus delectans* Peck = *Spongipellis delectans*; *Polyporus dryadeus* (Pers.) Fr. = *Inonotus dryadeus*; *Polyporus elegans* (Bull.) Fr. = *Polyporus leptocephalus*; *Polyporus fimbriatus* Fr. : Fr. = *Hydnopolyporus fimbriatus*; *Polyporus fomentarius* (L.) Fr. = *Fomes fomentarius*; *Polyporus frondosus* (Dicks.) Fr. = *Grifola frondosa*; *Polyporus giganteus* (Pers.) Fr. = *Meripilus giganteus*; *Polyporus hartigii* Allesch. & Schnabl = *Phellinus hartigii*; *Polyporus hirsutus* (Wulfen) Fr. = *Trametes hirsuta*; *Polyporus hispidus* (Bull.) Fr. = *Inonotus hispidus*; *Polyporus igniarius* (L.) Fr. = *Phellinus igniarius*; *Polyporus intybaceus* Fr. = *Grifola frondosa*; *Polyporus lentus* Berk. = *Polyporus tuberaster*; *Polyporus montanus* (Quél.) Ferry = *Bondarzewia montana*; *Polyporus mori* (Pollini : Fr.) Fr. = *Polyporus alveolaris*; *Polyporus nidulans* Fr. = *Hapalopilus nidulans*; *Polyporus pergamenus* Fr. [as "pargamenus"] = *Trichaptum pergamenum*; *Polyporus pinicola* (Sw. : Fr.) Fr. = *Fomitopsis pinicola*; *Polyporus pubescens* (Schumach.) Fr. = *Trametes pubescens*; *Polyporus radiatus* (Sowerby : Fr.) Fr. = *Inonotus radiatus*; *Polyporus rheades* Pers. = *Inonotus rheades*; *Polyporus schweinitzii* Fr. = *Phaeolus schweinitzii*; *Polyporus semisupinus* Berk. & M.A. Curtis = *Antrodiella semisupina*; *Polyporus stipticus* (Pers.) Fr. = *Postia stiptica*; *Polyporus sulphureus* (Bull.) Fr. = *Laetiporus sulphureus*; *Polyporus ulmarius* (Sowerby : Fr.) Fr. = *Rigidoporus ulmarius*; *Polyporus versicolor* (L.) Fr. = *Trametes versicolor*
- POLYSTICTUS *hirsutus* (Wulfen) Fr. = *Trametes hirsuta*; *Polystictus versicolor* (L.) Fr. = *Trametes versicolor*
- PORIA *bombycina* (Fr. : Fr.) Cooke = *Anomoporia bombycina*; *Poria medulla-panis* (Jacq.) Pers. = *Perenniporia medulla-panis*; *Poria mollusca* (Pers.) Quél. = *Trechispora mollusca*; *Poria obliqua* (Ach. ex Pers.) P. Karst. = *Inonotus obliquus*; *Poria ochroleuca* (Berk.) Kotl. & Pouzar = *Perenniporia ochroleuca*; *Poria punctata* (Fr.) P. Karst. = *Phellinus punctatus*; *Poria reticulata* (Fr.) Cooke = *Ceriporia reticulata*; *Poria taxicola* (Pers.) Bres. = *Meruliopsis taxicola*; *Poria vaillantii* (DC. : Fr.) Cooke = *Fibroporia vaillantii*; *Poria vaporaria* (Pers.) Cooke = *Fibroporia vaillantii*; *Poria vulgaris* (Fr.) Quél. = *Coriolopsis gallica*
- POROSTEREUM *spadiceum* (Pers. : Fr.) Hjortstam & Ryvarden = *Stereum gausapatum*
- POSTIA *sericeomollis* (Romell) Jülich = *Oligoporus sericeomollis*
- PSALLIOTA *campestris* (L. : Fr.) Gillet = *Agaricus campestris*

- var. *campestris*; *Psalliota edulis* var. *valida* F.H. Møller = *Agaricus bitorquis*
- PSATHYRELLA umbonata* Peck = *Psathyrella umbonata*
- PSATHYRELLA disseminata* (Pers. : Fr.) Quél. = *Coprinus disseminatus*; *Psathyrella hydrophila* (Bull.) Maire = *Psathyrella piluliformis*; *Psathyrella lacrymabunda* (Bull. : Fr.) M.M. Moser = *Lacrymaria lacrymabunda*; *Psathyrella lutensis* (Romagn.) Bon = *Psathyrella lutensis*; *Psathyrella pyrotricha* (Holmsk. : Fr.) M.M. Moser = *Lacrymaria pyrotricha*; *Psathyrella tephrophylla* (Romagn.) Bon = *Psathyrella tephrophylla*
- PSEUDOCRATERELLUS undulatus* var. *crispus* (Pers.) Courtec. = *Pseudocraterellus sinuosus*
- PSEUDOTRAMETES gibbosa* (Pers. : Fr.) Bondartsev & Singer = *Trametes gibbosa*
- PSILOCYBE foenicicii* (Pers.) Quél. = *Panaeolina foenicicii*
- RAMARIA condensata* (Fr.) Quél. = *Ramaria stricta*; *Ramaria versatilis* Quél. = *Ramaria fennica* var. *griseoilacina*
- RHIZOPOGON rubescens* (Tul. & C. Tul.) Tul. & C. Tul. = *Rhizopogon roseolus*
- RHODOCYBE truncata* (Schaeff.) Singer = *Rhodocybe gemina*
- RHODOPHYLLUS lanicus* Romagn. = *Entoloma lanicum*; *Rhodophyllum sinuatum* (Bull.) Quél. = *Entoloma sinuatum*
- RUSSULA aurata* (With.) Fr. = *Russula aurea*; *Russula emetica* Fr. var. *silvestris* Singer = *Russula silvestris*; *Russula erythropoda* Fr. ex Pelt. = *Russula xerampelina*; *Russula flava* Romell = *Russula claroflava*; *Russula krombolzii* Schaffer = *Russula atropurpurea*; *Russula laurocerasi* Melzer = *Russula grata*; *Russula lepida* Fr. = *Russula rosea*; *Russula mairei* Singer = *Russula nobilis*; *Russula obscura* Romell = *Russula vinosa*; *Russula rosacea* (Pers.) Gray = *Russula sanguinaria*; *Russula rosea* Quél. = *Russula aurora*; *Russula undulata* Velen. = *Russula atropurpurea*
- SARCOSPHAERA crassa* (Santi) Pouzar = *Sarcosphaera coronaria*; *Sarcosphaera eximia* (Durieu & Lév.) Maire = *Sarcosphaera coronaria*
- SCHIZOPHYLLUM alneum* J. Schröt. = *Schizophyllum commune*
- SCLERODERMA aurantium* (L. : Pers.) Pers. = *Scleroderma citrinum*
- SEPULTARIA arenicola* (Lév.) Masee = *Geopora arenicola*; *Sepultaria arenosa* (Fuckel) Boud. = *Geopora arenosa*; *Sepultaria sumneriana* (Cooke) Masee = *Geopora sumneriana*
- SOLENIA anomala* (Pers.) Fuckel = *Cyphellopsis anomala*; *Solenia candida* Pers. = *Henningsomyces candidus*; *Solenia fasciculata* Pers. = *Rectipilus fasciculatus*
- STEMONITIS hyperopta* Meyl. = *Stemonitopsis hyperopta*
- STEMONITOPSIS irregularis* (Rex) T.N. Lakh. & Mukerji = *Stemonaria irregularis*
- STEREUM chailletii* (Pers. : Fr.) Fr. = *Amylostereum chailletii*; *Stereum frustulosum* (Pers.) Fr. = *Xylobolus frustulatus*; *Stereum murrayi* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Burt var. *tuberculosum* (Fr.) Pilát = *Cystostereum murrayi*; *Stereum purpureum* Pers. : Fr. = *Chondrostereum purpureum*
- STROPHARIA squamosa* (Pers. : Fr.) Sacc. = *Psilocybe squamosa*; *Stropharia stercoraria* (Bull. : Fr.) Quél. = *Stropharia semiglobata*
- TERFEZIA leonis* (Tul. & C. Tul.) Tul. & C. Tul. = *Terfezia arenaria*
- THELEPHORA spiculosa* Fr. = *Thelephora penicillata*
- TOMENTELLA gibbosa* Litsch. = *Tomentella asperula*; *Tomentella isabellina* (Fr. : Fr.) Höhn. & Litsch. = *Botryohypochnus isabellinus*; *Tomentella mucidula* (P. Karst.) Höhn. & Litsch. = *Pseudotomentella mucidula*; *Tomentella spongiosa* (Schwein. : Fr.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Tomentella lapida*; *Tomentella subcervina* Litsch. = *Tomentella cinerascens*; *Tomentella umbrina* (Fr.) Litsch. = *Pseudotomentella tristis*
- TOMENTELLINA bombycina* (P. Karst.) Bourdot & Galzin = *Tomentella fibrosa*
- TRAMETES albida* (Schaeff.) Fr. = *Postia stiptica*; *Trametes carbonaria* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) Overh. = *Gloeophyllum carbonarium*; *Trametes colliculosa* Berk. = *Pachykytospora tuberculosa*; *Trametes heteromorpha* (Fr.) Bres. = *Antrodia heteromorpha*; *Trametes hispida* Bagl. = *Coriolopsis gallica*; *Trametes malicola* Berk. & M.A. Curtis = *Antrodia malicola*; *Trametes multicolor* (Schaeff.) Jülich. = *Trametes ochracea*; *Trametes pini* (Brot. : Fr.) Fr. = *Phellinus pini*; *Trametes pini* var. *abietes* P. Karst. = *Phellinus chrysoloma*; *Trametes radiciperda* R. Hartig = *Heterobasidion annuosum*; *Trametes sepium* Berk. = *Antrodia albida*; *Trametes serialis* Fr. = *Antrodia serialis*; *Trametes trabea* (Pers.) Bres. = *Gloeophyllum trabeum*; *Trametes trogii* Berk. = *Coriolopsis trogii*; *Trametes variiformis* (Peck) Peck = *Antrodia variiformis*
- TREMELLODON gelatinosum* (Scop.) Pers. = *Pseudohydnum gelatinosum*
- TRICHOLOMA auratum* (Paulet : Fr.) Gillet = *Tricholoma flavovirens*; *Tricholoma equestre* (L. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Tricholoma flavovirens*; *Tricholoma fracticum* sensu auct. mult. = *Tricholoma batschii*; *Tricholoma gambosum* (Fr.) Gillet = *Calocybe gambosa*; *Tricholoma grammopodium* (Bull.) Fr. = *Melanoleuca grammopodia*; *Tricholoma melaleucum* (Pers.) P. Kumm. = *Melanoleuca melaleuca*; *Tricholoma nudum* (Bull. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Lepista nuda*; *Tricholoma personatum* (Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Lepista personata*; *Tricholoma rutilans* (Schaeff.) Fr. = *Tricholomopsis rutilans*; *Tricholoma sordidum* (Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Lepista sordida*
- TUBARIA trigonophylla* Lasch = *Tubaria albstipitata*
- TUBIFERA ferruginosa* (Batsch) J.F. Gmel. = *Tubulifera arachnoidea*
- TYROMYCES caesius* (Schrad. : Fr.) Murrill = *Postia caesia*; *Tyromyces floriformis* (Quél.) Bondartsev & Singer = *Postia floriformis*; *Tyromyces mollis* (Pers.) Kotl. & Pouzar = *Leptoporus mollis*; *Tyromyces placenta* (Fr.) Ryvarden = *Postia placenta*; *Tyromyces sericeomollis* (Romell) Bondartsev = *Oligoporus sericeomollis*; *Tyromyces stipticus* (Pers. : Fr.) Kotl. & Pouzar = *Postia stiptica*; *Tyromyces tephroleucus* (Fr. : Fr.) Donk = *Postia tephroleuca*

UNGULINA annosa (Fr.) Pat. = *Heterobasidion annosum*;
Ungulina fuliginosa (Scop.) Pat. = *Ischnoderma resinosum*;
Ungulina marginata (Fr.) Pat. = *Fomitopsis pinicola*;
Ungulina rosea (Alb. & Schwein.) Bourdot & Galzin
 = *Fomitopsis rosea*; *Ungulina ulmaria* (Sowerby) Pat. =
Rigidoporus ulmarius

USTULINA deusta (Hoffm. : Fr.) Lind = *Kretzschmaria deusta*;
Ustulina vulgaris Tull. & C. Tull. = *Kretzschmaria deusta*

VERPA bohémica (Krombh.) J. Schröt. = *Ptychoverpa bohémica*

VOLVARIA bombycina (Schaeff. : Fr.) P. Kumm. = *Volvariella bombycina*

VOLVARIELLA speciosa (Fr. : Fr.) Singer = *Volvariella gloiocephala*

XANTHOCHROUS hispidus (Bull. : Fr.) Pat. = *Inonotus hispidus*;
Xanthochrous perennis (L.) Pat. = *Coltricia perennis*;
Xanthochrous pini (Brot.) Pat. = *Phellinus pini*; *Xanthochrous radiatus* (Sowerby) Pat. = *Inonotus radiatus*; *Xanthochrous rheades* (Pers.) Pat. = *Inonotus rheades*

XEROCOMUS badius (Fr. : Fr.) Kuhner ex E.-J. Gilbert = *Boletus badius*; *Xerocomus chrysenteron* (Bull.) Quél. = *Boletus chrysenteron*; *Xerocomus moravicus* (Vacek) Herink = *Boletus moravicus*; *Xerocomus spadiceus* (Fr.) Quél. = *Boletus ferrugineus*; *Xerocomus subtomentosus* (L. : Fr.) Fr. = *Boletus subtomentosus*; *Xerocomus truncatus* Singer, Snell & E.A. Dick = *Boletus truncatus*

XEROMPHALINA fellea Maire & Malençon = *Xeromphalina caudicinalis*

XERULA longipes (P. Kumm. : Fr.) Maire = *Xerula pudens*

XYLOSPHAERA hypoxylon = *Xylaria hypoxylon*

UTHATOBASIDIUM ochraceum (Masse) Donk = *Thanatephorus ochraceus*

Distribution

The current knowledge of Turkish myxomycetes and macromycetes comprises 1778 species that includes 177 species of myxomycetes and 1601 macromycetes (115 species of ascomycetes and 1486 of basidiomycetes proper).

The following 84 species have been recorded **only from the European part of Turkey**: *Myxomycetes* (*Arcyria anulifera*, *Badhamia utricularis*, *Collaria arcyriomena*, *Cribraria vulgaris*, *Echinostelium ladoi*, *Hyporhamma leiocarpa*, *H. minor*, *Lamproderma columbinum*, *Licea belmontiana*, *L. inconspicua*, *L. perexigua*, *Macbrideola martini*, *Metatrichia floriformis*, *Paradiacheopsis cribrata*, *P. microcarpa*, *Perichaena tessellate*, *Physarum luteolum*, *Ph. verum*, *Protophysarum phloiogenum*, *Trichia subfusca*), *Ascomycetes* (*Arachnopeziza aurata*, *Colpoma quercinum*, *Diatrype stigma*, *Nectria cinnabarina* var. *minor*, *Peziza coccinea*), and *Basidiomycetes* (*Agaricus rimulincola*, *Anthurus muellerianus* var. *aseroeformis*, *Antrodia juniperina*, *Bovista pila*, *Buglossoporus pulvinus*, *Byssocorticium atrovirens*,

Calvatia maxima, *Cantharellus amethysteus*, *C. cinereus*, *Clavulinopsis umbrinella*, *Coltricia spathulata*, *Coprinus deliquescens*, *Cortinarius mucosus*, *Cystolepiota seminuda*, *Datronia scutellata*, *Eichleriella deglubens*, *Fomes juniperinus*, *Fomitopsis cytisina*, *Gymnopus acervatus*, *Hapalopilus nidulans*, *Hebeloma circinans*, *Hydnum velutinum*, *Hygrophoropsis aurantiaca*, *Hyphodermella corrugata*, *Hyphodontia crustosa*, *Incrustoporia nivea*, *Inonotus cuticularis*, *I. nidus-pici*, *I. obliquus*, *I. vulpinus*, *Lentinus carneotomentosus*, *Lenzites warnieri*, *Lepiota forquignonii*, *Leptoporus mollis*, *Lycoperdon pulcherrimum*, *Macrolepiota prominens*, *Melanoleuca oreina*, *Mycena immaculata*, *Mycenastrum corium*, *Mycoacia uda*, *Myriostoma coliforme*, *Oligoporus sericeomollis*, *Peniophora lycii*, *P. quercina*, *P. rufomarginata*, *Perenniporia ochroleuca*, *Phellinus contiguus*, *Ph. pilatii*, *Phlebia radiata*, *Pleurotus spodoleucus*, *Podofomes trogii*, *Polyporus anisoporus*, *P. versatilis*, *Postia floriformis*, *Psathyrella umbonata*, *Spongipellis spumeus*, *Trametes robiniophila*, *Tremella virescens*, *Vararia ochroleuca*).

289 species are known from both the **European and Asian parts of Turkey**: *Myxomycetes* (*Arcyria pomiformis*, *Echinostelium minutum*, *Lycogala epidendrum*), *Ascomycetes* (*Aleuria aurantia*, *Biscogniauxia nummulata*, *Bulgaria inquinans*, *Chlorociboria aeruginosa*, *Cyathus striatus*, *Daldinia concentrica*, *Diatrype disciformis*, *Gyromitra esculenta*, *G. infula*, *Humaria hemisphaerica*, *Hypoxylon fragiforme*, *Morchella esculenta*, *M. vulgaris*, *Nectria cinnabarina* s. lat., *N. fuckeliana*, *Peziza badia*, *P. varia*, *Sarcoscypha coccinea*, *Sarcosphaera coronaria*, *Scutellinia scutellata*), and *Basidiomycetes* (*Abortiporus biennis*, *Agaricus arvensis*, *A. bisporus*, *A. bitorquis*, *A. campestris* var. *campestris*, *A. placomyces* s. lat., *A. placomyces* var. *meleagris*, *A. silvaticus*, *A. subperonatus*, *Agrocybe cylindracea*, *Amanita caesarea*, *A. citrina*, *A. muscaria*, *A. pantherina*, *A. phalloides*, *A. rubescens*, *A. vaginata*, *A. virosa*, *Antrodia albida*, *A. serialis*, *Armillaria mellea*, *A. tabescens*, *Astraeus hygrometricus*, *Auricularia auricula-judae*, *A. mesenterica*, *Basidioradulum radula*, *Bjerkandera adusta*, *Boletus appendiculatus*, *B. badius*, *B. chrysenteron*, *B. edulis*, *B. pinophilus*, *B. radicans*, *B. regius*, *B. reticulatus*, *B. rubellus*, *B. subtomentosus*, *Bovista nigrescens*, *B. plumbea*, *Cantharellus cibarius* var. *cibarius*, *C. tubaeformis*, *Cerrena unicolor*, *Chondrostereum purpureum*, *Chroogomphus rutilus*, *Clavariadelphus pistillaris*, *Clavulinopsis corniculata*, *Clitocybe dealbata*, *C. nebularis*, *C. squamulosa*, *Clitocybula familia*, *Clitopilus prunulus*, *Coniophora puteana*, *Conocybe albipes*, *Coprinus comatus*, *C. disseminatus*, *C. domesticus*, *C. micaceus*, *C. radiatus*, *Coriolopsis gallica*, *C. trogii*, *Cortinarius duracinus*, *C. obtusus*, *C. punctatus*, *C. purpurascens*, *C. trivialis*, *Craterellus cornucopioides*, *Crepidotus cesatii*, *C. epibryus*, *C. mollis*, *Cyathus olla*, *Daedalea quercina*, *Daedaleopsis confragosa*, *Entoloma clypeatum*, *E. sinuatum*, *Exidia glandulosa*, *Fibroporia vaillantii*, *Fistulina hepatica*, *Gammulina velutipes*, *Fomes fomentarius*, *Fomitopsis pinicola*, *Flammulina striatula*, *Ganoderma adspersum*, *G. applanatum*, *G. lucidum*, *G. resinaceum*, *Gastrum fornicatum*, *G. schmidelii*, *Gloeophyllum abietinum*, *G. sepiarium*, *Gymnopilus sapineus*, *Handkea excipuliformis*, *H. utrififormis*, *Hebeloma sinapizans*, *Hericium coralloides*, *H. erinaceus*, *Hohenbuehelia atrocoerulea*, *H. petalooides* var. *petalooides*, *H. tremula*, *Hydnum repandum*,

Hygrocybe virginea, *Hygrophorus chrysodon*, *H. eburneus*, *H. hypothejus*, *Hymenochaete cruenta*, *H. rubiginosa*, *Hypholoma fasciculare*, *H. sublateritium*, *Inocybe duriuscula*, *I. geophylla* var. *geophylla*, *Inonotus dryadeus*, *I. hispidus*, *I. radiatus*, *I. rheades*, *Kuehneromyces mutabilis*, *Laccaria amethystina*, *L. laccata*, *Lacrymaria lacrymabunda*, *Lactarius deliciosus*, *L. helvus*, *L. piperatus*, *L. pubescens*, *L. rufus*, *L. uvidus*, *Laetiporus sulphureus*, *Langermannia gigantea*, *Laricifomes officinalis*, *Leccinum aurantiacum*, *L. pseudoscabrum*, *L. quercinum*, *L. scabrum*, *L. versipelle*, *Lentinellus cochleatus*, *Lentinus strigosus*, *L. tigrinus*, *Lenzites betulina*, *Lepiota aspera*, *L. erminea*, *L. ignivolata*, *Lepista inversa*, *L. irina*, *L. luscina*, *L. nuda*, *L. sordida*, *Leucoagaricus leucothites*, *Leucopaxillus giganteus*, *Lycoperdon echinatum*, *L. molle*, *L. perlatum*, *L. umbrinum*, *Macrolepiota mastoidea*, *M. procera*, *M. rachodes* var. *rachodes*, *Marasmius epiphyllus*, *M. oreades*, *M. resinus*, *M. wynnei*, *Melanoleuca cognata*, *M. grammopodia*, *M. melaleuca*, *Meripilus giganteus*, *Merulius tremellosus*, *Mycena atroalba*, *M. galericulata*, *M. hiemalis*, *M. polygramma*, *M. pura*, *M. subincarnata*, *Mutinus caninus*, *Omphalotus olearius*, *Pachykytospora tuberculosa*, *Panaeolina foenicicii*, *Panaeolus campanulatus*, *P. fimicola*, *Panellus stipticus*, *Panus conchatus*, *Paxillus atrotomentosus*, *P. involutus*, *Phaeolepiota aurea*, *Phaeolus schweinitzii*, *Phallus impudicus*, *Phanerochaete sordida*, *Phellinus hartigii*, *Ph. igniarius*, *Ph. pini*, *Ph. pomaceus*, *Ph. punctatus*, *Ph. rimosus*, *Ph. robustus*, *Ph. torulosus*, *Ph. tremulae*, *Phellodon tomentosus*, *Phlebiopsis gigantea*, *Pholiota aurivella*, *Ph. populnea*, *Phylloporia ribis*, *Phylloporus pelletieri*, *Pisolithus arhizus*, *Pleurotus cornucopiae*, *P. ostreatus*, *P. pubescens*, *P. pulmonarius*, *Pluteus cervinus* var. *cervinus*, *P. petasatus*, *P. salicinus*, *Polyporus arcularius*, *P. brumalis*, *P. fulvus*, *P. leptcephalus*, *P. squamosus*, *P. tuberaster*, *P. varius*, *Postia caesia*, *P. stiptica*, *Pulcherricum caeruleum*, *Ramaria botrytis*, *R. flava*, *R. formosa*, *R. stricta*, *Rhodocollybia butyracea*, *Rigidoporus ulmarius*, *Russula atropurpurea*, *R. aurea*, *R. aurora*, *R. brevipes*, *R. delicata*, *R. foetens*, *R. fragilis*, *R. nobilis*, *R. olivacea*, *R. pseudodelicata*, *R. rhodopoda*, *R. rosea*, *R. virescens*, *Schizophyllum commune*, *Schizopora paradoxa*, *Scleroderma verrucosum*, *Stereum gausapatum*, *S. hirsutum*, *S. insignitum*, *S. sanguinolentum*, *Stropharia aeruginosa*, *S. coronilla*, *S. semiglobata*, *Suillus bovinus*, *S. granulatus*, *S. grevillei*, *S. luteus*, *S. variegatus*, *Trametes gibbosa*, *T. hirsuta*, *T. suaveolens*, *T. versicolor*, *Trechispora farinacea*, *Tremella mesenterica*, *Trichaptum abietinum*, *Tricholoma equestre*, *T. sulphureum*, *T. terreum*, *Trichaptum pargamentum*, *Tricholomopsis rutilans*, *Tubaria furfuracea*, *Tylopilus felleus*, *Tyromyces chioneus*, *Vascellum pratense*, *Volvariella bombycina*, *Xerula radicata*, *Xylobolus frustulatus*).

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Bibliography of the contributions to Turkish myxomycetes and macromycetes

- Abatay, M. 1983. [Studies on the fungus species infecting woody plants in the East Black Sea region]. – Ormançılık Araştırma Enstitüsü Yayınları 118: 57-67. (In Turkish) [001]
- Abatay, M. 1984. [The edible mushrooms growing in our forests, their production technique and valuation]. – Ormançılık Araştırma Enstitüsü Dergisi 30: 197-211. (In Turkish) [002]
- Abatay, M. 1985. [Wood decaying fungi growing in the East and Middle Black Sea region]. – In: IV. Türkiye Fitopatoloji Kongresi, İzmir, 8-11 October 1985. P. 1. Türkiye Fitopatoloji Derneği, İzmir. (In Turkish) [003]
- Abatay, M. 1988a. [Investigations of edible fungi which can grow on woods in different ecological conditions]. – In: S. İren *et al.* [eds]. V. Türkiye Fitopatoloji Kongresi, Antalya, 18-21 October 1988. P. 35. Türkiye Fitopatoloji Derneği, Antalya. (In Turkish) [004]
- Abatay, M. 1988b. [Investigations of some edible fungi of Turkey]. – In: A. Sagkaya *et al.* [eds]. I. Orman Tali Ürünleri Sempozyumu Programı, Ankara, 14-17 June 1988. P. 1. Ormançılık ve Tabiatı Koruma Vakfı, Ankara. (In Turkish) [005]
- Abatay, M. 1989. [Lignicolous fungi attacking test logs in the production of *Pleurotus* sp. and some prevention methods]. – Tarım Orman ve Köyişleri Bakanlığı Orman Genel Müdürlüğü Dergisi 1: 97-105. (In Turkish) [006]
- Afyon, A. 1994a. [The edible mushrooms of Isparta district]. – In: N. Aktaç *et al.* [eds]. XII. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Edirne, 6-8 June 1994. Pp. 145-149. Trakya Üniversitesi, Edirne. (In Turkish) [007]
- Afyon, A. 1994b. [Some new records for the mushroom flora of Turkey]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 18: 169-173. (In Turkish) [008]
- Afyon, A. 1996a. [Some macrofungi determined of Isparta province in Turkey]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 20: 161-164. (In Turkish) [009]
- Afyon, A. 1996b. [Some macrofungi identified in Konya (Meram-Selçuklu) district]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 20: 259-262. (In Turkish) [010]
- Afyon, A. 1996c. Macrofungi of Beyşehir district (Konya). – Turkish Journal of Botany 20: 527-530. [011]
- Afyon, A. 1997a. Two new ascomycete records for the fungi flora of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 21: 107-108. [012]
- Afyon, A. 1997b. New records for Turkish mycoflora from Beyşehir in the Konya province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 21: 109-113. [013]
- Afyon, A. 1997c. New records of Turkish macrofungi in Derbent county, Konya province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 21: 115-117. [014]
- Afyon, A. 1997d. Macrofungi of Seydişehir district (Konya). – Turkish Journal of Botany 21: 173-176. [015]
- Afyon, A. 1997e. Mycoflora of Derbent district (Konya). – Turkish Journal of Botany 21: 217-220. [016]

- Afyon, A. 2000a. [A study on macrofungi of Ilgın district (Konya)]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi 8(1): 27-33. (In Turkish) [017]
- Afyon, A. 2000b. [A study on macrofungi of Bartın district]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi 8(2): 77-86. (In Turkish) [018]
- Afyon, A. 2001a. New records of Entolomataceae for the macrofungi of Turkey. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi 9: 103-107. [019]
- Afyon, A. 2001b. New records of Hygrophoraceae for the macrofungi of Turkey. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi 9: 119-125. [020]
- Afyon, A. & Konuk, M. 2000. [Some important edible mushrooms known by the local people of Western Black Sea region]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi 9: 109-118. (In Turkish) [021]
- Afyon, A. & Konuk, M. 2001. [Poisonous mushrooms of West Black Sea region (Turkey)]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi 9: 145-153. (In Turkish) [022]
- Afyon, A. & Konuk, M. 2002. [A study on macrofungi of Zonguldak district]. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 9(1): 121-128. (In Turkish) [023]
- Afyon, A. & Yağız, D. 2004. Macrofungi of Sinop Province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 28: 351-360. [024]
- Afyon, A., Konuk, M. & Yağız, D. 2001. [Investigations on the macrofungi of West Black Sea region]. Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknik Araştırma Kurumu, project number: TBAG-1659, Ankara. (In Turkish) [025]
- Aktaş, S. 2001. [Taxonomic investigations of macrofungi growing in Ahırılı, Yalhöyük districts and North Bozkır (Konya)]. MSc thesis. Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Konya. (In Turkish) [026]
- Aktaş, S., Öztürk, C., Kaşık, G., Sabahlar, S. & Doğan, H.H. 2003. Macrofungus flora of Bozkır district (Konya). – Turkish Journal of Botany 27: 37-43. [027]
- Allı, H. 1999. [Taxonomical studies on parasitic macrofungi of Muğla province]. MSc thesis. Uludağ Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Bursa. (In Turkish) [028]
- Allı, H. & Işıloğlu, M. 2000. The parasitic macrofungi of Muğla province, Turkey. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 7(1): 249-255. [029]
- Altan, Y., Gücin F. & Babaç, M.T. 1986. [Observations on the flora of Gülveren village (Erzurum – Şenkaya)]. – Ege Üniversitesi Journal of Science Faculty 8: 21-38. (In Turkish) [030]
- Anşin, R. 1976. [The flora of Trabzon – Meryemana Research Forest and floristic researches at pure Oriental Spruce stands]. PhD thesis. İstanbul Üniversitesi, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [031]
- Anşin, R., Eminağaoğlu O. & Göktürk, T. 2000. [Some edible fungi in the Artvin Areas]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye VI. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi Bildirileri, Bergama, 20-22 September 2000. Pp. 122-129. Ege Üniversitesi Bergama Meslek Yüksekokulu, İzmir. (In Turkish) [032]
- Asan, A. & Gücin, F. 1990. [Some macrofungi determined on the Istranca mountains (Trakya)]. – In: A. Çakır, S. Özyurt, S. Salman & M. Özkan [eds]. X. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Erzurum, 18-20 July 1990. Pp. 155-161. Atatürk Üniversitesi, Erzurum. (In Turkish) [033]
- Asan, A., Sesli, E., Gücin, F. & Stojchev, G. 2002. *Myriostoma coliforme* and *Phylloporia ribis* (Basidiomycetes): First reports from European Turkey. – Botanika Chronika 15: 45-49. [034]
- Asbagh, E.A. & Solak, M.H. 2000. [Some edible macrofungi of Dede mountain and Balçova Dam (İzmir)]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye VI. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi Bildirileri, Bergama, 20-22 September 2000. Pp. 148-155. Ege Üniversitesi Bergama Meslek Yüksekokulu, İzmir. (In Turkish) [035]
- Aşkun, T. 1996. [Taxonomic study on the macrofungi of Balya (Balıkesir) and surroundings]. MSc thesis. Balıkesir Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Balıkesir. (In Turkish) [036]
- Aşkun, T. & Işıloğlu, M. 1997. Macrofungi of Balya (Balıkesir) county. – Turkish Journal of Botany 21: 279-284. [037]
- Aslantaş, I. 1999. [An investigation of the mushrooms of Sivas district]. MSc thesis. İnönü Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Malatya. (In Turkish) [038]
- Atasoy, N. 1998. [Investigations on the mushrooms growing in Fethipaşa, Sultantepe and Çamlıca woods]. MSc thesis. Marmara Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [039]
- Balci, Y. 1996. [Researches on the fungi species grown in Belgrad forest and surroundings]. MSc thesis. İstanbul Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [040]
- Baydar, S. & Sesli, E. 1994. [The macromycetes determined in Akçaabat district of Trabzon province]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 18: 99-101. (In Turkish) [041]
- Bilir, T. 2000. [Studies on the fungus flora of Uludağ particularly in and around Bursa, Turkey]. PhD thesis. Marmara Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [042]
- Çalışkan, S. 2001. [Investigations of antimicrobial effect of some macrofungi species]. MSc thesis. Pamukkale Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Denizli. (In Turkish) [043]
- Çoban, E. & Işıloğlu, M. 2000. [Antimicrobial activity of some edible mushrooms]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye VI. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi Bildirileri, Bergama, 20-22 September 2000. Pp. 229-235. Ege Üniversitesi Bergama Meslek Yüksekokulu, İzmir. (In Turkish) [044]
- Demirel, K. 1990. [Systematic, morphologic, ecologic and economic studies on some macrofungi growing in Erzurum district]. MSc thesis. Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Van. (In Turkish) [045]
- Demirel, K. 1993a. [Macrofungi of Ardanuç (Artvin) district. I]. – Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi 4: 49-57. (In Turkish) [046]
- Demirel, K. 1993b. [A taxonomical research on some edible, non edible and poisonous mushrooms growing in Van district]. PhD thesis. Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Van. (In Turkish) [047]
- Demirel, K. 1994. [The macrofungi of Ardanuç (Artvin) province. II]. – Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi 5: 139-146. (In Turkish) [048]
- Demirel, K. 1996a. Two new records of Gasteromycetes for Turkey. – Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Journal of Faculty of Education 1: 136-139 [049]
- Demirel, K. 1996b. [The macrofungi of Van province (Turkey)]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 20: 165-169. (In Turkish) [050]
- Demirel, K. 1997a. Two new records for the mycoflora of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 21: 103-105. [051]
- Demirel, K. 1997b. New records for the mycoflora of Turkey. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 4(1): 49-52. [052]
- Demirel, K. 1998a. New records for the fungus flora of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 22: 349-353. [053]
- Demirel, K. 1998b. [Some macrofungi determined on Karçal mountains (Artvin) and surroundings]. – In: M. Kılınc [ed.]. XIV. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Samsun, 7-10 September 1998. Pp. 177-184. Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi, Samsun. (In Turkish) [054]

- Demirel, K. 1999. Contributions to Turkish mycoflora from the Ardanuç district of Artvin province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 23: 405-409. [055]
- Demirel, K. & Nacar, M. 2000. Macrofungi of Çemişgezek (Tunceli) district. – Hacettepe Bulletin of Natural Sciences and Engineering 29: 1-7. [056]
- Demirel, K. & Öztürk, A. 1993. [Some edible mushroom species of Ardanuç (Artvin) district]. – Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi 4: 1-8. (In Turkish) [057]
- Demirel, K. & Öztürk, A. 1994. [Some edible and poisonous fungi of Van district]. – In: N. Aktaç *et al.* [eds]. XII. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Edirne, 6-8 July 1994. Pp. 151-155. Trakya Üniversitesi, Edirne. (In Turkish) [058]
- Demirel, K. & Uzun, Y. 1996a. [Some wood decaying macrofungi determined around Van lake]. – Ekoloji Çevre Dergisi 21: 32-36. (In Turkish) [059]
- Demirel, K. & Uzun, Y. 1996b. [Contributions to the macrofungi of Sarıkamış (Kars) district]. – Hacettepe Fen ve Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi 17: 121-132. (In Turkish) [060]
- Demirel, K. & Uzun, Y. 1999. [New records for Turkish mycoflora from Sarıkamış in the Kars province]. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 6(1): 83-88. (In Turkish) [061]
- Demirel, K. & Uzun, Y. 2002. Macrofungi of Ağrı province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 26: 291-295. [062]
- Demirel, K. & Uzun, Y. 2004. Two new records of *Phallales* for the mycoflora of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 28: 213-214. [cf. Demirel, K. & Uzun, Y. 2002. In: A. Güner *et al.* [eds]. VIth Plant Life of Southwest Asia Symposium, Van, 10-14 June 2002. Pp. 81-82. Yüzüncü Yıl University, Van, Turkey]. [063]
- Demirel, K., Kaya, A. & Uzun, Y. 2003. Macrofungi of Erzurum province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 27: 29-36. [064]
- Demirel, K., Uzun, Y. & Kaya, A. 2004. Some poisonous fungi of East Anatolia. – Turkish Journal of Botany 28: 215-219. [cf. Demirel, K. & Uzun, Y. 2002. In: A. Güner *et al.* [eds]. VIth Plant Life of Southwest Asia Symposium, Van, 10-14 June 2002. Pp. 57-58. Yüzüncü Yıl University, Van, Turkey]. [065]
- Doğan, H.H. 2001. [Taxonomical investigations of the macrofungi of Karaman district]. PhD thesis. Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Konya. (In Turkish) [066]
- Doğan, H.H. & Işiloğlu, M. 2002. A new and interesting ascomycete genus (*Pithya* Fuckel) record for the flora of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 26: 403-404. [067]
- Doğan, H.H., Öztürk, C. & Kaşık, G. 2000. Two new records for the macrofungi flora of Turkey. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi 17: 7-10. [068]
- Doğan, H.H., Güner, M. & Öztürk, C. 2001. Two new ascomycete genera for the fungus flora of Turkey. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 8(1): 113-118. [069]
- Doğan, H.H., Öztürk, C. & Kaşık, G. 2002. Two new *Peziza* records from Mut environ. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 9(2): 117-122. [070]
- Doğan, H.H., Kaşık, G., Öztürk, C. & Aktaş, S. 2003a. New records of Coprinaceae and Bolbitiaceae from Karaman province. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 10(1): 111-141. [071]
- Doğan, H.H., Öztürk, C., Kaşık, G., & Aktaş, S. 2003b. New records for the mycoflora of Turkey from Mut environ. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 10(2): 197-211. [072]
- Ergül, C.C. 1996. [A new record for Turkish myxomycetes – *Physurum pusillum* (Berk. & Curt.) G. Lister]. – In: A. Özalpan [ed.]. XIII. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi Bildiri ve Poster Özetleri, İstanbul, 17-20 September 1996. P. 55. İstanbul Üniversitesi, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [073]
- Ergül, C.C. & Başaran, D. 1998. The Myxomycetes of Görükle (Bursa) campus area. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 5(1): 93-96. [074]
- Ergül, C.C. & Dülger, B. 1999. [A new myxomycetes taxon for the Turkish mycoflora: *Symphytocarpus flaccidus* (Lister) Ing & Nann.-Bremek.]. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 6(1): 99-102. (In Turkish) [075]
- Ergül, C.C. & Dülger, B. 2000a. Three new records of *Paradiacheopsis* Hertel for the Turkish myxomycetes flora. – In: N. Özhatay [ed.]. Second Balkan Botanical Congress, İstanbul, 14-18 May 2000. Vol. 2. Pp. 201-206. İstanbul University, İstanbul. [076]
- Ergül, C. & Dülger, B. 2000b. A new Myxomycetes record for the Turkish mycoflora. – Turkish Journal of Botany 24: 289-291. [077]
- Ergül, C.C. & Dülger, B. 2000c. A new myxomycete genus record for Turkey (*Stemonitopsis* (Nann.-Bremek.) Nann.-Bremek.). – Turkish Journal of Botany 24: 355-357. [078]
- Ergül, C.C. & Dülger, B. 2000d. Myxomycetes of Turkey. – Karstenia 40: 39-41. [079]
- Ergül, C. & Dülger, B. 2002a. Two new records of myxomycete taxa for Turkish mycoflora. – Ot Sistematiği Botanik Dergisi 9(1): 129-136. [080]
- Ergül, C.C. & Dülger, B. 2002b. A new record for the myxomycete flora of Turkey: *Comatricha pulchella* (C. Bab.) Rost. var. *pulchella*. – Turkish Journal of Botany 26: 113-115. [081]
- Ergül, C.C. & Dülger, B. 2002c. New records for the myxomycetes flora of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 26: 277-280. [082]
- Ergül, C.C. & Gücin, F. 1992. [Two new myxomycetes taxa for Turkey]. – In: S. Özçelik & T. Babaç [eds]. XI. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Elazığ, 24-27 June 1992. P. 1. Fırat Üniversitesi, Elazığ. (In Turkish) [083]
- Ergül, C.C. & Gücin, F. 1994. [A new record for Turkish myxomycetes: *Fuligo septica* (L.) Wiggers]. – In: N. Aktaç *et al.* [eds]. XII. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Edirne, 6-8 July 1994. Pp. 157-159. Trakya Üniversitesi, Edirne. (In Turkish) [084]
- Ergül, C.C. & Gücin, F. 1995. [A new myxomycete taxon for Turkey: *Hemitrichia* Rost.]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 19: 165-166. (In Turkish) [085]
- Ergül, C.C., Dülger, B. & Akgül, H. In press. Myxomycetes of Mezit Stream valley of Turkey. – Mycotaxon (http://biyoloji.uludag.edu.tr/ergul/Checklist_001.pdf). [086]
- Erkal, C. 1996. [Taxonomical researches on macrofungi of Kapıdağ peninsula (Erdek) and its surroundings]. MSc thesis. Balıkesir Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Balıkesir. (In Turkish) [087]
- Ertan, Ö.O. 1992. [Some mushrooms determined Eğirdir environments]. – In: S. Özçelik & T. Babaç [eds]. XI. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Elazığ, 24-27 June 1992. P. 45. Fırat Üniversitesi, Elazığ. (In Turkish) [088]
- Ertan, Ö.O. 1994. [Some mushroom species determined Çamyol (Aksu-İsparta) environments]. – In: N. Aktaç *et al.* [eds]. XII. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Edirne, 6-8 July 1994. P. 91. Trakya Üniversitesi, Edirne. (In Turkish) [089]
- Gezer, K. 1988. [A taxonomic investigation of some macrofungi growing in Eskişehir province]. MSc thesis. Anadolu Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Eskişehir. (In Turkish) [090]
- Gezer, K. 1997. Taxonomic investigations of some mushrooms distributed in Antalya. PhD thesis. Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İzmir. [091]
- Gezer, K. 2000. Contributions to the macrofungus flora of Antalya province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 24: 293-298. [092]

- Gezer, K. & Durkan, N. 2000. [An investigation of some edible mushrooms distributed in Çal (Denizli)]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye VI. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi Bildirileri, Bergama, 20-22 September 2000. Pp. 116-121. Ege Üniversitesi Bergama Meslek Yüksekokulu, İzmir. (In Turkish) [093]
- Gezer, K., Durkan, N. & Köse, S. 1999. [The macrofungi of Babadağ (Denizli)]. – In: Y. Özpınar [ed.]. I. Babadağ Sempozyumu, Denizli, 1-3 December 1999. P. 154-165. Pamukkale Üniversitesi, Denizli. (In Turkish) [094]
- Gezer, K., Durkan, N., Yelek, F. & Köse, S. 2000. [Poisonous mushrooms of Denizli]. – In: VI. Ulusal Tıbbi Biyoloji Kongresi, Denizli, 2-5 November 2000. P. 242. Pamukkale Üniversitesi, Denizli. (In Turkish) [095]
- Gezer, K., Gökler, I. & Işiloğlu, M. 2000. [New records for Turkish mycoflora in the Antalya region]. – *Ekoloji ve Çevre Dergisi* 37: 17-19. (In Turkish) [096]
- Gezer, T. 1992. [A taxonomical investigation of some macrofungi growing in Denizli province]. MSc thesis. Ege Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İzmir. (In Turkish) [097]
- Gücin, F. 1982. [Macrofungus flora of Manisa province in Turkey]. – *Doğa Bilim Dergisi* 6(3): 91-96. (In Turkish) [098]
- Gücin, F. 1984. [Edible wild mushrooms in Elazığ district and new records for Turkish mycoflora.]. – In: Türkiye III. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi, Yalova, 10-12 October 1984. P. 1. Tarım Orman ve Köyişleri Bakanlığı, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [099]
- Gücin, F. 1985. [An edible important fungus growing in some region which will remain under the Karakaya dam lake and environments: *Terfezia boudieri* Chatin.]. – In: H. Asmaz [ed.]. II. Tabiatı Koruma Kongresi, Ankara, 18-20 November 1985. Pp.1-11. Türkiye Tabiatını Koruma Derneği, Ankara. (In Turkish) [100]
- Gücin, F. 1986. [Some medicinal and poisonous fungi determined in Fırat River basin.]. – In: Fırat Havzası Tıbbi ve Endüstriyel Bitkileri Sempozyumu, Elazığ, 6-8 October 1991. Pp. 63-82. Fırat Üniversitesi, Elazığ. (In Turkish) [101]
- Gücin, F. 1987. Macrofungi of Pütürge (Malatya) in Eastern Anatolia. – *The Journal of Fırat University* 2(1): 19-26. [102]
- Gücin, F. 1990. [Macrofungi found surroundings of Elazığ.]. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* 14: 171-177. (In Turkish) [103]
- Gücin, F. 1992. [The morels (*Morchella*) growing in Kozak highland (Bergama – İzmir) and having potential for export.]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye IV. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi, Yalova, 2-4 November 1992. Pp. 40-48. Yalova Atatürk Bahçe Kültürleri Merkez Araştırma Enstitüsü, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [104]
- Gücin, F. 1994. [Macrofungi.]. – *Bilim ve Teknik Dergisi* 12: 74-81. (In Turkish) [105]
- Gücin, F. & Baltepe, S. 1989. [Mushrooms as heavy metal accumulators.]. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* 13(3): 584-594. (In Turkish) [106]
- Gücin, F. & Ergül, C. 1995. A new myxomycete genus (*Enteridium*) record for the Turkish mycoflora. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* 19: 565-566. [107]
- Gücin, F. & Işiloğlu, M. 1995. Some new ascomycete genera records for the fungi flora of Turkey. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* 19: 485-487. [108]
- Gücin, F. & Öner, M. 1982. [New ascomycetes for Turkish mycoflora.]. – *Fırat Üniversitesi Fen Fakültesi Dergisi* 2(2): 107-110. (In Turkish) [109]
- Gücin, F., Gezer K. & Tamer, A.Ü. 1988. [Some macrofungi from Eskişehir district.]. – In: Z. Özer [ed.]. IX. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Sivas, 21-23 September 1988. Pp. 445-502. Cumhuriyet Üniversitesi, Sivas. (In Turkish) [110]
- Gücin, F., Işiloğlu, M. & Solak, M.H. 1995a. Macrofungi of Kozak plateau (West Anatolia). – In: XIIth Congress of European Mycologists, Wageningen, 3-7 September 1995. P. 22. Wageningen, The Netherlands. [111]
- Gücin, F., Işiloğlu, M., Solak, M.H. & Ergül, C. 1995b. [Determination of Northwest Anatolian mushrooms (edible, poisonous and lignicolous ones)]. Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknik Araştırma Kurumu, project number: TBAG-1132, Ankara. (In Turkish) [112]
- Gücin, F., Solak, M.H. & Işiloğlu, M. 1996. Mushrooms of Uludağ (Bursa-Turkey). – In: M. Öztürk, Ö. Seçmen & G. Görk [eds]. Plant Life in Southwest and Central Asia Symposium, İzmir, 21-28 May 1995. Vol. 1. Pp. 402-413. Ege University Press, İzmir. [113]
- Gün, Z., Gücin, F. & Ergül, C.C. 1996. [The myxomycetes taxa determined from Uludağ vegetation zone.]. – In: A. Özalp [ed.]. XIII. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, İstanbul, 17-20 September 1996. P. 76. İstanbul Üniversitesi, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [114]
- Härkönen, M. 1988. Some additions to the knowledge of Turkish Myxomycetes. – *Karstenia* 27[1987]: 1-7. [115]
- Härkönen, M. & Uotila, P. 1983. Turkish Myxomycetes developed in moist chamber cultures. – *Karstenia* 23: 1-9. [116]
- Hatat, G. & Peksen, A. 2000. Galeropsidaceae, a new family for the mycobiota of Turkey. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* 24: 203-205. [117]
- Hüseyin, E., Aslantaş, I. & Selçuk, F. 2000. [The trophic structure of agaricoid fungi in Sivas Province (Turkey)]. – In: XV. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Ankara, 5-9 September 2000. Pp. 143-147. Ankara Üniversitesi, Ankara. (In Turkish) [118]
- Huseyinov, E., Selçuk, F. & Aslantaş, I. 2001. Some data on agaricoid fungi from Sivas Province (Turkey). – *Mikologia & Fitopatologia* 35(4): 29-33. [119]
- Işiloğlu, M. 1987. [Taxonomical investigations of the edible and poisonous mushrooms growing in Malatya and surroundings.]. MSc thesis. Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Konya. (In Turkish) [120]
- Işiloğlu, M. 1992a. Popular edible macrofungi of Adana and Icel (South Turkey). – In: XIth Congress of European Mycologists, Kew, England 7-11 September 1992. P. 21. Kew. [121]
- Işiloğlu, M. 1992b. Poisonous macrofungi from Adana and Icel (South Turkey) – In: XIth Congress of European Mycologists, Kew, England 7-11 September 1992. P. 21. Kew. [122]
- Işiloğlu, M. 1992c. [The edible mushroom species of Muğla district.]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye IV. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi, Yalova, 2-4 November 1992. Pp. 49-55. Yalova Atatürk Bahçe Kültürleri Merkez Araştırma Enstitüsü, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [123]
- Işiloğlu, M. 1992d. [The mushroom species using up by people living in Malatya.]. – In: S. Özçelik & T. Babaç [eds]. XI. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Elazığ, 24-27 June 1992. P. 11. Fırat Üniversitesi, Elazığ. (In Turkish) [124]
- Işiloğlu, M. 1994. A new record for the fungus flora of Turkey. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* 18: 451-452. [125]
- Işiloğlu, M. 1997. Macrofungi of Sarıçekrek yaylası (Malatya). – *Turkish Journal of Botany* 21: 63-65. [126]
- Işiloğlu, M. 1999. The macrofungi of Sandras Mountain (West Anatolia). – In: J.L. Manjón [ed.]. Congress of European Mycologists, Alcalá de Henares, 21-25 September 1999. P. 59. Madrid. [127]
- Işiloğlu, M. 2001. [The macrofungi of Sandras mountain (Muğla)]. – *Selçuk Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi* 9: 127-136. (In Turkish) [128]

- İşiloğlu, M. & Bahçecioglu, Z. 1994. [Parasitic macrofungi of Malatya province]. – In: N. Aktaş *et al.* [eds]. XII. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Edirne, 6-8 July 1994. Pp. 141-143. Trakya Üniversitesi, Edirne. (In Turkish) [129]
- İşiloğlu, M. & Gücin, F. 1995. [Auriscalpiaceae, a new family for Turkey]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 19: 171-172 (In Turkish) [130]
- İşiloğlu, M. & Öder, N. 1995a. [Macrofungi of Malatya province]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 19: 321-324. (In Turkish) [131]
- İşiloğlu, M. & Öder, N. 1995b. Contributions to the macrofungi of Mediterranean Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 19: 603-609. [132]
- İşiloğlu, M. & Watling, R. 1991. Poisonings by *Lepiota helveola* Bres. in Southern Turkey. – Edinburgh Journal of Botany 48(1): 91-100. [133]
- İşiloğlu, M. & Watling, R. 1992. Macromycetes of Mediterranean Turkey. – Edinburgh Journal of Botany 49(1): 99-121. [134]
- İşiloğlu, M., Gücin, F. & Solak, M.H. 1995. Macrofungi of Kazdağları (Mount Ida). – In: Th.W. Kuyper [ed.]. XIIth Congress of European Mycologists, Wageningen, 3-7 September 1995. P. 27. Wageningen, The Netherlands. [135]
- İşiloğlu, M., Solak, M.H. & Gücin, F. 1998. The edible macrofungi of northwest Anatolia. – In: O. Ashurmetov, F. Khassanov & Y. Salieva [eds]. International Symposium Plant Life in South-West and Central Asia, Tashkent, 18-22 May 1998. Pp. 88-90. Tashkent. [136]
- İşiloğlu, M., Merdivan, M. & Yılmaz, F. 2001a. Heavy metal contents in some macrofungi collected in the Northwestern Part of Turkey. – Archives of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology 41: 1-7. [137]
- İşiloğlu, M., Yılmaz, F. & Merdivan, M. 2001b. Concentrations of trace elements in wild edible mushrooms. – Food Chemistry 73: 169-175. [138]
- İşiloğlu, M., Solak, M.H. & Yılmaz, F. 2002. Morels of Turkey. – In: T.J. Baroni [ed.]. Mycological Society of America, Annual Meeting, Corvallis, Oregon, June 24-26, 2002. P. 1. Oregon State University, Corvallis, Oregon. [139]
- İşiloğlu, M., Allı, H., Solak, M.H. & Yılmaz Ersel, F. 2004a. *Lactarius* taxa of Turkey. – In: Planta Europa, Proceedings of the 4th European conference on the conservation of wild plants, Valencia, Spain, 17-20 September 2004. <http://www.nerium.net/plantaeuropa/Proceedings.htm>. [140]
- İşiloğlu, M., Bas, H. & Allı, H. 2004b. Some critically endangered taxa from Turkey. – In: Planta Europa, Proceedings of the 4th European conference on the conservation of wild plants, Valencia, Spain, 17-20 September 2004. <http://www.nerium.net/plantaeuropa/Proceedings.htm>. [141]
- Karadelev, M. 1999. Lignicolous Aphyllophorales on Mediterranean Turkey. – Mycologia Montenegrina 2: 79-82. [142]
- Karadelev, M. & Doğan, H.H. 2003. *Laricifomes officinalis* (Vill. : Fr.) Kotl. & Pouz. on *Cedrus libani* in Turkey. – Mycologia Montenegrina 6: 69-72. [143]
- Karamanoğlu, K. & Öder, N. 1973. [Some mushrooms from Bursa area]. – Ankara Üniversitesi Eczacılık Fakültesi Mecmuası 3(13): 13-33. (In Turkish) [144]
- Kaşık, G. 1990. [A taxonomical investigation on mushrooms growing on trees around the city of Konya]. MSc thesis. Atatürk Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Erzurum. (In Turkish) [145]
- Kaşık, G. 1994. [A research on taxonomy of macrofungi on trees in Konya]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 18: 23-27. (In Turkish) [146]
- Kaşık, G. & Öztürk, C. 1995. [Some edible, poisonous and non-edible macrofungi in Aksaray]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 19: 401-403. (In Turkish) [147]
- Kaşık, G. & Öztürk, C. 1998a. [Some macrofungi growing in Ereğli (Konya) district]. – In: M. Kılınc [ed.]. XIV. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Samsun, 7-10 September 1998. Pp. 185-191. Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi, Samsun. (In Turkish) [148]
- Kaşık, G. & Öztürk, C. 1998b. [The macrofungi determined after poisoning by fungi in İstanbul]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi 5: 41-46. (In Turkish) [149]
- Kaşık, G. & Öztürk, C. 1999. [A new record for macrofungus flora of Turkey]. – Ot Sistematik Botanik Dergisi 6(1): 89-94. (In Turkish) [150]
- Kaşık, G. & Öztürk, C. 2000. [Macrofungi of Hadim and Taşkent (Konya) district]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi 17: 1-6. (In Turkish) [151]
- Kaşık, G., Öztürk, C., Akkoz, C. & Doğan, H.H. 1998. [Some macrofungi determined in S. U. Alaaddin Keykubat campus]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi 15: 87-99. (In Turkish) [152]
- Kaşık, G., Öztürk, C. & Doğan, H.H. 2000. [Macrofungi of Ermenek (Karaman) district]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi 1(16): 61-65. (In Turkish) [153]
- Kaşık, G., Öztürk, C. & Toprak, E. 2001. Macrofungi of Niğde province (Turkey). – Ot Sistematik Botanik Dergisi 8(2): 137-142. [154]
- Kaşık, G., Öztürk, C., Türkoğlu, A. & Doğan, H.H. 2002. Macrofungi flora of Yeşilhisar district (Kayseri). – Ot Sistematik Botanik Dergisi 9(2): 123-134. [155]
- Kaşık, G., Doğan, H.H., Öztürk, C. & Aktaş, S. 2003a. New records of Tricholomataceae and Cortinariaceae for Turkish macrofungi flora from Alanya (Antalya) district. – Ot Sistematik Botanik Dergisi 10(1): 143-170. [156]
- Kaşık, G., Öztürk, C., Türkoğlu, A. & Doğan, H.H. 2003b. Macrofungi of Yahyalı (Kayseri) province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 27: 453-462. [157]
- Kaşık, G., Doğan, H.H., Öztürk, C. & Aktaş, S. 2004. New records in Coprinaceae and Bolbitiaceae from Mut (Mersin) District. – Turkish Journal of Botany 28: 449-455. [158]
- Kaya, A. 1999. [A taxonomic research on edible and poisonous macrofungi growing in Muş and Bitlis]. PhD thesis. Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Van. (In Turkish) [159]
- Kaya, A. 2000a. [Edible macrofungi determined in Muş and Bitlis provinces]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye VI. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi Bildirileri, Bergama, 20-22 September 2000. Pp. 112-115. Ege Üniversitesi, Bergama. (In Turkish) [160]
- Kaya, A. 2000b. Two new genus records for the mycoflora of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 24: 285-288. [161]
- Kaya, A. 2000c. Poisonous macrofungi determined in Muş and Bitlis provinces (Turkey). – In: N. Özhatay [ed.]. Second Balkan Botanical Congress, İstanbul, 14-18 May 2000. Vol. 2. Pp. 263-267. İstanbul Üniversitesi, İstanbul. [162]
- Kaya, A. 2000d. New records of Tricholomataceae for the mycoflora of Turkey. – Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences 19B(2): 77-81. [162a]
- Kaya, A. 2001. Contributions to the macrofungus flora of Bitlis province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 25: 379-383. [163]
- Kaya, A. 2005. Macrofungi determined in Gölbaşı (Adıyaman) district. – Turkish Journal of Botany 29: 45-50. [163a]
- Kaya, A. & Demirel, K. 1998. Two new Myxomycetes for the mycoflora of Turkey. – Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences 17B(2): 47-48. [164]

- Kaya, A., Demirel, K. & Bıyık, H. 1999. Three new *Coprinus* records for the mycoflora of Turkey. – Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences **18B**(1): 11-14. [165]
- Kaya, A., Akan, Z. & Demirel, K. 2004. A checklist of macrofungi of Besni (Adıyaman) district. – Turkish Journal of Botany **28**: 247-251. [cf. Kaya, A., Akan, Z. & Demirel, K. 2002. Macrofungi of Besni (Adıyaman) district. – In: A. Güner, S.A. Ghazanfar, M. Koyuncu & N. Adıgüzel [eds]. Plant Life of Southwest Asia Symposium, Van, 10-14 June 2002. Pp. 79. Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi, Van, Turkey]. [166]
- Kızılkaya, Y. 1997. [*Morchella* fungi growing in Denizli district]. MSc thesis. Pamukkale Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Denizli. (In Turkish) [167]
- Köse, S. 1999. [A research on macrofungus flora of Bekilli (Denizli) and its surroundings]. MSc thesis. Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İzmir. (In Turkish) [168]
- Köse, S. & Gezer, K. 1999. [Taxonomical investigations of some edible mushrooms distributed in Bekilli (Denizli)]. – In: A. Tatlı, H. Ölçer, N. Bingöl & H. Akan [eds]. 1st International Symposium on Protection of Natural Environment and Ehlami Karaçam, Kütahya, 23-25 September 1999. Pp. 192-198. Dumlupınar Üniversitesi, Kütahya. (In Turkish) [169]
- Kotlaba, F. 1976. Contribution to the knowledge of the Turkish macromycetes. – Česka Mycologie **30**: 3-4. [170]
- Küçük, M. 1992. [The flora of Kürtün (Gümüşhane) Örumcek forests and the floristic composition of pure stand types]. PhD thesis. Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Trabzon. (In Turkish) [171]
- Kurt, H. 1999. [A research on macrofungi of Akören county (Konya)]. MSc thesis. Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Konya. (In Turkish) [172]
- Lohwag, K. 1957. [Research on Turkish mycoflora]. – İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi **7**(1): 129-137. (In Turkish) [173]
- Mat, A. 1998. [Mushroom poisoning and poisonous fungi in Turkey]. Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknik Araştırma Kurumu, Ankara. (In Turkish) [174]
- Nacar, M. 1997. [A taxonomic research on some macrofungi growing in Çemişgezek (Tunceli) district]. MSc thesis. Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Van. (In Turkish) [175]
- Niemela, T. & Uotila, P. 1977. Lignicolous macrofungi from Turkey and Iran. – Karstenia **17**: 33-39. [176]
- Ocak, İ. 2001. [An investigation of myxomycetes flora in Erzurum, Bayburt, Gümüşhane cities and Trabzon – Giresun coast line]. PhD thesis. Atatürk Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Erzurum. (In Turkish) [177]
- Ocak, İ. & Hasenekoğlu, İ. 2003a. Myxomycetes from Erzurum, Bayburt and Gümüşhane provinces (Turkey). – Turkish Journal of Botany **27**: 223-226. [178]
- Ocak, İ. & Hasenekoğlu, İ. 2003b. Four new records of myxomycetes from Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany **27**: 333-337. [179]
- Ocak, İ. & Hasenekoğlu, İ. 2005. Myxomycetes from Trabzon and Giresun Provinces (Turkey). – Turkish Journal of Botany **29**: 11-21. [179a]
- Öder, N. 1972. [Taxonomic investigations of edible and poisonous mushrooms growing in Bolu province]. PhD thesis. Ankara Üniversitesi Tıp Fakültesi Botanik Kürsüsü, Ankara. (In Turkish) [180]
- Öder, N. 1976. [Some important edible mushrooms familiar with the people of inner Aegean and West Black Sea region]. – In: Türkiye I. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi, Yalova, 23-24 November 1976. Pp. 50-59. Yalova Atatürk Bahçe Kültürleri Merkez Araştırma Enstitüsü, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [181]
- Öder, N. 1978a. [Taxonomic investigations of some important edible and poisonous mushrooms growing in Black Sea region (between Sinop and Artvin provinces)]. Associate Professorship thesis. Ankara Üniversitesi Veteriner Fakültesi, Ankara. (In Turkish) [182]
- Öder, N. 1978b. [Taxonomic investigations of edible and poisonous mushrooms of Middle East and East Black Sea region]. – Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknik Araştırma Kurumu, project number: TBAG-217, Ankara. (In Turkish) [183]
- Öder, N. 1980. [Some important edible mushrooms using up by people]. – In: VII. Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknik Araştırma Kurumu Bilim Kongresi, Kuşadası, 6-10 October 1980. Pp. 785-798. Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknik Araştırma Kurumu, Ankara. (In Turkish) [184]
- Öder, N. 1982. [Some capped mushrooms growing in the vicinity of Kastamonu]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Fakültesi Dergisi **2**: 39-48. (In Turkish) [185]
- Öder, N. 1986. [The taxonomic investigations of some important poisonous mushrooms which grow in the region of Black Sea (between Sinop and Artvin)]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi **5**: 87-104. (In Turkish) [186]
- Öder, N. 1988a. [The taxonomic investigations of some important edible mushrooms known by the people which grow in the region of Black Sea]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi **8**: 215-236. (In Turkish) [187]
- Öder, N. 1988b. [The taxonomical investigations of important edible and poisonous mushrooms growing in the Konya center and some districts of Konya]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Dergisi **8**: 237-257. (In Turkish) [188]
- Öner, M. 1972. A contribution to the knowledge of common Turkish higher fungi. – Mycopathologia et Mycologia Applicata **47**(4): 369-373. [189]
- Oran, R.B. & Ergül, C.C. 2004. New records for the myxobiota of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany **28**: 511-515. [190]
- Özdal, S. 1999. [Identification of naturally grown mushrooms in certain forest areas of Ankara]. MSc thesis. Ankara Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Ankara. (In Turkish) [191]
- Öztürk, A., Demirel, K. & Arık, I. H. 1990. [Systematic, morphologic and ecologic investigations of poisonous and edible macrofungi growing in İnegöl (Bursa)]. – Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi **1**(1): 27-38. (In Turkish) [192]
- Öztürk, A., Demirel, K. & Uzun, Y. 1996. [Some edible mushrooms growing in Sarıkamış (Kars) Province]. – Yüzüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Ziraat Fakültesi Dergisi **6**(3): 113-128. (In Turkish) [193]
- Öztürk, C. 2002. [Two new records for macrofungus flora of Turkey]. – Ot Sistematik Botanik Dergisi **9**(1): 117-120. (In Turkish) [194]
- Öztürk, C. & Kaşık, G. 1996. [Macrofungi in Ürgüp district]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi **13**: 50-54. (In Turkish) [195]
- Öztürk, C., Kaşık, G. & Toprak, E. 1997. [Two new records of Ascomycetes for Turkey]. – Ot Sistematik Botanik Dergisi **4**(1): 53-56. (In Turkish) [196]
- Öztürk, C., Kaşık, G. & Doğan, H.H. 2000a. [Some macrofungi in Beyreli (Hadim-Konya) district]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi **1**: 37-41. (In Turkish) [197]
- Öztürk, C., Kaşık, G. & Yıldız, Y.K. 2000b. [Taxonomic studies of macrofungi of Hınıs and Karaçoban Counties (Erzurum)]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi **1**: 1-3. (In Turkish) [198]

- Öztürk, C., Doğan, H.H. & Kaşık, G. 2001a. [Additions to the macrofungus flora of Ermenek (Karaman)]. – Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Edebiyat Fakültesi Fen Dergisi 18: 61-66. (In Turkish) [199]
- Öztürk, C., Güner, M. & Doğan, H.H. 2001b. Two new records for the fungus flora of Turkey. – Ot Sistematiik Botanik Dergisi 8(2): 133-136. [200]
- Öztürk, C., Doğan, H.H., Aktaş, S. & Kaşık, G. 2002. New records for the macrofungi flora of Turkey from Ahırlı and Yalıhüyük districts (Konya). – Ot Sistematiik Botanik Dergisi 9(2): 135-148. [201]
- Öztürk, C., Doğan, H.H., Kaşık, G. & Aktaş, S. 2003a. [New records for Turkish mycoflora from Karaman province]. – Ot Sistematiik Botanik Dergisi 10(2): 213-248. (In Turkish) [202]
- Öztürk, C., Kaşık, G., Doğan, H.H. & Aktaş, S. 2003b. Macrofungi of Alanya district. – Turkish Journal of Botany 27: 303-312. [203]
- Pekşen, A. & Karaca, G.H. 2000a. [Macrofungi of Haciosman forest (Samsun)]. – Ot Sistematiik Botanik Dergisi 7(1): 211-218. (In Turkish) [204]
- Pekşen, A. & Karaca, G.H. 2000b. [Edible mushrooms found in Samsun province and their consumption potential]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye VI. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi Bildirileri, Bergama, 20-22 September 2000. Pp. 100-111. Ege Üniversitesi Bergama Meslek Yüksekokulu, İzmir. (In Turkish) [205]
- Pekşen, A. & Karaca, G.H. 2001. [Determination of the macrofungus flora of Samsun and Cultivation possibilities of some edible species]. – Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknik Araştırma Kurumu, project number: TOGTAG-1727, Ankara. (In Turkish) [206]
- Pekşen, A. & Karaca, G.H. 2003. Macrofungi of Samsun province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 27: 173-184. [207]
- Pilát, A.A. 1932. Contribution a l'etude des hymenomycetes de l'Asie Mineure. – Bulletin Trimestriel Society Mycologie France 48: 162-189. [208]
- Pilát, A.A. 1933a. Additamenta ad floram Asiae Minoris hymenomycetum parstertia: Meruliaceae, Hydnaceae, Stereaceae, Cyphellaceae, Cluvariaceae, Asterostromellinae. – Bulletin Trimestriel Society Mycologie France 49: 34-77. [209]
- Pilát, A.A. 1933b. Additamenta ad floram Asiae Minoris hymenomycetum pars secunda: Agaricinae. – Bulletin Trimestriel Society Mycologie France 49: 283-302. [210]
- Pilát, A.A. 1937. Additamenta ad floram Asiae Minoris hymenomycetum et gasteromycetum. – Bulletin Trimestriel Society Mycologie France 53: 253-264. [211]
- Selçuk, F., Aslantaş, I. & Huseyinov, E. 2000. The mushrooms of Sivas Province (Turkey). – In: Mycology and Cryptogamic Botany in Russia: traditions and modern state. Proceedings of the International Conference devoted to 100th anniversary of investigations on mycology and cryptogamic botany in V.I. Komarov Botanical Institute, RAS, Saint Petersburg, 24-28 April 2000. Pp. 309-310. V.I. Komarov Botanical Institute, RAS, Saint Petersburg. [212]
- Selik, M. 1962. [Some wood decaying fungi, especially *Schizophyllum commune* Fr., in the southwestern part of Turkey]. – İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi 12(2): 120-124. (In Turkish) [213]
- Selik, M. 1964. [Mycological notes from Belgrad forest]. – İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi 14(2): 129-135. (In Turkish) [214]
- Selik, M. 1965. [Edible mushrooms in Belgrad forest]. – İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi 15(2): 48-57. (In Turkish) [215]
- Selik, M. 1973a. [Wood decaying fungi in East Black Sea region especially Trabzon environments]. – İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi 23(2): 27-32. (In Turkish) [216]
- Selik, M. 1973b. [Wood decaying and disease causing fungi on Turkish woody plants, especially forest trees]. İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [217]
- Selik, M. & Aksu, S. 1967. [Wood decaying fungi attacking the native and foreigner trees in the parks and gardens of İstanbul]. – İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi 17(1): 89-101. (In Turkish) [218]
- Selik, M. & Sümer, S. 1982. [Some new additions to the Turkish mycoflora]. – İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi 32(2): 22-32. (In Turkish) [219]
- Sesli, E. 1993. [The macrofungi of Maçka district in Trabzon province]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 17: 179-182. (In Turkish) [220]
- Sesli, E. 1994a. [A taxonomic investigation of macromycetes grown in the region of Trabzon]. PhD thesis. Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Trabzon. (In Turkish) [221]
- Sesli, E. 1994b. [Macromycetes growing in Çaykara (Trabzon) district]. – In: N. Aktaç *et al.* [eds]. XII. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Edirne, 6-8 July 1994. P. 98. Trakya Üniversitesi, Edirne. (In Turkish) [222]
- Sesli, E. 1995. *Tulostoma brumale* Pers. ex Pers.: A new record of Gasteromycetes for Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 19: 599-600. [223]
- Sesli, E. 1996. Two new records of Agaricales for Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 20: 469-472. [224]
- Sesli, E. 1997. Two new records of cantharelloid fungi for Turkey. – Israel Journal of Plant Sciences 45: 71-74. [225]
- Sesli, E. 1998a. Ten new records of macrofungi for Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 22: 43-50. [226]
- Sesli, E. 1998b. Four interesting records of Pezizales of the macrofungus flora of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 22: 289-293. [227]
- Sesli, E. 1998c. [The macrofungi determined in the region of Giresun]. – In: M. Kılınç [ed.]. XIV. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Samsun, 7-10 September 1998. Pp. 456-465. Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi, Samsun. (In Turkish) [228]
- Sesli, E. 1999. [The macrofungi determined in A5 (Samsun-Bafra) and A6 (Ordu)]. – Ot Sistematiik Botanik Dergisi 6(1): 95-98. (In Turkish) [229]
- Sesli, E. & Baydar, S. 1995. A preliminary checklist of Russulaceae of Turkey. – Russulales News 5: 5-22. [230]
- Sesli, E. & Baydar, S. 1996. A preliminary checklist of Agaricales of Turkey. – Mycotaxon 60: 213-224. [231]
- Sesli, E. & Türkel, İ. 2000a. [Some edible mushrooms of East Black Sea region]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye VI. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi, Bergama, 20-22 September 2000. Pp. 262-264. Ege Üniversitesi Bergama Meslek Yüksekokulu, İzmir. (In Turkish) [232]
- Sesli, E. & Türkel, İ. 2000b. Three new records for the Turkish mycoflora. – Turkish Journal of Botany 24: 259-262. [233]
- Sesli, E. & Türkel, İ. 2000c. *Sepultaria sumneriana* (Cooke) Masseur – taxonomy, illustration and distribution. – Energy Education Science & Technology 6(1): 43-46. [234]
- Sesli, E. & Türkel, İ. (unpubl.). Some interesting fungi of Tokat province. [Presented on a poster during the Second Balkan Botanical Congress, İstanbul, 14-18 May 2000]. [235]
- Sesli, E. & Tüzen, M. 1999. Levels of trace elements in the fruiting bodies of macrofungi growing in the East Black Sea region of Turkey. – Food Chemistry 65: 453-460. [236]
- Sesli, E., Wright, J.E. & Türkel, İ. 2000. The genus *Tulostoma* Pers. : Pers. (Gasteromycetes) in Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 24: 269-272. [237]

- Solak, M.H. 1990. [Taxonomic investigations of some macrofungi growing in Bursa and its surroundings]. MSc thesis. Uludağ Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Bursa. (In Turkish) [238]
- Solak, M.H. 1996. Taxonomical investigations of some mushrooms distributed in İzmir. PhD thesis. Dokuz Eylül Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İzmir. [239]
- Solak, M.H. 1998. A new ascomycete genus (*Cyathipodia* Boud.) record for the fungus flora of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 22: 347-348. [240]
- Solak, M.H. & Gücin, F. 1990. [Some macrofungi from Bursa district]. – In: A. Çakır, S. Özyurt, S. Salman & M. Özkan [eds]. X. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Erzurum, 18-20 July 1990. Pp. 163-181. Atatürk Üniversitesi, Erzurum. (In Turkish) [241]
- Solak, M.H. & Gücin, F. 1992a. [Edible macrofungi of Bursa]. – In: A. Günay *et al.* [eds]. Türkiye IV. Yemeklik Mantar Kongresi, Yalova, 2-4 November 1992. Pp. 56-63. Yalova Atatürk Bahçe Kültürleri Merkez Araştırma Enstitüsü, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [242]
- Solak, M.H. & Gücin, F. 1992b. [New records of macrofungi for Turkey from Bursa district and other macrofungi found in the district]. – Turkish Journal of Botany 16: 335-346. (In Turkish) [243]
- Solak, M.H. & Yılmaz, F. 2002. [Contributions to the macrofungus flora of Manisa district]. – Ekoloji Çevre Dergisi 11(43): 30-32. (In Turkish) [244]
- Solak, M.H. & Yılmaz Ersel, F. 2003. [New records from Muğla province to the Turkish macromycota]. – Ekoloji 12(48): 10-12. (In Turkish) [245]
- Solak, M.H., Gücin, F., Işıloğlu, M. & Kalmış, E. 1997a. Wood-decaying fungi which were found in some provinces and their surroundings in the Northwest Anatolia. – In: XIth World Forestry Congress, Antalya, 13-22 October 1997. Pp. 199. Antalya. [246]
- Solak, M.H., Gücin, F., Işıloğlu, M. & Pacioni, G. 1997b. New record of *Geopora cooperi* Harkness f. *cooperi* Burdsall from West Asia (Turkey). – In: Second International Scientific Conference, Cairo, 17-20 March 1997. P. 56. Al-Azhar University, Cairo. [247]
- Solak, M.H., Işıloğlu, M., Gücin, F. & Gökler, I. 1999. Macrofungi of İzmir province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 23: 383-390. [248]
- Solak, M.H., Kalmış, E. & Işıloğlu, M. 2001a. New records for the fungus flora of Turkey. – Bio-Science Research Bulletin 17: 99-103. [249]
- Solak, M.H., Yılmaz, F. & Işıloğlu, M. 2001b. [Some *Morchella* species of Muğla district]. – In: IV. Ulusal Ekoloji ve Çevre Kongresi, Bodrum, 5-8 October 2001. Pp. 63. Bodrum. (In Turkish) [250]
- Solak, M.H., Gücin, F., Yılmaz, F. & Işıloğlu, M. 2002a. Some macrofungi from Çanakkale province. – Ot Sistematik Botanik Dergisi 10(1): 97-109. [251]
- Solak, M.H., Işıloğlu, M. & Pacioni, G. 2002b. A new record of *Geopora cooperi* f. *cooperi* from West Asia. – Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences 21B(2): 131-135. [252]
- Solak, M.H., Yılmaz Ersel, F., Gücin, F. & Işıloğlu, M. 2002c. Macrofungi of Balıkesir Province from Turkey. – Bio-Science Research Bulletin 18(2): 137-149. [252a]
- Stojchev, G., Asan, A. & Gücin, F. 1998. Some macrofungi species of European part of Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 22: 341-346. [253]
- Sümer, S. 1976. [Researches on important wood decaying fungi attacking cut woods in Belgrad forest]. – İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Dergisi 26(1): 175-236. (In Turkish) [254]
- Sümer, S. 1977. [The important fungi causing Decay of standing trees in the Belgrad forest]. – İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Yayınları, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [255]
- Sümer, S. 1982. [Wood-decaying fungi in the western Black Sea region of Turkey, especially in and around Bolu province]. İstanbul Üniversitesi Orman Fakültesi Yayınları, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [256]
- Sümer, S. 1987. [The edible mushrooms of Turkey]. Ersu Matbaacılık, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [257]
- Sümer, S. 1989. Some new records for the fungus flora of Turkey. – University of Marmara Journal of Sciences and Technology 6: 1-22. [258]
- Taşkın, H. 2000. [Studies on fungi causing rots in the wooden material of historical and plateau houses in Bolu province, Turkey]. PhD thesis. Marmara Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, İstanbul. (In Turkish) [259]
- Toprak, E. 1995. [Taxonomic investigations of macrofungi growing in Niğde]. MSc thesis. Selçuk Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Konya. (In Turkish) [260]
- Türkekel, İ. 2001. [A taxonomic investigation of macromycetes grown in the region of Tokat]. PhD thesis. Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Trabzon. (In Turkish) [261]
- Türkekel, İ. 2002. A new record for the mycoflora of Turkey. – Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences 21B(2): 147-148. [262]
- Türkekel, İ. 2003a. A contribution to the fungal flora of Tokat province. – Turkish Journal of Botany 27: 313-320. [263]
- Türkekel, İ. 2003b. *Arrhenia lobata* (Pers.: Fr.) Kühn. & Lamoure ex Redhead, a new record for Turkey. – Bio-Science Research Bulletin 19(2): 169-170. [264]
- Türkekel, İ. & Sesli, E. 2003. Macrofungi of Gümenek Picnic Area of Tokat province. – Bio-Science Research Bulletin 19(2): 117-120. [265]
- Uşak, M. 2001. [A taxonomic investigation of some macrofungi growing in Tavas (Denizli)]. MSc thesis. Pamukkale Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Denizli. (In Turkish) [266]
- Uzun, Y. 1996. [A taxonomic investigation of some macromycetes growing in Sarıkamış (Kars) district]. MSc thesis. Yüzcüncü Yıl Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Van. (In Turkish) [267]
- Uzun, Y. & Demirel, K. 1998. [Macrofungi of Şenkaya (Erzurum) Town]. – In: M. Kılınç [ed.]. XIV. Ulusal Biyoloji Kongresi, Samsun, 7-10 September 1998. Pp. 213-222. Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi, Samsun. (In Turkish) [268]
- Uzun, Y., Keleş, A., Demirel, K. & Solak, M.H. 2004. Some macrofungi from Bayburt Province in Turkey. – Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences 23(1): 47-55. [268a]
- Vlaev, K. 1915. [Contribution to the higher fungus flora of Turkish Thrace]. – Travaux de la Société Bulgare des Sciences Naturelles 8: 199-207. (In Bulgarian) [269]
- Watling, R. & Gregory, N.M. 1977. Larger fungi from Turkey, Iran and neighbouring countries. – Karstenia 17: 59-72. [270]
- Watling, R. & Işıloğlu, M. 1991. *Torrencia pulchella* Bres. A new and interesting record from Turkey. – Turkish Journal of Botany 15: 297-299. [271]
- Watling, R., Gücin, F. & Işıloğlu, M. 1995. *Battarraea phalloides* – its history, biology, and extension to its distribution. – Nova Hedwigia 60(1-2): 13-18. [272]
- Yağız, D., Ergül, C.C. & Afyon, A. 2002. [A study on the myxomycetes in Beşehir (Konya)]. – Ot Sistematik Botanik Dergisi 9(1): 137-141. (In Turkish) [273]
- Yalınkılıç, M.K., Kalay, Z., Karagül, R. & Sesli, E. 1992. [Investigations of *Morchella* spp. locally grown in the area of Yeşilova (Trabzon) village and their economical importance as secondary forest products]. – In: Y. Örs [ed.].

- Ulusal Orman Ürünleri Kongresi, Trabzon, 22-25 September 1992. Pp. 177-198. Karadeniz Teknik Üniversitesi, Trabzon. (In Turkish) [274]
- Yeşil, Ö.F. & Yıldız, A. 2004. Contributions to the macrofungi flora of Batman Province. – *Fırat Üniversitesi Fen ve Mühendislik Bilimleri Dergisi* **16**(1): 11-16. [275]
- Yıldız, A. & Ertekin, A.S. 1996. [Two new records of basidiomycetes for Turkey]. – *Ot Sistematik Botanik Dergisi* **3**(1): 55-58. (In Turkish) [276]
- Yıldız, A. & Ertekin, A.S. 1997. Contribution to the macrofungi flora of Diyarbakır. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* **21**: 119-122. [277]
- Yılmaz, F. 1995. [Researches based on taxonomy of mushrooms growing in Soma, Province of Manisa and Savaştepe, Province of Balıkesir]. MSc thesis. Balıkesir Üniversitesi Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Balıkesir. (In Turkish) [278]
- Yılmaz, F. & Işıloğlu, M. 2002. Macrofungi of Değirmenboğazı (Balıkesir). – *Turkish Journal of Botany* **26**: 161-164. [279]
- Yılmaz, F., Öder, N. & Işıloğlu, M. 1997. The macrofungi of the Soma (Manisa) and Savaştepe (Balıkesir) districts. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* **21**: 221-230. [280]
- Yılmaz, F., Merdivan, M. & Işıloğlu, M. 1999. Heavy metal contents in mushrooms in wayside having heavy traffic from Balıkesir in Turkey. – In: 37th IUPAC Congress, Berlin, 14-19 August 1999. P. 284. Berlin. [281]
- Yılmaz, F., Merdivan, M. & Işıloğlu, M. 2000a. [Trace metal accumulation in some mushrooms growing in Balıkesir district]. – In: XIV. Ulusal Kimya Kongresi, Diyarbakır, 10-15 September 2000. P. 375. Dicle Üniversitesi, Diyarbakır. (In Turkish) [282]
- Yılmaz, F., Merdivan, M. & Işıloğlu, M. 2000b. Trace metal accumulation in wild growing edible macrofungi in Balıkesir. – In: IIIrd Mediterranean Basin Conference on Analytical Chemistry, Antalya, 4-9 June 2000. P. 231. Turkish Chemical Society, Antalya. [283]
- Yılmaz, F., Işıloğlu, M. & Merdivan, M. 2003. Heavy metal levels in some macrofungi. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* **27**: 45-56. [284]
- Yılmaz Ersel, F. & Solak, M.H. 2004a. Contributions to the macrofungi of İzmir Province. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* **28**: 487-490. [285]
- Yılmaz Ersel, F. & Solak, M.H. 2004b. Three new records for the Turkish macromycota. – *Ekoloji* **13**(52): 7-8. [286]
- Yılmaz Ersel, F. & Solak, M.H. 2004c. New records of morels from Turkey. – *Mycotaxon* **91**: 293-302. [286a]
- Yılmaz Ersel, F., Solak, M.H. & Gücin, F. 2003. Two new records from Anatolia. – *Bio-Science Research Bulletin* **19**(2): 83-85. [287]
- Zeybek, N. 1968. [About *Morchella* cf. *conica* species growing in West Anatolia]. – In: VI. Milli Türk Biyoloji Kongresi, 15-21 August 1968. Pp. 197-201. Ege Üniversitesi, İzmir. (In Turkish) [288]

References

- Baytop, A. 1994. A list of publications on Turkish macrofungi. – *Turkish Journal of Botany* **18**: 175-185.
- Ergül, C.C. & Dülger, B. 2000. Myxomycetes of Turkey. – *Karstenia* **40**: 39-41.
- Kirk, P.M. & Ansell, A.E. 1992. Authors of fungal names. International Mycological Institute, CABI, Wallingford.
- Kirk, P.M., Cannon, P.F., David, J.C. & Stalpers, J.A. [eds] 2001. Dictionary of the fungi. 9th edn. CAB International, Oxon.
- Kirk, P.M. *et al.* 2004. Authors of fungal names. CABI Bioscience, Wallingford. Electronic version: <http://www.speciesfungorum.org/AuthorsOfFungalNames.htm>.
- Lannoy, G. & Estadès, A. 1995. Monographie des *Leccinum* d'Europe. Fédération Mycologique Dauphiné-Savoie.
- Sesli, E. & Baydar, S. 1995. A preliminary checklist of Russulaceae of Turkey. – *Russulales News* **5**: 5-22.
- Sesli, E. & Baydar, S. 1996. A preliminary checklist of Agaricales of Turkey. – *Mycotaxon* **60**: 213-224.